

SysMus25 Conference Proceedings

June 11th – 13th 2025
RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies
in Rhythm, Time and Motion
University of Oslo, Norway

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Editorial Note

It is with great pleasure that we present the official conference proceedings of the 18th International Conference of Students of Systematic Musicology (SysMus25). This conference proceedings contains abstracts accepted for spoken and poster presentations at the SysMus25 conference hosted at the RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies in Rhythm, Time, and Motion, University of Oslo, from June 11-13, 2025.

Abbigail Fleckenstein, Hugh Alexander von Arnim, & Anna-Maria Christodoulou

About SysMus

The SysMus conferences are annual events organized by PhD students for PhD and master's students whose research relates to the field systematic musicology. These conferences provide an invaluable opportunity for early researchers to come together and share their research with peers and receive feedback on their work in a supportive academic environment. Each SysMus conference invites internationally renowned researchers from the various subfields of systematic musicology to present their work and engage with student attendees. The field of systematic musicology covers a wide range of research topics including music perception, music cognition, music psychology, music therapy, music modelling, music information retrieval, musical acoustics, music theory and analysis, music sociology, music education, music technology, music and culture, music and semiotics, and music philosophy. For more information about the SysMus conference series, please visit: <https://sites.google.com/view/sysmus/home>

About RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies in Rhythm, Time, and Motion

The RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies in Rhythm, Time, and Motion is a Norwegian Center of Excellence based at the University of Oslo. RITMO's research integrates methods from psychology, musicology, and informatics to investigate rhythm as a fundamental property of human cognition, behavior, and culture. In addition to world-class research facilities, including motion capture studios, brain imaging suites, and robotics labs, RITMO is home to a highly diverse, international group of researchers and takes pride in connecting various areas of academia. For more information about RITMO, please visit: <https://www.uio.no/ritmo/>

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Hugh Alexander von Arnim
Maham Riaz

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Sandra Solli
Prof. Jonna Vuoskoski (Academic Supervisor)

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Thank you to all our reviewers for your vital contribution to SysMus25.

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SysMus25 is generously supported by: RITMO through the Research Council of Norway's Centers of Excellence scheme, UiO: Life Science, the European Society for the Cognitive Sciences of Music (ESCOM), the Society for Education, Music and Psychology Research (Sempre), and the SysMus24 Organizing Committee at University of Jyväskylä. We extend our deepest gratitude to all our sponsors for making SysMus25 possible!

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Program

Day 1 - June 11th

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
09:00–09:30	Morning coffee and name tag pick-up	Forsamlingssalen
09:30–10:00	Opening Remarks	Forsamlingssalen
10:00–11:00	Keynote 1 Ecomusicking: How Musical Encounters Shape Environmental Thinking Professor Nicola Dibben	Forsamlingssalen
11:00–11:10	Break	
11:10–12:00	Talk Session 1: Music, Social Connection, and Emotional Wellbeing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bruna Martins: <i>The Choir Experiences of People Affected by Homelessness</i>• Catherine Tan: <i>Tunes and Technology: A Lifespan Comparison on Uses and Attitudes Towards Music Technologies for Mood Regulation</i>• Dana Greaves: <i>Examining the Psychosocial Effects of Singing in VR: A Mixed-Methods RCT Pilot Study</i>	Forsamlingssalen
12:00–13:00	Lunch	Psychosocial
13:00–13:50	Talk Session 2: Psychological and Embodied Aspects of Music Performance <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pedro Palhares: <i>Discerning the Real-time Effects of Mind Wandering on Musical Creativity</i>• Cheryl Ockrant: <i>Feeling Safe Vs. Being Safe: Music Performance Anxiety and Polyvagal Theory</i>• Liliana Aparício: <i>The Importance of Body Awareness in Accordion Learning and Performance</i>	Forsamlingssalen
13:50–14:00	Break	
14:00–14:50	Poster Session 1 Serena Allegra, Rodrigo Almonte, Cesc Bayle, Oliver Tab Bellmann, James Cannon, Francesca Cantoni, Francisco Cossavella, Tyler Davis, Rhun Gwilym, Florian Hoesl, Veeda Kala, Fruzsina Mihok, Jonathan Stumber, Marko Vesić	Forsamlingssalen
14:50–15:00	Break	

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
15:00–15:50	Talk Session 3: Neural Mechanisms of Musical Timing, Rhythm, and Memory <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ligia Silva: <i>Exploring Time Perception in Music Listening</i>• Ana Marta Aguiar: <i>Mind the Bar</i>• Sandra Solli: <i>Rhythm-based Temporal Expectations</i>	Forsamlings salen
15:50–16:00	Break	
16:00–17:00	Workshops 1 & 2 (parallel sessions) Workshop 1: Concert Listening: Qualitative, Phenomenological Inquiry Workshop 2: Human-Swarm Interactive Music Systems	Auditorium 3 Forsamlings salen
18:30–19:30	Welcome Swing Dance (Optional Social Activity)	Chateau Neuf

Day 2 - June 12th

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
09:00–09:30	Morning Coffee	Forsamlingssalen
09:30–10:30	Keynote 2 Computational Modeling of Music Information: Connecting Musicological Inquiries on Musical Structures with Developing Interactive Technologies to Foster Music Engagement Professor Anja Volk	Forsamlingssalen
10:30–10:40	Break	
10:40–11:30	Talk Session 4: Music Applications for Health and Stress Management <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Silvia Genovese: <i>The Impact of Individual Factors and Preferences on Music for Sleep</i>• Yuting Wu: <i>Soundscapes for Stress Regulation: A Multi-Modal Investigation of Psychophysiological Responses to Environmental Audio Stimuli in Hong Kong Workplaces</i>• Tristan Eissing: <i>How Music Can Jeopardise the Abstinence of Individuals with Substance Use Disorder</i>	Forsamlingssalen
11:30–11:40	Break	
11:40–12:30	Talk Session 5: Cross-Cultural Perspectives in Music Cognition and Perception <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Jonathan Tang: <i>Favorite Tunes, Cultural Clues: Self-Construction and Musical Rewards</i>• Nashra Ahmad: <i>Effect of Length of the Rhythmic Cycle on its Perception and Learning: A Cross-Cultural Exploration through North-Indian Rhythmic Patterns</i>• Keerthana Vishwanath: <i>Comparing Absolute Pitch Recognition Between Western and Carnatic Musicians</i>	Forsamlingssalen
12:30–13:30	Lunch	Psychosocial
13:30–14:50	Poster Session 2 Nashra Ahmad, Chiara Apa, Athanasia Kontouli, Anastasiya Kryvanos, Adam Lewartowski, Marion Boudet, Annalisa Mazzolari, Nandhini Natarajan, Styliani Papadamou, Gabriela Sarmiento-Cabrera, Joana Sayal, Michael Solomon Williams, Hazel Van Der Walle, Merel Van Heeswijk, Melina Witt, Lulin Yang, Tiannan Ye, Yue You, Lijun Zhang	Forsamlingssalen
14:50–15:00	Break	

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
15:00–15:50	Talk Session 6: Music Interventions for Aging and Neurological Conditions <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Marietta Ungerer: <i>Emotional-Motivational Functions of Musical Imagery in Parkinson's</i>• Heini Siltainsuu: <i>Becoming Me with Music - A Qualitative Investigation of Older Adults' Autobiographical Narratives on Music, Identity and Wellbeing</i>• Poulami Kar: <i>Understanding Neurological Music Therapy: An Intervention for Parkinson's through Diffusion Tensor Imaging</i>	Forsamlingsalen
15:50–16:00	Break	
16:00–17:00	Workshops 3 & 4 (parallel sessions) Workshop 3: Coherence and Cause – Exploratory analysis strategies for physiological measurements from live concert participants Workshop 4: Dancing Puzzle: Reconstructing a dance through collective kinesthetic memory	Auditorium 3 Forsamlingsalen
18:30–21:30	Conference Dinner	Barcode Street Food (Cocktail Bar)

Day 3 - June 13th

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
09:00–09:30	Morning Coffee	Forsamlingssalen
09:30–10:30	Keynote 3 Measuring Chills... “defrosting” and “dissecting” them Professor Bruno Laeng	Forsamlingssalen
10:30–10:40	Break	
10:40–11:30	Talk Session 7: Children and Adolescent Musical Experiences <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Caroline Owen: <i>Children’s Free Descriptions of Subjective Responses to Selected Musical Extracts Reveal New Taxonomy of Music-evoked Experience</i>• Katariina Henttonen: <i>Finnish Adolescents’ Experiences of Scary Music: A Qualitative Study</i>• Alicia Lucendo Noriega: <i>The Role of Non-formal Musical and Sports Engagement in Children’s Development</i>	Forsamlingssalen
11:30–11:40	Break	
11:40–12:30	Talk Session 8: Music’s Influence on Cognitive and Emotional Processing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Hazel van der Walle: <i>Thoughtscapes in Music: An Examination of Thought Types Occurring During Music Listening Across 17 Genres</i>• Mitia Ganade D’Acol: <i>Kinetic Affect and the Construction of Musical Emotions</i>	Forsamlingssalen
12:30–13:30	Lunch	Psychosocial
13:30–14:20	Talk Session 9: Methodological Approaches and Theoretical Frameworks in Music Psychology <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Laura Serra Marin: <i>Psychophysiological and Biomechanical Methods in Music Skill Acquisition: A Systematic Review</i>• Connor Kirts: <i>DEEM Instrument: Content Validity Assessments Using Subject Experts</i>• Oliver Tab Bellmann: <i>The Origins of Musicality and Music Through an Extended Evolutionary Lens</i>	Forsamlingssalen
14:20–14:30	Break	

Time UTC+2	Activities	Location
14:30–15:20	Talk Session 10: Computational Modeling and Analysis Methods in Music Research <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rhun Gwilym: <i>A New Way of Thinking: A Proposed Methodology for EDM (Electronic Dance Music) Analysis</i>• Joshua Frank: <i>Modeling Individual Differences in Chord Pleasantness Judgments</i>• Samuel Morgan: <i>Active Preference Learning for Musical Stimuli</i>	Forsamlingsalen
15:20–15:30	Break	
15:30–16:20	Panel Discussion: Wellbeing During a PhD Moderator: Liv Merve Abrahamsson Panellists: Anna Maria Christodoulou, Jonathan Tang, Persefoni Tzanaki	Forsamlingsalen
16:20–16:50	Closing Remarks	Forsamlingsalen
17:00–18:00	Parting Springer Dance (Optional Social Activity)	Forsamlingsalen

Keynotes

Ecomusicking: How Musical Encounters Shape Environmental Thinking

Professor Nicola Dibben

University of Sheffield, Sheffield, United Kingdom

Time: June 11th, 10:00 – 11:00 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67394295763>

Computational Modeling of Music Information: Connecting Musicological Inquiries on Musical Structures with Developing Interactive Technologies to Foster Music Engagement

Professor Anja Volk

Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands

Time: June 12th, 09:30 – 10:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68332075785>

Measuring Chills... “defrosting” and “dissecting” them

Professor Bruno Laeng

University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

Time: June 13th, 09:30 – 10:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67606774782>

Workshops

Workshop 1 — Concert Listening: Qualitative, Phenomenological Inquiry

Dr. Remy Haswell-Martin

London College of Music, University of West London, London, UK

Time: June 11th, 16:00 – 17:00 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67394295763>

Workshop 2 — Human-Swarm Interactive Music Systems: Implementation and data analysis using Python

Pedro P. Lucas

RITMO, Department of Informatics, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

Time: June 11th, 16:00 – 17:00 UTC+2

Location: Auditorium 3, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/69264043362>

Workshop 3 — Coherence and Cause — Exploratory analysis strategies for physiological measurements from live concert participants

Finn Upham, Ph.D.

RITMO, Department of Musicology, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

Time: June 12th, 16:00 – 17:00 UTC+2

Location: Auditorium 3, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68879919588>

Workshop 4 — Dancing puzzle: reconstructing a dance through collective kinesthetic memory

Diego Marín Bucio

RITMO, Department of Musicology, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

Time: June 12th, 16:00 – 17:00 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68332075785>

Talk Session 1

Music, Social Connection, and Emotional Wellbeing

Chair: James Cannon

Time: June 11th, 11:00 – 12:00 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67394295763>

The Choir Experiences of People Affected by Homelessness

Bruna Francisco Martins

University of Leeds, Leeds, United Kingdom

Background Housing instability is associated with multilevel issues related to social, psychological, and health challenges. A wealth of research highlights the positive impacts of participating in artistic activities for people affected by homelessness. Impacts are associated with the social, emotional, and cognitive well-being of people who have, in some way, experienced unstable housing situations. In a smaller number, studies about choirs and homelessness also indicate similar outcomes. Choirs can become safe spaces where these populations develop social connections and a sense of belonging (Bailey and Davidson, 2005), strengthening their voices and perspectives for the future (Boal-Palheiros, 2017). However, less attention has been taken to investigating the diverse ways in which people affected by homelessness engage in choirs, and the impacts these forms of engagement might play on the perceived impacts.

Aim To explore the ways in which people affected by homelessness engage in choirs and the possible outcomes of their engagement.

Methods Observations of choir rehearsals in six cities in the UK were conducted, and further observations will be carried out from January to March 2025 in a new choir. All observed choirs are aimed at people affected by homelessness, and most of their participants are currently experiencing or have faced housing insecurity. The researcher adopts the role of 'participant observer' (Robson, 2024), engaging in singing while observing behaviours and interactions.

Expected Results Data analysis is currently underway. Notes from all observations have been formally analysed according to nine categories proposed by Spradley (2016) to describe observations: space, actors, activities, objects, acts, events, time, goals and feelings. This strategy will contribute to the identification of diverse ways by which choir members engage in choirs, including observation of proactive or passive roles and their involvement with the music and with others. Comments collected during the rehearsal will support the findings, helping to understand feelings, and impacts perceived by members.

Conclusions Implications of this project concern improved understanding of singing group activities designed for populations affected by homelessness.

References

Bailey, B. A., & Davidson, J. W. (2005). Effects of group singing and performance for marginalized and middle-class singers. *Psychology of Music*, 33(3), 269-303. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735605053734>

Boal-Palheiros, G. (2017). Singing Against Loneliness: Songs of a homeless choir in Porto. *Music and Arts in Action*, 6, 63–79.

Robson, C. (2024). *Real World Research*. Wiley.

Spradley, J. P. (2016). *Participant observation*. Waveland Press.

Tunes and technology: A lifespan comparison on uses and attitudes towards music technologies for mood regulation

Catherine Tan¹, Laura Cirelli², Suvi Saarikallio¹

¹University of Jyväskylä, Jyväskylä, Finland

²University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

Background Music listening often supports mood regulation; however, the practice may differ musically and psychologically based on listeners' individual differences (Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2007; Saarikallio & Erkkilä, 2007; Tan & Harrison, 2025). In today's technological era, music streaming and listening technologies have altered music consumption behaviours and show potential in supporting personalised mood regulation practices (Agres et al., 2021; Avdeeff, 2012; Goldschmitt & Seaver, 2019; Krause & North, 2016). Nevertheless, little is known about how the use of, and attitudes toward, music and technology as tools for well-being differ across the lifespan.

Aims This study aims to reveal how music mood regulation compares musically, socially, and technologically across different life stages. We also explore how background variables (i.e., age, sensitivity to musical reward, life satisfaction, resilience) predict the usage of different music mood regulation strategies and their contexts. Lastly, we aim to identify future directions for improving music technologies for mood regulation.

Methods An online questionnaire collected demographic details and data on the musical, social, and technological context of seven music mood regulation scenarios, each based on a music mood regulation strategy (Saarikallio & Erkkilä, 2007). Open-ended responses on participants' attitudes towards incorporating music technologies into their music mood regulation practices were also collected alongside measures on the aforementioned background variables.

Expected Results Data analysis will focus on identifying characteristics in the music selected for mood regulation across the life stages and how technologies used for music access and listening may support or hinder the experience. Furthermore, demographic details and measures from participant profiles will be assessed as predictive factors in relation to these themes.

Conclusions This research will provide new knowledge on the psychological underpinnings of music mood regulation and their social and technological contexts. Furthermore, it will establish guidelines for the development of music technologies that can meet diverse emotional and psychological needs to support the develop-

ment of healthy and resilient individuals.

References

- Agres, K. R., Schaefer, R. S., Volk, A., van Hooren, S., Holzapfel, A., Dalla Bella, S., Müller, M., de Witte, M., Herremans, D., Ramirez Melendez, R., Neerincx, M., Ruiz, S., Meredith, D., Dimitriadis, T., & Magee, W. L. (2021). Music, computing, and health: A roadmap for the current and future roles of music technology for health care and well-being. *Music & Science*, 4, 2059204321997709. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2059204321997709>
- Avdeeff, M. (2012). *Technological engagement and musical eclecticism: An examination of contemporary listening practices*, 9(2).
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T., & Furnham, A. (2007). Personality and music: Can traits explain how people use music in everyday life? *British Journal of Psychology*, 98(2), 175–185. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000712606X111177>
- Goldschmitt, K. E., & Seaver, N. (2019). Shaping the stream: Techniques and troubles of algorithmic recommendation. In D. Trippett, M. M. Ingalls, & N. Cook (Eds.), *The Cambridge Companion to Music in Digital Culture* (pp. 63–81). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316676639.006>
- Krause, A. E., & North, A. C. (2016). Music listening in everyday life: Devices, selection methods, and digital technology. *Psychology of Music*, 44(1), 129–147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735614559065>
- Saarikallio, S., & Erkkilä, J. (2007). The role of music in adolescents' mood regulation. *Psychology of Music*, 35(1), 88–109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735607068889>
- Tan, C., & Harrison, P. (2025). What music do people use for mood regulation? OSF. https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/t4w5d_v1
- Tan, C., & Harrison, P. (2025). What music do people use for mood regulation? OSF. https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/t4w5d_v1

Examining the Psychosocial Effects of Singing in VR: A Mixed-Methods RCT Pilot Study

Dana Greaves¹, Catherine O'Neill^{1,2}, Lina Gega¹, Helena Daffern¹

¹University of York, York, United Kingdom

²University of Lincoln, Lincoln, United Kingdom

Background In recent years, there have been many studies showing that singing in a group, virtually or face-to-face, can positively affect many facets of an individual's health. In particular, group singing has been shown to be an important and effective tool for maintaining an individual's wellbeing and mental health through supporting social connectivity, providing a pleasurable leisure activity, increasing mood, self-esteem, confidence, and feelings of empowerment, reducing negative affects such as anxiety and loneliness, creating life meaning, and improving quality of life. Interestingly, one of the most common psychosocial benefits being reported in virtual group singing (VGS) activities is social connection although this result may have been influenced by a majority of research on this topic being conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Aims The aim of this study is to examine a) the differences between active and passive musicking/solo and group singing in VGS experiences hosted in VR, b) the extent to which VR group singing experiences that involve no face-to face social interaction affect wellbeing, self-esteem, social connectedness, and mood, and c) the psychosocial potential and interest of hosting VGS in VR for young adult populations. Overall, this study intends to answer the question: if in-person social interaction is removed, can participation in VR group singing experiences still impact psychosocial health?

Methods The current study is a mixed methods pilot that involves participants engaging with a singing activity in VR over 2-weeks. Methods include a pre-post, within- and between-groups, four-arm RCT and qualitative analysis. Each participant is assigned one of three conditions (singing with a choir, watching a choir, or singing alone) and participates in a waitlist condition for 2-weeks before starting the study for a total of 4-weeks of participation. Participants are instructed to engage with a pre-recorded, VR group singing experience according to their assigned condition and asked to complete a series of pre- and post- forms which measure the socio-psychological effects of their engagement and asked open-ended questions about their experiences.

Expected Results It is hypothesized that there will be a positive, significant relationship between participating in singing activities and wellbeing, mood, and self-

esteem. Social connectedness is expected to have no significant changes across conditions. If these hypotheses are correct, this may indicate that the lack of social interactions within VGS experiences does not necessarily hinder the satisfaction of the experience or ability to ascertain certain psychological benefits through that participation. Therefore, this type of singing activity can be beneficial to certain populations with certain goals outside of creating community or social connection.

Conclusions The implications of this study may provide insights into the functions of socialising and musicking in VGS experiences which may inform our understanding of how group singing as an instinctive, human activity promotes individual and collective health. As VGS research continues in a post-COVID 19 world, the accessibility and target demographics of varying VGS technologies should be considered. Further understanding these relationships between singing and psychosocial health can inform the future directions of this research and technology.

Talk Session 2

Psychological and Embodied Aspects of Music Performance

Chair: Kjell Andreas Oddekalv

Time: June 11th, 13:00 – 13:50 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67394295763>

Discerning the real-time effects of mind wandering on musical creativity: A psycho-phenomenological study of jazz improvisation

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Background Mind wandering (MW) is a prevalent and ubiquitous phenomenon (Smallwood & Schooler, 2015) that despite its negative effects on cognitive processes like working memory, sustained attention, or response inhibition, has found in later years increasing evidence that it could play a key role in creative cognition. While several studies suggest that MW benefits creativity if it occurs in the incubation period of a creative problem-solving task (Baird et al., 2012; Leszczynski et al., 2017), it remains unclear if MW during the course of a creative task does benefit the real-time expression of creative behaviour (Hao et al., 2015). Musical improvisation provides an ecologically useful framework for studying the real-time effects of MW on creativity. Indeed, a recent preliminary study by the present authors suggested that MW during a jazz improvisation task enhanced the creativity of musical improvisation in expert pianists, compared with improvisation during on-task attention (Palhares, Branco & Gonçalves, 2021).

Aims Here, we aim to replicate these findings with a bigger sample size and a more refined experience sampling methodology that not only captures mind wandering, but also other off-task thought phenomena, namely mind blanking and task-related interference. Therefore, we ultimately aim to discern the real-time impact of each type of off-task phenomena on ongoing musical creativity.

Methods 52 jazz musicians (piano, guitar, double-bass, voice, vibraphone, saxophone, trumpet and violin) of various levels of expertise underwent a series of jazz improvisation tasks interleaved with random experience sampling probes.

Expected Results We expect to replicate previous findings of MW-associated enhancement of musical creativity. We also expect that this effect will be more prevalent in proficient musicians, compared to novices. Finally, we expect that mind blanking and task-related interference will pose instances of off-task thought that do not positively affect improvisatory performance.

Conclusions Should we obtain our expected results, this investigation will sediment our previous claim that mind wandering during improvisation is associated with a significant increase in musical creativity. It will also provide the first account of the real-time impact of different attentional states on musical performance.

References

- Baird, B., Smallwood, J., Mrazek, M. D., Kam, J. W. Y., Franklin, M. S., & Schooler, J. W. (2012). Inspired by distraction: Mind wandering facilitates creative incubation. *Psychological Science*, 23(10), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797612446024>
- Hao, N., Wu, M., Runco, M. A., & Pina, J. (2015). More mind wandering, fewer original ideas: Be not distracted during creative idea generation. *Acta Psychologica*, 161, 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2015.09.001>
- Leszczynski, M., Chaieb, L., Reber, T. P., Derner, M., Axmacher, N., & Fell, J. (2017). Mind wandering simultaneously prolongs reactions and promotes creative incubation. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 10197. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-10616-3>
- Palhares, P. T., Branco, D., & Gonçalves, Ó. F. (2022). Mind wandering and musical creativity in jazz improvisation. *Psychology of Music*, 50(4), 1212–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03057356211033346>
- Smallwood, J., & Schooler, J. W. (2015). The science of mind wandering: Empirically navigating the stream of consciousness. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 66(1), 487–518. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010814-015331>

Feeling Safe Vs. Being Safe: Music Performance Anxiety and Polyvagal Theory

Cheryl Ockrant

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Background Following decades of trauma-induced instrumental shutdown, this cellist experimented in a self-directed renewal process of carefully starting over, using the idea of rewiring her brain to be newly acquainted with her instrument. Subsequently, she conducted a research study to investigate the neurophysiological mechanisms that enabled her to recondition neural pathways and restore her performance ability. The discovery of Polyvagal Theory further solidified her research in rebuilding trust and creativity in personal instrumental practice including the use of free-improvisation. Polyvagal Theory describes the science to understanding how the vagus nerve- one part of this system which connects the brain to the heart to the belly- relates to our human ability to connect and communicate with each other, and reaches beyond the exterior effects of anxieties around performance.

Aims This presentation will begin by outlining the interplay of trauma, body memory, vulnerability, and shame in the context of performing arts, by examining Polyvagal Theory and its relevance to safety and creativity. I will discuss how we, as performers, artists, and human beings, must begin from the place of extreme anxiety to a place of acceptance and understanding of the hierarchy of the central nervous system, so that we can begin to work with it rather than against it. Using the principles of Polyvagal Theory, performance anxiety can be addressed and pre-empted using specific exercises in a step-by-step process. This approach is a bottom-up method, meaning the body memory dictates the 'story' to the brain. A brief outline of these exercises will be addressed.

Main Contribution With the right tools, rebuilding trust and autonomy in the privacy of the practice room can build social engagement and creativity where musicians had previously left the craft.

Implications Many areas of severe performance anxiety relate to and cross paths with addiction, depression, and isolation. Research in rebuilding musical engagement may have lasting effect in other areas.

The importance of body awareness in Accordion learning and performance

Liliana Aparício

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Background Playing a musical instrument requires many hours of daily study to achieve an excellence level in musical performance (Fonseca, 2000). However, prolonged and repetitive study, without organization, planning or structure, becomes a relevant factor for the appearance of musculoskeletal injuries and pain (Brandfonbrener, 2000 and Manchester, 2006). The literature revealed that the musicians' prevalence of pain can reach 90% (Silva et al., 2015). In addition to the physical issues, studies also refer neurological and psychological conditions (Silva et al., 2015; Kok et al., 2016). Playing accordion also have some issues, such as the weight, the considerable size and the asymmetric body posture to perform it (Aparício, 2014). This suggests the need to rethink the accordion *curriculum* (Wijsman and Ackermann, 2018) and to implement and evaluate strategies that promote body awareness and healthy study habits (technically and expressively) (Lennon and Reed, 2012), to promote health and quality in musical performance (Dick et al., 2013; Bergeron et al., 2015) and its sustainability throughout the performer's life (Norton et al., 2015a, b).

Aims The main study aims are to: a) understand the importance of the body awareness in accordion learning; b) to know how the performers' own body awareness can optimize and influence an expressive, performative and artistic accordion learning and practice and b) characterize how the implications of pedagogical practice, the structuring of an official accordion course and the choice of repertoire, focused on the instrumentalist's body awareness, influence the accordion learning/performance.

Methods This empirical study will have two phases. Phase 1 will be a comparative evaluation of music teaching *curricula* at conservatory and higher education levels between Portugal and foreign peer institutions, focusing on the issue of preparing the instrumentalist's health during their academic training process. Phase 2 will involve carrying out semi-structured interviews with accordion teachers and/or national and international accordionists who have a relevant teaching or performing career in this field.

Expected Results The dearth of knowledge about health in music education among instrument teachers perpetuates a cycle of lack of health awareness. This may suggest the need to implement and evaluate strategies that promote healthy study

habits, including issues of technical and expressive execution, but also of preparation for performance. So, it is necessary to do teacher training in this specific area and to rethink about the accordion curriculum and official course at Conservatories and Universities. In the specific case of the accordion in Portugal, it is expected to change the official accordion curriculum. For this, it would be also helpful to understand what is being done in other countries and to know what strategies can also be implemented in Portugal to improve the accordion curriculum.

Conclusion Noting that it is still necessary to evaluate and implement strategies to improve body awareness when learning to play the accordion, it is crucial to implement training and raising awareness among teachers and students about this topic. It is necessary to improve the quality of physical and mental health in musical learning and performance.

References

- Aparício, L. (2014) Postura, Dor e Percepção de esforço na aprendizagem do acordeão. Tese de Mestrado. Pol. Aveiro: Universidade de Aveiro
- Bergeron, M.F., Mounjoy, m., Armstrong, N. et al. (2015) International Olympic Committee consensus statement on youth athletic development. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 49, 843-851.
- Brandfonbrener, A. (2000) "Epidemiology and risk factors" in R. Tubiana e P. Amadio (eds). *Medical problems of the instrumentalist musician*, pp. 171-194. Londres: Martin Dunitz Ltd.
- Dick, R., Berning, J.R., Dawson, W. et al. (2013) Athletes and the arts- the role of sports medicine in the performing arts. *Current Sports Medicine Reports*, 12, 397-403.
- Fonseca, E. Q. and Andrade, J.G.M. (2000) Artista-A atleta: Reflexões sobre a utilização do corpo na performance dos instrumentos de cordas. *Revista Per Music*, 2:118-128.
- FRY, H. (1987) Prevalence of overuse (injury) syndrome in Australian music schools. *British Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 44, 35-40.
- Kok, L. M. et al. (2016) The occurrence of musculoskeletal complaints among professional musicians: a systematic review. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 89, 373-396.
- Lennon, M. e Reed, (2012) Instrumental and vocal teacher education: competences, roles and curricula. *Music Education Research*, 14, 285-308.
- MANCHESTER, R. (2006) Toward better prevention of injuries among performing artists. *Medical Problems of Performing Artists*, 21 (1): 1-2.
- Manchester, R. (2006) Toward better prevention of injuries among performing artists. *Medical Problems of Performing Artists*, 21(1):1-2.

Norton, N., Ginsborg, J., Greasley, A. e McEwan, I. (2015a) Instrumental and vocal music teacher's view on a multi-disciplinary team approach to health promotion for musicians. In Ginsborg, J., Lamont, A., Phillips, M. e Bramley, S., Eds. Proceedings of the Ninth Triennial Conference of the European Society for the Cognitive Sciences of Music, pp. 605- 611.

Norton, N., Ginsborg, J., Greasley, A. e McEwan, I. (2015b) Health and wellness education for musicians- Investigating music teacher's perspectives. In Ginsborg, J., Lamont, A., Phillips, M. e Bramley, S., Eds. Proceedings of the Ninth Triennial Conference of the European Society for the Cognitive Sciences of Music, pp. 612-615.

Silva, A.G., Lã, F. M. and Afreixo, V. (2015) Pain prevalence in instrumental musicians: a systematic review. *Med Probl Perform Art*, 30(1):8-19.

Wijisman, S. e Ackermann, J. (2018) Educating Australian musicians: are we playing it safe? *Health Promotion International*. Doi: 10.1093/heapro/day030 Perspectives.

Poster Session 1

Time: June 11th, 14:00 – 14:50 UTC+2

Location:

Online Presentation: <https://sysmus25.virtualpostersession.org/>

Lo ferm voler qu'el cor m'intra: the unexpected result of a dice roll

Serena Allegra

Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy

Background The composition *Lo ferm voler qu'el cor m'intra* by Arnaut Daniel marks the birth of the lyric sestina, a fixed form of six stanzas (coblas) with six endecasyllabic verses each, plus a three-verse leave-taking (tornada). The sestina is notable for its absence of a conventional rhyme scheme, with the six ending words of the first stanza repeating in a set sequence across the stanzas (ABCDEF, FAEBDC, CFDABE, etc.). However, *Lo ferm voler* contains peculiarities that need to be reinterpreted within the context of the trobador's oral performance (Mayo, 2012). The piece's significance lies not in formal contrivances, but in the composer's intent to infuse the performance with his passion for gambling (Marchis, 2009).

Aims The dice are not only an aesthetic feature but connect to the mental states of the game, involving the audience. According to Schechner (2013), it is not the stage that defines the performance, but rather everyday actions, which hold a performative dimension where we replay behaviors. Therefore, *Lo ferm voler qu'el cor m'intra* can be seen as a form of gamification: Arnaut Daniel aimed to transcribe the dice game into music, creating a blend of musical, prosodic, and semantic effects.

Main Contributions An analysis of the text reveals a consistent permutation following the 6-1-5-2-4-3 pattern, derived from the dice faces, where opposite faces sum to seven (6+1, 5+2, 4+3). Rhymes and notes become the dice with which Arnaut plays, and the sestina is reshaped into a series of possible random combinations (Canetti, 2023). This is further enhanced by melodic patterns (Rossell, 2015): unusual intervals of thirds, the iambic rhythm, and textual allusions immerse the listener in a goliardic tavern setting, where dice games are common, resulting in a playful art.

Implications The focus shifts from the text as a historical document to its role as an expression of cognitive, emotional, and social processes, prompting a multidisciplinary approach that blends musicology and cognitive science. A renewed humanism would be beneficial, recognizing that creative output is connected to perception and cognitive processes. Thus, the sestina is not only a metric reflection of the dice faces but a musical and linguistic reification of the dice game, involving the audience in a participatory experience with Arnaut.

References

- Canettieri, P. (2023). La “sestina” di Arnaut Daniel: permutazione e rime. In Barberi, L., & Vuagnoux-Uhlig, M. (Eds.). (2023). *Contrainte créatrice: la fortune littéraire de la sextine dans le tempo et dans l’espace* : 31-69. Edizioni del Galluzzo, Firenze.
- Marchis, V. (2009). *Storie di cose semplici*. Springer Science & Business Media, Milano.
- Mayo, A. R. (2012). La tradición musical de la sextina de Arnaut Daniel “Lo ferm voler qu’el cor m’intra” (BDT 29, 14): un artefacto lírico perfecto. In *Medievalia*, 15 : 33-38.
- Rossell, A. (2015). Medieval liturgical drama, carmina burana and the arnaut daniel’s sestina: Music and literature. In Proto, T., Canettieri, P., & Valenti, G. (2015) *Text and Tune. On the Association of Music and Lyrics in Sung Verse. Text and Tune: On the Association of Music and Lyrics in Sung Verse* : 23-52, Peter Lang, Frankfurt am Main.
- Schechner R. 2013, *Performance studies: An introduction* , Routledge, London and New York.

Mountains in Motion: The Non-Isochronous Heartbeat of Andean Music

Rodrigo Almonte

Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland

Background The non-isochronous rhythms of Andean music represent a unique aspect of its cultural and performative identity. Previous studies differ from each other regarding their interpretations of the aural perception of Andean rhythms and their notated values, while highlighting the uniqueness of this rhythmic performance (see d'Harcourt, 1925; Vasquez, 1990; Cross & Stobart, 2000; Ferrier, 2010; Carrasco, 2017; Valencia, 2020). These rhythms are especially evident in traditions such as huayno music and chakiri music. Unlike western rhythmic frameworks, which often rely on evenly spaced subdivisions, Andean music employs complex patterns that emerge organically from ritual and communal participation. This paper situates these rhythms within the concept of "metric bridges"¹, a term introduced by Steyn de Wet (2017) and inspired by Malcolm Braff's approach to non-isochronous rhythmic structures (2015). Metric bridges provide a lens to analyse the connections between rhythmic complexity and cultural stimuli, such as pilgrimage rituals and embodied practices, in Andean musical traditions.

Aims The aims of this research are to examine the role of non-isochronous subdivisions in Andean music, particularly in the huayno and chakiri genres, explore how cultural and performative stimuli activate and sustain these rhythmic structures, analyse the application of metric bridges as an interpretive framework for understanding non-western rhythmic practices, and investigate how simplifying these rhythms into quantised grids affects their cultural and performative essence.

Methods This research combines ethnographic fieldwork conducted by the author in Cusco, Peru, with focus groups and interviews involving traditional musicians. Participant collaboration and rehearsal recordings provide primary data for spectrographic rhythmic analysis using Sonic Visualiser. Using Braff's metric bridges as a conceptual tool, the research applies empirical rhythmic analysis to identify correlations between ritual contexts and the emergence of complex rhythmic patterns. Additionally, qualitative insights from traditional and contemporary

¹Metric bridges are conceived as transitional rhythmic structures that enable modulation between distinct temporal frameworks. They operate by gradually transforming one set of microbeat groupings into another through non-isochronous interpolation, effectively sustaining intermediate durations that mediate between contrasting tuplets. This allows performers to aurally navigate otherwise disconnected metric spaces, creating perceptual bridges that serve both expressive and structural functions in performance.

practitioners inform interpretations of how these rhythms function within communal and sacred settings and provide validation on spectrographic data.

Results Preliminary findings suggest that non-isochronous rhythms in Andean music are deeply tied to ritual and social contexts, where performative triggers such as sacred spaces, communal participation, and pilgrimage events foster rhythmic fluency. The application of metric bridges reveals how performers navigate rhythmic complexity intuitively, bypassing formal musical theory. However, the simplification of these rhythms into quantised grids, often for external analysis or adaptation, risks distorting their cultural essence and performative purpose, as is currently the case with the vast majority of adaptations and transcriptions of Andean music for western audiences. This paper anticipates further insights into how ritual dynamics and cultural transmission underpin these rhythmic practices. It also anticipates further possibilities of rhythmic evolution in Andean music through the use of metric bridges and metric modulation as creative compositional tools.

Conclusions The findings of my research, included in this paper, underscore the importance of situating Andean music within its cultural and ritual contexts to appreciate its rhythmic sophistication fully. Metric bridges provide a valuable framework for understanding the interplay between non-isochronous rhythms and cultural triggers. However, the imposition of external rhythmic frameworks highlights the tension between preserving cultural authenticity and engaging with globalised musical paradigms. These findings contribute to broader discussions on rhythm as a culturally embedded phenomenon, challenging universalised assumptions of musical structure.

References

- Braff, Malcolm, 'Basic Principles', *General Theory of Rhythm* (2015) <http://general-theory-of-rhythm.org/category/theory/> [accessed 8 March 2025]
- Carrasco, Rolando, 'El Huayno, apuntes sobre su rítmica', *Cuadernos Arguedianos*, 16 (2017) <https://cuadernosarguedianosjma.escuelafolklore.edu.pe/articulos-pdf/edicion-16/16-7.pdf> [accessed 8 March 2025]
- Cross, Ian, and Stobart Henry, 'The Andean Anacrusis? Rhythmic Structure and Perception in Easter Songs of Northern Potosí, Bolivia', *British Journal of Ethnomusicology*, 9.1 (2000), 63–94, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/3060646.pdf> [accessed 8 March 2025]
- De Wet, Steyn, 'Malcolm Braff's Approach to Rhythm for Improvisation: Definition, Analysis and Aesthetic' (Master's thesis, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, 2017) <https://wiredspace.wits.ac.za/items/f19a3760-bd7b-48d4-9ec0-4dac04f7ff78> [accessed 8 March 2025]

D'Harcourt, Raoul and Marguerite, *La Musique des Incas et ses survivances* (Paris: Librairie Orientaliste Paul Geuthner, 1925)

Ferrier, Claude, *El huayno con arpa: estilos globales en la nueva música popular andina*, 1st edition (Lima: Instituto de Etnomusicología PUCP, 2010)

Valencia, Roger, 'Análisis informatizado y transcripción del huayno Maura Zapato, de Daniel Kirwayo' (Master's thesis, Universidad Internacional de La Rioja, 2020) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340901711_Analisis_informatizado_y_transcripcion_del_huayno_Mauka_zapato_de_Daniel_Kirwayo?enrichId=rgreq-33a4de8383569c2ca2c851435a515aa0-XXX&enrichSource=Y292ZXJQYWdlOzM0MDkwMTcxMTtBUzo4ODU5OTU5NjA1MzcwODIAMTU4ODI0OTMwNjIzNg%3D%3D&el=1_x_2&_esc=publicationCoverPdf [accessed 8 May 2025]

Vázquez, Chalena, and Abilio Vergara, Ranulfo, *el hombre* (Lima: CEDAP, 1990)

Flow from expected performance in dynamic tempo drum practice: a pilot study

Cesc Bayle, Anton Berg, Benjamin Ultan Cowley

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Background Flow is widely investigated as an indicator of task engagement, particularly in the context of skill acquisition, where it is used to study participants' motivation (Engeser et al, 2021). In music learning, much of this research is conducted outside experimental contexts (Tan & Sin, 2021; Harmat et al, 2021) relying heavily on retrospective self-reported practice (Araújo & Hein, 2016), highlighting a need for further investigation into how Flow is operationalized. Previous studies on Flow and task learning in a steering paradigm (Cowley et al, 2019; Palomäki et al, 2021) found that Flow is affected more by discrepancies between anticipated and actual performance than by normative skill level. In this pilot study, we investigate this phenomenon in a behavioral longitudinal experiment on drum learning.

Aims This study aims to explore the relationship between skill acquisition and Flow during the learning process and how performance expectations influence this psychological state. Specifically, we examine participants' expectations derived from two measurement sources: the power-law learning curve fitted to their trial-wise performance data, and participants' trial-wise predictions of their own performance. The pilot serves as a preliminary exploration of these relationships and aims to refine the experimental design for full-scale implementation.

Methods In the experiment, participants learn to perform a drum rudiment over a dynamic tempo sequence (accelerating, holding peak tempo, decelerating), with temporal accuracy score as an indicator of skill level. They performed several trials per session (13 to 27 trials), and multiple sessions (3 to 5). Their goal is to improve accuracy and progress to higher tempos. Participants predict their scores and report their experience of Flow, using the Flow Short Scale Form (Laakasuo et al, 2022), when the skill-demand balance is met (Moneta, 2021). The pilot involved four participants over two iterations, two in each. In the first iteration, participants had trouble performing consistently, showing a considerable missed note ratio, especially in the peak tempo section, due to the parameters for progressing to further levels of difficulty. In the second iteration, we adjusted these parameters to improve the skill-demand setting, reflecting an increase in performance consistency. Mixed-Effects Linear Model regressions analyzed Flow as the outcome, using trial-wise skill level, deviations from expected performance, and participants' self-reported predictions as independent variables.

Results The exploratory results of this pilot generally align with findings from earlier studies (Cowley et al, 2019; Palomäki et al, 2021), where Flow is influenced by deviations between expected and actual performance, as predicted by the power-law model. Interestingly, deviations between participants' predicted performance and actual performance seem to have the opposite effect, with greater divergence associated with lower reported Flow. However, there was considerable variability among participants in these relationships, as well as in the statistical significance of the effects.

Conclusions This pilot study introduces a novel experimental design for investigating skill acquisition and Flow in music learning. It aims to contribute to more advantageous approaches for investigating activity engagement in music learning within experimental frameworks. Despite the impossibility of generalizing from the findings given the small sample size, results are promising and support further research in subsequent stages of the project. Potential educational implications emphasize the importance of maintaining an optimal challenge-skill ratio in practice environments to facilitate Flow and motivate continued engagement in music learning.

References

- Araújo, M.V., Hein, C.F. (2016). Finding Flow in Music Practice: An Exploratory Study About Self-Regulated Practice Behaviours and Dispositions to Flow in Highly Skilled Musicians. In: Harmat, L., Ørsted Andersen, F., Ullén, F., Wright, J., Sadlo, G. (eds) *Flow Experience*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28634-1_2
- Cowley, B.U., Palomäki, J., Tammi, T., Frantsi, R., Inkilä, V-P., Lehtonen, N., Pölonen, P., Vepsäläinen, J., Lappi, O. (2019). Flow Experiences During Visuomotor Skill Acquisition Reflect Deviation From a Power-Law Learning Curve, but Not Overall Level of Skill. *Front. Psychol.* 10:1126. doi: <https://10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01126>
- Engeser, S., Schiepe-Tiska, A., Peifer, C. (2021). Historical Lines and an Overview of Current Research on Flow. In: Peifer, C., Engeser, S. (eds) *Advances in Flow Research*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53468-4_1
- Harmat, L., de Manzano, Ö., Ullén, F. (2021). Flow in Music and Arts. In: Peifer, C., Engeser, S. (eds) *Advances in Flow Research*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53468-4_14
- Laakasuo, M., Palomäki, J., Abuhamdeh, S., Lappi, O., & Cowley, B. U. (2022). Psychometric analysis of the flow short scale translated to Finnish. *Sci Rep* 12, 20067 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-24715-3>
- Moneta, G.B. (2021). On the Conceptualization and Measurement of Flow. In:

Peifer, C., Engeser, S. (eds) *Advances in Flow Research*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53468-4_2

Palomäki, J., Tammi, T., Lehtonen, N., Seittenranta, N., Laakasuo, M., Abuhamdeh, S., Lappi, O., & Cowley, B. U. (2021). The link between flow and performance is moderated by task experience. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 124, 106891. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106891>

Tan, L., & Sin, H. X. (2021). Flow research in music contexts: A systematic literature review. *Musicae Scientiae*, 25(4), 399-428. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1029864919877564>

An Inverted-U Shape Preference for Melodies in Parrots and Humans

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Background There's a well-known inverted U-shaped relationship between the complexity of a stimulus and human preference. This means that people tend to prefer stimuli with a moderate level of complexity, while both low and high complexity are less appealing. This preference is believed to be rooted in a mechanism that drives organisms towards stimuli that are optimally useful for learning. In vocal learning species, such as birds, medium-complexity auditory signals could strike a balance between facilitating communication and optimizing learning. This same principle appears to apply to music, which is often transmitted through social learning and relies on repetitive patterns and variations. Research suggests that humans prefer music with a balance of predictability and novelty, avoiding both overly simple and overly complex patterns. However, it remains uncertain whether this preference in the acoustic domain is a recent cultural phenomenon, an adaptation specific to music, or a more general characteristic shared by vocal learners.

Aims We aimed to determine whether the preference for intermediate levels of complexity in acoustic patterns is a uniquely human trait or if it's shared with other species. To address this, we focused on a parrot species renowned for its vocal learning abilities and pattern recognition skills: The budgerigar (*Melopsittacus undulatus*).

Methods Both humans and budgerigars were presented with similar sets of pitch sequences in a three-option place preference paradigm, ensuring maximum comparability between the two species. In a given session, participants could choose between two of the three stimulus types: Random tones (tones arranged in a random order); Changing repeated patterns (sequences of different tone patterns, each repeated four times); Single regular patterns (the same pattern repeated indefinitely). The third place option was always silence, serving as a control condition. To minimize bias, all stimulus combinations were presented to each participant in a randomized order and were counterbalanced across physical positions.

Results Our results demonstrate that budgerigars, like humans, exhibit a preference for intermediate stimulus complexity (changing repeated patterns), suggesting that this may be a fundamental trait shared across species.

Conclusions The inverted-U-shaped preference for stimulus complexity might not stem from specific adaptations for music or its cultural transmission. Instead, it may be rooted in general auditory processing mechanisms shared by budgerigars and humans, potentially linked to vocal learning. However, further research on other vertebrates could reveal whether this phenomenon extends to acoustic patterns in non-vocal learners. Interestingly, research on other vertebrates has shown an inverted-U-shaped relationship in various non-auditory behavioral contexts, such as prey choice and playmate familiarity. Our findings further suggest that human aesthetic perception might be grounded in our fundamental vertebrate nature, opening up exciting avenues for future research beyond the auditory and musical domains.

Feelings in Motion: Embodiment, Emotional Synchrony and Social Connection on the Dancefloor (A Large-Scale Survey Study).

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Background Electronic dance music events promote social connection (Cannon & Greasley, 2021) and are regarded as collective rituals, characterised by collective effervescence (Olaveson, 2004) - a feeling of connection and harmony that emerges when a group engages in a shared purpose (Durkheim, 1912). Research suggests that *kama muta* ("being moved by love") and perceived emotional synchrony are key factors in promoting social connection in collective rituals (Zabala et al., 2024; Włodarczyk et al., 2021). Moreover, electronic dance music facilitates pleasure via entrainment to a repetitive, syncopated beat (Witek et al., 2014), resulting in a feedback loop that reinforces dance (Senn et al., 2023). This 'embodied pleasure,' conveyed through dance, may lead to a powerful collective emotional experience via emotional contagion (Witek, 2017). However, these factors and their relationship with social connection at electronic dance music events remain unexplored.

Aims The present study aimed to explore the relationship between emotional experiences (embodied pleasure and *kama muta*) and social connection at EDM events, assess the extent to which perceived emotional synchrony and emotional contagion play a role in the relationship between embodied pleasure, *kama muta* and social connection, and examine the role of the music, DJ(s) and intoxication within these relationships.

Methods Participants ($N=612$) completed an online survey describing the most recent EDM event they had attended. They then completed Likert scales measuring embodied pleasure, *kama muta*, perceived emotional synchrony, emotional contagion, and social connection with the crowd at the event. Music/DJ preference, music familiarity and desire to dance were also measured. Drug/alcohol use was measured through an optional check-box item.

Results Kendall's Tau correlations revealed that emotional experience variables, desire to dance and social connection were positively correlated. Regression analyses tested whether desire to dance mediated the effects of musical and DJ-related factors on embodied pleasure. Desire to dance mediated relationships between music preference ($\beta = .08, p < .001$), music familiarity ($\beta = .03, p < .05$), DJ preference ($\beta = .05, p > .01$) and embodied pleasure. A parallel mediation model tested using multiple regressions explored whether emotional contagion and perceived

emotional synchrony mediated the relationship between embodied pleasure and social connection. Embodied pleasure significantly predicted social connection, ($\beta = .61, p < 0.001$). There was a significant indirect effect of embodied pleasure on social connection through both emotional contagion, ($\beta = .09, p < 0.001$), and perceived emotional synchrony, ($\beta = .28, p < 0.001$). The direct effect of embodied pleasure on social connection remained significant while controlling for emotional contagion and perceived emotional synchrony, suggesting partial mediation, ($\beta = .24, p < 0.001$). No significant differences in social connection were found between participants based on alcohol or drug use.

Conclusions Findings suggest music familiarity and music/DJ preference predict a desire to dance, leading to embodied pleasure which enhances social connection through emotional contagion and synchrony. This provides new insights into the psychological mechanisms that underpin social connection on the dancefloor at electronic dance music events and has implications for understanding interrelated embodied and socio-affective processes in music.

References

- Cannon, J. W., & Greasley, A. E. (2021). Exploring relationships between electronic dance music event participation and well-being. *Music & Science*, 4(1), 1-17.
- Durkheim, É. (1912). *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life*. New York, NY: The Free Press
- Olaveson, T. (2004). 'Connectedness' and the rave experience: Rave as new religious movement? In G. St John (Ed.), *Rave Culture and Religion* (pp. 83-104). Routledge.
- Senn, O., Bechtold, T., Hoesl, F., Jerjen, R., Kilchenmann, L., Rose, D., ... & Alessandri, E. (2023). An SEM approach to validating the psychological model of musical groove. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 49(3), 290-305.
- Witek, M. A. (2017). Filling in: Syncopation, pleasure and distributed embodiment in groove. *Music Analysis*, 36(1), 138-160.
- Witek, M. A., Clarke, E. F., Wallentin, M., Kringelbach, M. L., & Vuust, P. (2014). Syncopation, body-movement and pleasure in groove music. *PLoS one*, 9(4), e94446.
- Włodarczyk, A., Zumeta, L., Basabe, N., Rimé, B., & Páez, D. (2023). Religious and secular collective gatherings, perceived emotional synchrony and self-transcendent emotions: two longitudinal studies. *Current Psychology*, 42(6), 4754-4771.
- Zabala, J., Vázquez, A., Conejero, S., & Pascual, A. (2024). Exploring the origins of identity fusion: Shared emotional experience activates fusion with the group over time. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 63(3), 1479-1496.

Behind the Beat: Investigating the Cognitive and Musical Foundations of 'Au Fond du Temps'

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Background Numerous research has investigated rhythm, beat and meter processing in music and its cognitive implications, including the phenomenon of groove. Playing “au fond du temps” (i.e., slightly behind the beat, or “playing slightly laid-back”), frequently occurs in music with high groove (Danielsen et al., 2024; Witek, 2017). While this temporal deviation can enhance engagement and groove perception, its cognitive underpinnings and dependence on musical style, instrument type, or expertise remain underexplored.

Aims We investigated whether and how temporal shifts in the beat keeper are influenced by the type of beat-keeping instrument within a new beat-alignment task, also manipulating whether the temporal shift occurred earlier or later.

Methods We developed a more musical version of the Beat Alignment Test (BAT), a seminal tool for assessing beat processing, included in the BAASTA battery (Dalla Bella et al., 2017). Pop-style musical excerpts were created featuring either an integrated kick drum or an external triangle as the beat keeper, playing an isochronous sequence (Inter-Beat-Interval IBI: 500 ms, 120 bpm). Three versions of each excerpt were prepared, with the beat keeper being either on beat, earlier (-25% IBI), or later (+25% IBI). Non-musician adults judged whether the musicians were playing well in rhythm together once the kick/triangle had joined. They also rated on-beat excerpts for “pleasure”, “wanting to move”, and “pulse clarity”. Additionally, they completed a shortened version of the BAASTA-BAT (600 ms).

Results Overall, participants performed well, and accuracy correlated with the BAASTA-BAT. Items featuring the kick received higher ratings for “pleasure”, “wanting to move”, and “pulse clarity” than those with the triangle, suggesting more groove for the excerpts with the kick. Results revealed a significant interaction between instrument type of the beat-keeper and timing shift. Later shifts were perceived less often as offbeat than earlier shifts for the kick, but not for the triangle. For earlier shifts, the two timbres did not differ. This asymmetry aligns with temporal prediction theory, which posits that early violations are more disruptive than late ones (McAuley & Kidd, 1998). However, our data pattern suggests that additional factors - such as the instrument’s integration into the musical texture and

its perceived link to groove - may modulate temporal perception in music.

Conclusion The new pop-music version of the BAT was successfully completed by adults, and performance correlates with the BAASTA-BAT. Our findings suggest that the detection of timing deviations in groove contexts depends on both instrument and temporal shift direction. The kick, being integrated into the musical ensemble, revealed an asymmetry in temporal shift detection: later shifts were more tolerated. These results expand on the BAT by showing that perception of temporal shifts is shaped by instrumental implementation. To further investigate this phenomenon, we are running an online experiment in which musicians judge whether the temporal shift of the kick is early or late. These studies explore whether flexibility in perceiving temporal shifts reflects a domain-general mechanism for processing timing, or a style-specific sensitivity related to groove-based music. Investigating the “au fond du temps” phenomenon allows bridging research into musical performance, perceptual science, and cognitive theory, contributing to a broader understanding of how timing is perceived, predicted, and enjoyed.

References

- Dalla Bella, S., Farrugia, N., Benoit, C.-E., Begel, V., Verga, L., Harding, E., & Kotz, S. A. (2017). BAASTA: Battery for the Assessment of Auditory Sensorimotor and Timing Abilities. *Behavior Research Methods*, 49(3), 1128–1145.
- Danielsen, A., Brøvig, R., Bøhler, K. K., Câmara, G. S., Haugen, M. R., Jacobsen, E., Johansson, M. S., Lartillot, O., Nymoën, K., Oddekalk, K. A., Sandvik, B., Sioros, G., & London, J. (2024). There’s More to Timing than Time: Investigating Musical Microrhythm Across Disciplines and Cultures. *Music Perception*, 41(3), 176–198.
- McAuley, J. D., & Kidd, G. (1998). Effect of deviations from temporal expectations on tempo discrimination of isochronous tone sequences. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 24(6), 1786–1800.
- Witek, M. A. G. (2017). Filling In: Syncopation, Pleasure and Distributed Embodiment in Groove. *Music Analysis*, 36(1), 138–160.

Why music makes us dance: insights from thematic analysis and computational musical features.

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Background Groove is a multidimensional, participatory experience closely tied to the desire to move to music (Duman et al., 2024; Janata et al., 2012), with expressions ranging from clapping to head-banging (Hosken, 2020; Hudson, 2022). Dancing—a central form of groove—has received limited empirical attention (Fitch, 2016), despite involving full-body coordination and complex interactions between individuals, music, and context (Leman, 2010; Bigand et al., 2024). Research has largely focused on rhythm-related variables like complexity and microtiming (Witek et al., 2014; Danielsen et al., 2015), often using simplified stimuli or WEIRD musical samples and populations (Henrich et al., 2010; Cossavella et al., 2023). This limits the ecological and cultural scope of findings on musical engagement and movement. This study addresses these gaps by examining naturalistic music selected by participants from a non-WEIRD country. We analyzed subjective reflections on the musical qualities that promote or hinder dancing, alongside high-level features extracted via MIR.

Aims We investigated which musical and experiential features people perceive as relevant for the desire to dance. Specifically: What qualities do participants identify in songs that do or do not make them want to dance? Do these song types differ in extracted features (valence, arousal, engagement, danceability)? How well do these features align with subjective descriptions? Features were selected based on prior research linking affect and movement induction (e.g., Janata et al., 2012). Valence and arousal capture emotional response; engagement and danceability relate to attention and motor resonance.

Methods Ninety-one participants from Argentina each selected one song that makes them want to dance and one they enjoy but do not associate with dancing. For each, they answered the open-ended question: “Why do you think this song makes/does not make you want to dance?”. We conducted thematic analysis using a structured multi-coder approach, including codebook development and in-

tercoder reliability checks. Audio features were extracted using the Essentia library (Bogdanov et al., 2013).

Results Dance songs scored significantly higher in danceability, engagement, arousal, and valence. Participants linked their desire to dance with bodily activation, emotional uplift, and energetic qualities. Non-dance songs were described as calm, introspective, or lyrically focused, with lower perceived energy and affect. Lyrics and sound-gesture associations were often cited in dance songs, revealing experiential dimensions beyond rhythm.

Conclusion MIR features like danceability and affective dimensions aligned with participants' experiences. Subjective references to positive affect and high arousal in dance songs support the relevance of valence and arousal features. Additionally, lyrical content, emotional tone, and attentional demands emerged as key factors in non-dance music. Participants often selected Latin American genres like cumbia, quarteto, and reggaetón, highlighting styles often omitted from music cognition research. While musically diverse, the sample was geographically limited. Future research should expand cross-cultural coverage and further validate automated features perceptually. This study contributes to embodied music cognition by combining subjective insights with computational analysis to illuminate how people experience danceable music in everyday life.

References

- Bigand, F., Bianco, R., Abalde, S. F., & Novembre, G. (2024). The geometry of interpersonal synchrony in human dance. *Current Biology*.
- Bogdanov, D., Wack, N., Gómez, E., Gulati, S., Herrera, P., Mayor, O., ... & Serra, X. (2013, October). Essentia: An open-source library for sound and music analysis. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia* (pp. 855-858).
- Cossavella, F., Miguel, M., & Fernandez Slezak, D. (2023, December). The role of the motor system in the processing of rhythmic complexity: A critical review. In *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society* (Vol. 46).
- Danielsen, A., Haugen, M. R., & Jensenius, A. R. (2015). Moving to the beat: Studying entrainment to micro-rhythmic changes in pulse by motion capture. *Timing & Time Perception*, 3(1-2), 133-154.
- Duman, D., Snape, N., Danso, A., Toiviainen, P., & Luck, G. (2024). Groove as a multidimensional participatory experience. *Psychology of Music*, 52(1), 93-116.
- Fitch, W. T. (2016). Dance, music, meter and groove: A forgotten partnership. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 10, 64.

- Henrich, J., Heine, S. J., & Norenzayan, A. (2010). Most people are not WEIRD. *Nature*, 466(7302), 29-29.
- Hosken, F. (2020). The subjective, human experience of groove: A phenomenological investigation. *Psychology of Music*, 48(2), 182-198.
- Hudson, S. S. (2022). Bang your head: Construing beat through familiar drum patterns in metal music. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 44(1), 121-140.
- Janata, P., Tomic, S. T., & Haberman, J. M. (2012). Sensorimotor coupling in music and the psychology of the groove. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 141(1), 54.
- Leman, M. (2010). An embodied approach to music semantics. *Musicae Scientiae*, 14(1), 43-67.
- Senn, O., Bechtold, T. A., Hoesl, F., & Kilchenmann, L. (2021). Taste and familiarity affect the experience of groove in popular music. *Musicae Scientiae*, 25(1), 45-66.
- Witek, M. A., Clarke, E. F., Wallentin, M., Kringelbach, M. L., & Vuust, P. (2014). Syncopation, body-movement and pleasure in groove music. *PLOS ONE*, 9(4), e94446.

How do the Psychological Benefits of Nostalgic Music Differ Across Age Groups, and What Makes it Particularly Effective in Enhancing Well-being?

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Background Historically, linked to disease, nostalgia is now recognised as a self-relevant social emotion (Sedikides et al., 2008). Research has shown that feeling nostalgic can mitigate existential anxiety through shared beliefs that imbue meaning in life and help regulate negative emotional states (Wildschut et al., 2006; Routledge et al., 2008; Sedikides et al., 2008). However, there are inconsistencies regarding whether age influences the potency of nostalgic experiences or whether nostalgia is experienced regardless of age (Turner, 2021; Routledge et al., 2008).

Aims This study explored how personally significant nostalgic music affects psychological well-being across different age-groups. Individual relationships with nostalgia and baseline well-being were measured and compared to post-music mood.

Methods A sample of 59 participants, divided into four age groups (18-25, 26-40, 41-59, and 60+) was recruited through snowball sampling and online advertisements. Reflexivity and diverse referral networks were employed to mitigate self-selection bias. Data was collected using a QuestionPro survey. Pre-task measures included the Southampton Nostalgia Scale (SNS; Routledge et al., 2008). Items 4-7 were adapted to measure participants' relationship with music. Followed by the Depression and Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). Participants were then asked to listen to a personally significant nostalgic song and asked to rate the intensity of their nostalgic experience using two 5-point Likert style questions. As song selection was participant-led the musical components (e.g., pitch, tempo, melody) were not analysed, although the title, artist and genre of selected songs were collected. Post-task mood was assessed using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (Watson et al., 1988), followed by a reflective writing task to capture psychological themes.

Results The descriptive statistics showed that the sample collected had high trait nostalgia, low psychological distress, as well as high post-music nostalgia and positive mood following listening to nostalgic music. For hypotheses 1 and 2, a multiple linear regression was conducted with age group and well-being predicting post-music nostalgia. For hypothesis 3, a multiple linear regression with an interaction between age group and baseline nostalgic predicting post-music nostalgia. It was

found that age group did not predict post-music nostalgia, however slightly higher levels of nostalgia were reported in the older age groups (41-59 and 60+). It was also found that lower well-being scores marginally predicted post-music nostalgia, though these findings were not statistically significant. Finally, it was found that trait nostalgia strongly predicted post-music nostalgia, but the analysis revealed that this was not predicted by age group.

Conclusions These findings suggest that listening to personally significant nostalgic music can support emotional regulation and reduce anxiety regardless of age. Further exploration of music evoked nostalgia may hold therapeutic potential in settings such as music therapy or art therapy, or even as a daily well-being task. However, future research should collect larger more diverse samples and employ standardised post-music nostalgia measures.

References

- Barrett, F. S., Grimm, K. J., Robins, R. W., Wildschut, T., Sedikides, C., & Janata, P. (2010). Music-evoked nostalgia: Affect, memory, and personality. *Emotion, 10*(3), 390-403. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019006>
- Lovibond, S. H., & Lovibond, P. F. (1995). *Manual for the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales* (2nd ed.). Psychology Foundation.
- Routledge, C., Arndt, J., Sedikides, C., & Wildschut, T. (2008). A blast from the past: The terror management function of nostalgia. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology, 44*(1), 132-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2006.11.001>
- Sedikides, C., Wildschut, T., Arndt, J., & Routledge, C. (2008). Nostalgia: Past, present, and future. *Current Directions in Psychological Science, 17*(5), 304-307. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2008.00595.x>
- Turner, J. R., & Stanley, J. T. (2021). Holding on to pieces of the past: Daily reports of nostalgia in a life-span sample. *Emotion, 21*(5), 951-961. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000980>
- Watson, D., Clark, L. A., & Tellegen, A. (1988). Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: The PANAS scales. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 54*(6), 1063-1070. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.54.6.1063>
- Wildschut, T., Sedikides, C., Arndt, J., & Routledge, C. (2006). Nostalgia: Content, triggers, functions. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 91*(5), 975-993. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.91.5.975>

The Exploration of How a UBI Model Would Affect the Behaviours of EDM Artists and if a Credible Way Forward in the UK

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Background The nightlife scene is in decline. With more clubs closing each year and a predicted collapse of the scene by the end of 2029 in the UK (NTIA, 2023), this study proposes to look at the ways in which a UBI (Universal Basic Income) model could help EDM artists escape this predicted reality and how it could also change the way they behave in the production of their music building on past work, particularly work from the pandemic (Cannizzo, Strong and Whiting, 2024 & Madden, 2021). Specific models of UBI are explored and an intended sample of EDM artists will be gathered through an interview format. Additionally, some UBI or more accurately, Basic Income models exist already in one of which is Ireland, a current example that could be followed which is considered to be included in the interview questions (Johnston, 2022) and its viability (Reed, Johnson, Lansley, et al. 2023). All in all, this paper looks at the outcomes that can benefit the EDM artist through the use of UBI or conversely, hinder them as a potential way forward in this uncertain, ever-changing scene that they live in. Further research ideas are also contemplated.

Aims The aims of this article is to: investigate the different experiences of musicians in Ireland who receive UBI and (EDM) artists in the UK who do not, explore how musicians in receipt of UBI in Ireland and (EDM) artists in the UK experience their creative output differently, examine and compare specific areas of difference in the creative life of musicians in receipt of UBI and those who are not in receipt, and compare the different experiences of musicians in Ireland post-Covid-19 pandemic with and without UBI.

Methods Through Interviews with UBI artists from the Ireland UBI trial and artists (most likely EDM) from the UK in a semi-structured format. There will be a series of predetermined questions and done as a qualitative study.

Main Contribution Through Interviews with UBI artists from the Ireland UBI trial and artists (most likely EDM) from the UK in a semi-structured format. There will be a series of predetermined questions and done as a qualitative study.

Implications The expected results is to discover how (EDM) artists in the UK would think that given a model similar to the Ireland trial would benefit them greatly

in ways such as no creativity pressure, financial security, well-being and more of the like.

References

Cannizzo, Fabian, Catherine Strong, and Sam Whiting. "Basic income for creative justice: Weathering inequity in the creative industries during COVID-19." *Journal of Sociology* (2024)

Madden, David. "Covid Nights: Crisis, and Street-level Institutions in Montreal and Beyond." *Dancecult: Journal of Electronic Dance Music Culture* 13(1) (2021): 54-68.

Reed RH, Johnson MT, Lansley S, et al. "Universal basic income is affordable and feasible: Evidence from UK economic microsimulation modelling." *Journal of Poverty and Social Justice* 31(1) (2023): 146–162.

Patel, Salil B., and Joel Kariel. "Universal basic income and covid-19 pandemic." *BMJ* 372 (2021).

Johnston, H. (2022). Basic Income in Ireland: The Development of Two Pilots. *European Journal of Social Security*, 24(3), 243-256. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13882627221109287>

Complex Terrain: What musicians go through when confronted with complex rhythms.

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Background Research on defining, measuring and effects of rhythmic complexity on listeners has been done extensively in recent years, especially within the groove research community (for overviews: Etani et al. 2024, Senn 2023). However, there seems to be a gap when it comes to systematic investigations on musicians' experiences when confronted with complex rhythms. With this small-scale autoethnographic pilot study I have taken my first steps to explore if such research gives valuable insights.

Aims The goal was a systematic observation and description of my reactions (i.e. stress, imbalance, frustration, joy, etc.) that occur while practicing complex rhythms.

Methods The autoethnographic approach met my personal interest as a musician (Poulos 2021) and the limited resources for this study. It ensured that practicing and data collection was executed thoroughly. The data was collected via journaling and analyzed using inductive thematic analysis. I conducted thirteen practice sessions of approximately 60 minutes. The topic was a 3 beat drumset pattern within a $\frac{5}{4}$ meter. I took handwritten notes on my observations on a protocol sheet during the sessions.

Results I observed a large variety of reactions. Currently the preliminary categories are: Physical reactions (i.e. muscle tension), Emotions/moods (i.e. stress), Mental state (i.e. focus), Performance (i.e. inspiration). The most obvious observations were the number and variety of reactions and how rapidly they changed. In just a few moments they can shift from frustration to ecstasy or from tension to relaxation. A closer look revealed one interesting pattern. At times, I experienced states best described as "losing groundedness" and "orientation" combined with strong focus and quick mental exhaustion. This occurred especially when I changed exercises, and the challenge was increased. Interesting about these states is that they match some important theories on complexity and how it is processed. Pressing described complexity as the mental effort an organism must make to solve a problem (Pressing 1999). Another interesting theory from neuroscience that has been used to explain complexity in music is called predictive coding (Vuust et al. 2022, Senn 2023). Here an organism interacts with its environment by making predictions of incoming sensory stimuli. Complexity is the level of surprisal aroused

by prediction errors. Both theories might be useful to explain the states mentioned above. Furthermore, I observed how quickly reactions wore off and one exercise became “just a normal task” in my daily routine.

Conclusions Despite the limitations (researcher bias, small number of sessions, only one drum pattern) I am confident that this direction of research on complexity is worth pursuing. Not only will it provide basic knowledge but understanding complexity on a scale of “feelings” might contribute to new approaches on problem solving. If investigated more extensively, including band work and interviews with fellow musicians, these findings may also add a complementary perspective on certain concepts for defining and measuring complexity like predictive coding or others.

References

- Etani, T., Miura, A., Kawase, S., Fujii, S., Keller, P. E., Vuust, P., & Kudo, K. (2024). A review of psychological and neuroscientific research on musical groove. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 158, 105522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiore.2023.105522>
- Poulos, C. N. (2021). *Essentials of Autoethnography*. American Psychological Association.
- Pressing, J. (1999). *Cognitive complexity and the structure of musical patterns*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cognitive-complexity-and-the-structure-of-musical-Pressing/8fcbf060908058873a91389f156891ad357aba91>
- Senn, O. (2023). A predictive coding approach to modelling the perceived complexity of popular music drum patterns. *Heliyon*, 9(4), e15199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15199>
- Vuust, P., Heggli, O. A., Friston, K. J., & Kringelbach, M. L. (2022). Music in the brain. *Nature Reviews. Neuroscience*, 23(5), 287–305. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41583-022-00578-5>

Key roles in opera production regarding achieving singers' sung text intelligibility

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Background Even if the text is sung in a language the listener knows, it is difficult for them to understand the words sung in the traditional Western classical style in operas. Reasons given for this include very high notes (Sundberg, 2018). So far, the perspective of singers on achieving intelligibility has been collected in various contexts, such as in their biographies.

Aims This study aimed to systematically collect information on aspects of intelligibility from the singers' perspective, relating to the contributions of the various key roles in an opera performance.

Methods This study involved interviewing 30 opera singers from Europe and North America in a semi-structured way. Eleven of the singers were interviewed in Estonian and the remaining 19 in English. As the issue affects all voice types, all opera singers who agreed to participate in the study were included. These singers included two basses, one bass-baritone, two baritones, seven tenors, one contratenor, six mezzo-sopranos and eleven sopranos. The interview did not include any direct questions about other people who influence singers' ability to make text intelligible.

Results Analysis of the interviews shows that a number of issues in opera production affect lyrical clarity, and that these issues do not depend solely on the singers. The interviewed singers shared their thoughts on various topics, including training, textual clarity, receiving feedback, and organisational aspects of the production.

Conclusions The study shows that, to achieve intelligibility in opera, cooperation must be improved between singers, singing teachers, cultural organisers, stage directors, conductors and listeners. If possible, composers and librettists should also be involved. The results described in the poster also provide guidance on how to enhance cooperation.

References

Sundberg, J. (2018). Phonetics of Singing in Western Classical Style. Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199384655.013.412>

Violently themed music and emotion regulation

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Background Music is a widely used tool for emotion regulation with listeners selecting genres based on personal preferences and emotional needs. Factors such as age, gender, musical background, and specific musical characteristics such as tempo, instrumentation and rhythm influence how music impacts mood and emotions (Saarikallio, 2007; Cook et al., 2017). Genres often perceived as aggressive or extreme, such as heavy metal and drill, are frequently associated with violent themes due to their intense sonic qualities and explicit lyrics (Weinstein, 2009; Ilan, 2020). Despite these negative stereotypes, research shows that fans use these genres for mood regulation, emotional catharsis, improved mood, and identity formation (Hines & McFerran, 2014; Saarikallio, 2007; Sharman & Dingle, 2015). Research on aggressive music often focuses on the symbolism and violence depicted in lyrics and visuals. However, less attention is given to how fans interpret or relate to these themes. While heavy metal often incorporates visuals and lyrics about violence, vengeance, or anger, many subgenres also address societal injustices and mental well-being (Buts & Engels, 2010). Additionally, drill music, originating in Chicago, often reflects hyper-masculinity and violence while exploring systemic injustice and community struggles (Ilan, 2020; Farje, 2022). Though these genres are linked to violence and antisocial behavior, they help fans process complex emotions and offer a sense of community (Olsen et al., 2022; Thompson et al., 2019).

Aim This study explores two questions: (1) How do fans of these genres use music for emotion regulation? (2) How do fans of violently-themed music relate to this categorization and the themes in heavy metal and drill? It examines how these often stigmatised genres contribute to emotional well-being and identity formation among listeners. It provides in-depth data on how fans perceive the violent themes associated with these genres and whether extreme music can be utilized for emotional regulation, challenging the negative stereotypes associated with it.

Method This research was conducted through an online, anonymous, and voluntary survey focused on personal experiences and perspectives of heavy metal and drill fans. The data was collected through open-ended questions and focused on exploring narrative responses to uncover patterns related to emotion regulation using extreme music and fans' perceptions of the violent themes found in the highlighted genres.

Results Data gathered from 37 participants suggests that while fans are aware of these violent themes, they rarely pay attention or engage with these elements. According to their testimonies, fans resonate more with the emotionality of these genres, using the music for catharsis, ecstasy or to feel powerful.

Conclusion Preliminary results suggest heavy metal and drill help fans process complex emotions and find comfort. Although previous research has focused on the symbolic and lyrical violence in these genres, by exploring the emotional and social functions of these styles, we can gain insight how listeners navigate difficult emotions and societal challenges.

References

Buts, J., & Engels, M. (2010). The Thematical and Stylistic Evolution of Heavy Metal Lyrics and Imagery.

Cook, T., Roy, A. R. K., & Welker, K. M. (2017). Music as an emotion regulation strategy: An examination of genres of music and their roles in emotion regulation. *Psychology of Music*, 47(1), 144–154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735617734627>

Farje, A. (2022). *The Silenced Sound of Drill*.

Green, D. (2018). *Documenting Drill Music: Understanding Black Masculine Performances in Hip-Hop*. Kuscholarworks.ku.edu. <https://kuscholarworks.ku.edu/handle/1808/28068>

Hines, M., & McFerran, K. S. (2014). Metal made me who I am: Seven adult men reflect on their engagement with metal music during adolescence. *International Journal of Community Music*, 7(2), 205–222. https://doi.org/10.1386/ijcm.7.2.205_1

Ilan, J. (2020). Digital Street Culture Decoded: Why Criminalizing Drill Music Is Street Illiterate and Counterproductive. *British Journal of Criminology*, 60(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azz086>

McFerran, K. S. (2016). Contextualising the relationship between music, emotions and the well-being of young people: A critical interpretive synthesis. *Musicae Scientiae*, 20(1), 103–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1029864915626968>

Olsen, K. N., Terry, J., & Thompson, W. F. (2022). Psychosocial risks and benefits of exposure to heavy metal music with aggressive themes: Current theory and evidence. *Current Psychology*, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03108-9>

Saarikallio, S. (2007). Music as mood regulation in adolescence. *Jyväskylä Studies in Humanities*, 67. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/13403>

Sharman, L., & Dingle, G. A. (2015). Extreme Metal Music and Anger Processing.

Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 9(272). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2015.00272>

Thompson, W. F., Geeves, A. M., & Olsen, K. N. (2019). Who enjoys listening to violent music and why? *Psychology of Popular Media Culture*, 8(3), 218–232. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ppm0000184>

Weinstein, D. (2009). *Heavy metal the music and its culture* (Revised ed., pp. 22-27). Da Capo Press.

Large (Sleep) Music Analysis – from Raw Audio to Feature Spaces and Clustering

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Background Music is often used as a sleep aid. As many as 43.6% of insomniacs utilize music to promote sleep. [1] In recent years, first research has been conducted to identify relevant features and clusters of sleep music. [2] However, the research was based on proprietary audio features by Spotify. Not only is there no public information available on how those audio features by Spotify are derived, but Spotify has stopped its service of providing those audio features altogether.

Aims To overcome these limitations and issues, the idea is to base the music analysis showcased for sleep music titles collected by Scarrat et al. [2] on the actual audio, and to derive an audio feature space for music clustering which is only based on open available tools and algorithms.

Main Contribution Audio forming over 100k tracks categorized as sleep music is obtained, and the Essentia software tool [3] is then utilised to derive audio features. The feature space is further refined by exploring different methods for dimensionality reduction, ranging from data-driven approaches such as PCA to manual selection based on expert knowledge. A purely data-driven approach, utilizing a machine learning embedding space for music is explored as well. Clustering methods such as K-Means and GMM are used as a starting point. This clustering will be expanded beyond the tracks collected by Scarratt et al. [2] and compared to sleep music tracks from other sources, to see if the clustering is consistent and can be reproduced more generally. First results show that initial expectations are not always met.

Implications This contribution will provide deeper insight to relevant audio features for sleep, because the clusters can be related to objective audio features and is based on open algorithms for the underlying audio, compared to now-no-longer-available and non-public audio features of a company.

Such an insightful clustering provides the foundation to categorize songs based on audio features, and identify patterns and preferences of human choice for sleep music. The process of how to analyse music tracks and obtain a dimensionally-reduced feature space for clustering can even be transferred to other types of music or audio.

References

- [1]: Morin, Charles M., et al. "Epidemiology of insomnia: prevalence, self-help treatments, consultations, and determinants of help-seeking behaviors." *Sleep medicine* 7.2 (2006): 123-130.
- [2]: Scarratt, Rebecca Jane, et al. "The audio features of sleep music: Universal and subgroup characteristics." *PloS One* 18.1 (2023): e0278813.
- [3]: Bogdanov, Dmitry, et al. "Essentia: an open-source library for sound and music analysis." *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*. 2013

The Future of Sound: An Evolutionary Perspective on Possible Histories of Homo Musicus

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Background Viewed through the perspective of the history of culture, our approach to the problems of music has evolved from metaphysics (Šopenhauer, 2016), through social theories (Aleksander, 2007) and psychology (Deutsch, 2007; Leibold & Loepthien, 2015), musical analysis (Cook, 1992) and acoustics with a formalized mathematical apparatus (Chan et. al., 2019), eventually reaching interdisciplinary movements between cognitive sciences (Zatorre & Salimpoor, 2013) and evolutionary theories (Cross & Morley, 2009; Killin, 2017) – shifting the object of study from sound per se to the neural system that, in complex interaction with culture and technology, produces the experience of music. Along this path, the question arises of how to understand possible histories of Homo Musicus (basically, our Musical subjectivity) in future

Aim If we move away from the anthropocentric musicological perspective, which often reduces music to a sonic event and its inherent musical logic, the aim of this research would be to: a) present possible explanations for the development of the Western European musical tradition up to and after the emergence of *larpurlartism* (art for art's sake), b) explain the evolutionary foundations of musical behavior and experience, ultimately shaped by culture, and c) explore the possible future 'uses of music' through the lens of emerging technologies, evolutionary functions and constraints of our cognition, as well as the social factors that shape our experience (Creanza et. al., 2017). Additionally, we aim to answer question whether music can even be perceived as a 'unitary neural phenomenon', or if it is an abstract class of experiences that we integrate into a unified experience within our own mental theater (Nummenmaa et. al., 2021).

Main Contribution Music will be considered in a specific transdisciplinary intersection of evolutionary theory and neurobiology, SETI studies (Dejvis, 2000), sociology of culture – as well as the psychology and philosophy of music – which form the foundation of the research (Vesić, 2023). Furthermore, we will present the complexity of the musical experience through the questions of perception, creativity, and cultural transmission in possible future(s), outlined through an abstract analytical framework (Nichols et. al., 2024). Finally, ideas about the music of the future will be presented through compelling examples from SF literature, where we can find perspectives on the cultures of (extra)terrestrial intelligences (Lem, 2024;

Dik, 2018; Haksli, 2017; Zamyatin, 2017).

Implications The main implications of research relate to offering a new perspectives on the music through an interdisciplinary approach to the phenomenon, re-defining traditional musicological stances on the analysis of music as an 'autonomous' sonic sensation. By directing the focus toward the philosophical questions of music, we will present a pedagogically important approach that cannot be replaced by partial discourses due to disciplinary limitations, but also because of the 'growing of knowledge' – which is not visible from the specific fields of expertise.

References

- Aleksander, V. (2007). *Sociologija umetnosti (Sociology of Art)*. Beograd: Clio
- Chan, P. Y., Dong, M., Li, H. (2019). *The Science of Harmony: A Psychophysical Basis for Perceptual Tensions and Resolutions in Music*. *Research* 2019, 1-22
- Creanza, N., Kolodny, O., Feldman, M. W. (2017). Cultural evolutionary theory: How culture evolves and why it matters. *PNAS* Vol. 114., No. 30, 7782-7789
- Cross, I., Morley, I. (2009). Music in evolution and evolutionary theory: the nature of evidence. In Malloch, S., Trevarthen, C. (Eds.), *Communicative Musicality, Exploring the Basis of Human Companionship* (pp. 61-81). Oxford University Press
- Deutch, D. (2007). Music Perception. *Frontiers of Biosciences* 12, 4474-4482
- Dik, F. K. (2018). *Ubik (Ubik)*. Beograd: Kontrast
- Dejvis, P. (2000). *Poslednja tri minuta*. Beograd: Polaris
- Haksli, O. (2017). *Vrli novi svet (Brave New World)*. Beograd: Kontrast
- Jung Choi, Y., Yoon, S. (2014). Neuroaesthetics: A Concise Review of the Evidence Aimed at Aesthetically Sensible Design. *Science of Emotions* Vol, 17, No. 2, 45-54
- Killin, A. (2017). The origins of music: Evidence, Theory, and prospects. *Music & Science* Vol. 1: 1-23
- Leipold, B., Loepthien, T. (2015). Music reception and emotional regulation in adolescence and adulthood. *Musica Scientiae* Vol. 19(I), 111-128
- Lem, S. (2002). *Solaris*. New York: Harper Voyager
- Nichols R., Charbonneau, M., Chellappoo, A. et. al. (2024). Cultural evolution: A review of theoretical challenges. *Evolutionary Human Sciences* 6, 1-25
- Nummenmaa, L., Putkinen, V., Sams, M. (2021). Social pleasures of music. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences* 39: 196-202
- Vesić, M. (2023). *Logika [ne]naučnog otkrića (Logic of [non]scientific discovery)*. Beograd: Intranet Centar
- Zamyatin, Y. (1993). *We*. London: Penguin Books

Zatorre, R. J., Salimpoor, N. V. (2013). From perception to pleasure: Music and its neural substrates. *PNAS*, Vol. 110, 10430-10437

Šopenhauer, A. (2016). *Metafizika lepog* (Metaphysics of Beauty). Beograd: Partenon

Talk Session 3

Neural Mechanisms of Musical Timing, Rhythm, and Memory

Chair: Laura Serra Marin

Time: June 11th, 15:00 – 15:50 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67394295763>

Exploring Time Perception in Music Listening: How Musical and Personal Factors Influence Duration and Speed of Time Passage

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Background Empirical evidence suggests that music influences our sense of time, involving three main factors: musical, listener-related and contextual (Phillips, 2022). However, understanding this influence is complicated by the variety of methodologies adopted across studies, such as tasks (music listening only vs background music), duration estimation methods (verbal estimates, reproduction of duration, comparison), musical stimuli durations (from seconds to 30 minutes) and musical complexity (from rhythmical sentences to sets of commercial music). Studies also differ in whether participants are informed that the experiment investigates time perception before starting it (prospective vs retrospective timing).

Aims This project focused on the role of musical factors (tempo, rhythm, meter, tonality, timbre) on listeners' subjective estimates of duration (*how long the music lasted*) and passage of time (PoT) (*how fast did time pass while listening to it*). Individual factors (age, gender, musical expertise) were also considered. To address the methodological diversity in existing literature, all experiments followed a standardized methodology, procedure and musical stimuli.

Methods Five experiments were conducted online, each dedicated to one or two musical factors. In each experiment, only the targeted factor(s) were altered in the stimuli, while other musical elements remained constant. Stimuli consisted of 19-38 second melodies (mostly single-lined), composed and recorded by musicians specifically for this project, and validated in a pre-test. For each stimulus, listeners estimated the perceived duration (using a Start/stop button to reproduce duration and then verbally, filling “__ minutes and __ seconds”), and rated PoT and enjoyment using Likert scales. Musical expertise was assessed with the Gold-MSI. Post-hoc power analysis confirmed a minimum statistical power of 0.8 for all experiments (minimum $N = 125$), except for one retrospective experiment on tempo. All factors were investigated prospectively, with tempo and tonality also being studied retrospectively.

Results Retrospective timing was only affected in PoT (not duration), with slower musical tempos leading to the perception of time passing slower. Prospective timing was influenced by all the factors studied. Faster tempos were associated with

longer duration estimates (Silva et al., 2024), while a faster accompaniment (more events, lower metrical level) led to shorter estimates compared to a slower accompaniment (less events, higher metrical level), contradicting existing evidence. Time was perceived as passing faster with a natural timbre (human voice), compared to an artificial timbre (synthesized voice). Tonality (tonal vs atonal) did not directly impact duration or PoT (Silva et al., 2024). Across all experiments, pleasant music was perceived as passing faster than unpleasant music. No effects were found for age. Higher musical training improved the accuracy of prospective duration reproductions. Sex impacted duration reproduction both prospectively and retrospectively, with males being more accurate than females.

Conclusions Pitch-related parameters (tonality and timbre) seem to primarily affect PoT and enjoyment, while temporal parameters influence both perceived duration (tempo and meter) and PoT (tempo). Future research should explore the effects of different timbres on PoT, the role of meter perception and embodiment in duration estimation, the influence of tonality, timbre, and rhythm on retrospective timing, and sex differences in the perception of duration.

References

- Phillips, M. (2022). Music Listening and the Perception of Time: The LEMI Model. In M. Phillips & M. Sergeant (Eds.), *Music and Time* (1st ed.). Boydell & Brewer.
- Silva, L. B., Phillips, M., & Martins, J. O. (2024). The influence of tonality, tempo, and musical sophistication on the listener's time-duration estimates. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 77(9), 1846–1864. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17470218231203459>

Mind the Bar: Tracing the Role of Musical Structure in EEG activity and Memory Development

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Background Memory is a key mechanism in musical performance, with research into memory for music generally focusing on its auditory and motor aspects. However, semantic and visual aspects of musical memory are also crucial to consider. Research into memorization in the field of music psychology has suggested that musical structure and performance cues play an essential role in memory formation (Chaffin et al., 2010), aligning with event segmentation theory, which emphasizes the role of event boundaries in memory processes (Zacks, 2020). Despite overlapping insights, this connection between theories has been underexplored. One of the few studies that has investigated musical structure and memory formation in the context of music learning while using neuroimaging techniques has been Williamon & Egner (2004). They identified a unique event-related potential (ERP) component for structural bars (e.g., beginning of a phrase) compared to non-structural bars and not-learned bars, suggesting an effect of structural importance on musical memory. However, limitations such as unbalanced stimuli and small sample size warrant further investigation.

Aims This study aims to replicate Williamon and Egner's (2004) study with improvements in experimental design, in order to confirm its results. This will include adding a control condition (sightreading), balancing the stimuli presented (12 structural and non-structural bars instead of 8 structural and 24 non-structural) and increasing the sample size (from 6 to 30 participants).

Methods A total of 30 participants will learn a piece of music for 2 weeks and then perform it alongside a sightreading piece, which they will have 2 minutes to look at beforehand. A visual recognition task will then be conducted while EEG data is collected. On each trial, the participant will be presented with a bar of music and asked to indicate whether they have learned that bar or not. If they identify the bar as being learned, they will be asked to say if it is from the 2-week piece or the sightreading piece. Pre- and post-experiment questionnaires will also be presented, focusing on their use of musical structure and performance cues in practice and performance, including asking participants to annotate copies of their musical scores.

Expected Results We expect to observe a more negative ERP for structural bars compared with the other bars. This ERP component is expected to be more pronounced for the 2-week piece than for the sightreading piece, and no difference in ERP components is expected for the not-learned piece. Questionnaire responses are anticipated to report the use of musical structure and performance cues in practice and performance.

Conclusions This research will confirm whether there is an observable ERP component related to structural bars, potentially providing evidence for a neuronal mechanism akin to event segmentation. Additionally, it will give initial evidence of the impact of learning (2 weeks, 5 minutes and no learning) on these musical structural neuronal mechanisms. This study will contribute to our understanding of the role of musical structure and performance cues in musical memory from the performer's perspective and its neural underpinnings.

References

- Chaffin, R., Lisboa, T., Logan, T., & Begosh, K. T. (2010). Preparing for memorized cello performance: The role of performance cues. *Psychology of Music*, 38(1), 3–30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735608100377>
- Williamon, A., & Egner, T. (2004). Memory structures for encoding and retrieving a piece of music: An ERP investigation. *Cognitive Brain Research*, 22(1), 36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogbrainres.2004.05.012>
- Zacks, J. M. (2020). Event Perception and Memory. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 71(1), 165–191. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010419-051101>

Rhythm-based Temporal Expectations: Unique Contributions of Predictability and Periodicity

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Background Anticipating events and focusing attention accordingly are crucial for navigating our dynamic environment. Rhythmic patterns of sensory input offer valuable cues for temporal expectations and facilitate perceptual processing. Rhythm-based temporal expectations may rely on oscillatory entrainment, where neural activity and perceptual sensitivity synchronize with periodic stimuli. However, whether entrainment models can account for aperiodic predictable rhythms remains unclear.

Aims Our study aimed to delineate the distinct roles of predictability and periodicity in rhythm-based expectations.

Methods Participants performed a pitch-identification task preceded by periodic predictable, aperiodic predictable, or aperiodic unpredictable temporal sequences. Additionally, electroencephalography (EEG) was recorded. By manipulating the temporal position of the target sound, we observed how auditory perceptual performance and event-related potentials (ERPs) were modulated by the target position's relative phase relationship to the preceding sequences.

Results Results revealed a significant performance advantage for predictable sequences, both periodic and aperiodic, compared with unpredictable ones. However, only the periodic sequence induced an entrained modulation pattern, with performance peaking in synchrony with the inherent sequence continuation. ERPs corroborated these findings. The target-evoked P3b, possibly a neural marker of attention allocation, mirrored the behavioral performance patterns. This supports our hypothesis that temporal attention guided by rhythm-based expectations modulates perceptual performance. Furthermore, the predictive sequences were associated with enhanced target-preceding negativity (akin to the contingent negative variation), indicating enhanced target preparation. The periodic-specific modulation likely reflects more precise temporal expectations, potentially involving neural

entrainment and/or more focused attention.

Conclusions Our findings suggest that predictability and periodicity influence perception through distinct mechanisms.

Talk Session 4

Music Applications for Health and Stress Management

Chair: Rory Kirk

Time: June 12th, 10:40 – 11:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68332075785>

The Impact of Individual Factors and Preferences on Music for Sleep

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Background Sleep is essential for human health and wellbeing, yet one third of adults experience insomnia symptoms at least once in their lifetime¹. Among different strategies that individuals use to aid sleep, music represents one of the most ancient ones, with lullabies sharing characteristics between cultures². Today, music is easily accessible, and represents a widely used strategy to fall asleep^{3,4,5,6}. Despite studies highlighting the broad variety of music for sleep⁷, there is still little insight on its specific features and on the characteristics of individuals who listen to music at bedtime. Similarly, little attention has been paid to the link between these two aspects. Our study builds on previous machine learning-based research on the characteristics of music for sleep^{7,8} and on the motivations that lead individuals to listen to music at bedtime⁴.

Aims Our study aims to model the influence of individual factors and preferences on the choice of music for sleep. This can lead to the development of more effective personalised interventions.

Methods This study was approved by Aarhus University's Research Ethics Committee and the survey was launched in December 2023. The study consists of an online survey exploring demographics, music preferences and habits, motivations and psychological factors of adults listening to music at bedtime worldwide. We also asked our participants to provide examples of music they use to aid sleep. Our aim is to link individual factors to the characteristics of music used for sleep. To protect the privacy of our participants, we didn't collect any identifying variables such as name, email address or phone number. This work uses state-of-the-art MIR techniques to characterise musical content, highlighting features such as rhythm, tonality, instrumentation, etc. The extracted MIR features are then combined with other survey data within ML-based analysis. More specifically, we calculate similarity measures between individuals both in a 'musical features space' (currently based on genre), and in an 'individual factors space' to test whether pairwise distances between individuals in the two spaces correlate. Moreover, on the musical features side, we are using dimensionality reduction techniques to identify the fea-

tures that are more important in music for sleep. We will also perform clustering on the musical features to identify distinct types of sleep music. Clustering was also applied on the individual factors based on the similarity metrics to characterise different types of individuals who use sleep music. The generalisability of these models will be tested by splitting the data between training and test sets.

Expected Results We expect to understand how the different characteristics of individuals listening to music at bedtime could influence the choice of the music used. We also expect to find a large variability in the features of sleep music, depending on individual factors. Finally, we aim to create an annotated dataset of music for sleep, that will be made openly available, and that could be used for the development of personalised recommendations.

Conclusions This study can give us insight into the link between individual characteristics and the choice of sleep music. This could ultimately lead to the creation of more personalised music-driven interventions for sleep disorders.

References

1. Morin, C. M., & Jarrin, D. C. (2022). Epidemiology of Insomnia: Prevalence, Course, Risk Factors, and Public Health Burden. *Sleep medicine clinics*, 17(2), 173–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsmc.2022.03.003>
2. Mehr, S. A., Singh, M., Knox, D., Ketter, D. M., Pickens-Jones, D., Atwood, S., Lucas, C., Jacoby, N., Egner, A. A., Hopkins, E. J., Howard, R. M., Hartshorne, J. K., Jennings, M. V., Simson, J., Bainbridge, C. M., Pinker, S., O'Donnell, T. J., Krasnow, M. M., & Glowacki, L. (2019). Universality and diversity in human song. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 366(6468), eaax0868. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax0868>
3. Morin, C. M., LeBlanc, M., Daley, M., Gregoire, J. P., & Mérette, C. (2006). Epidemiology of insomnia: prevalence, self-help treatments, consultations, and determinants of help-seeking behaviors. *Sleep medicine*, 7(2), 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2005.08.008>
4. Trahan, T., Durrant, S. J., Müllensiefen, D., & Williamson, V. J. (2018). The music that helps people sleep and the reasons they believe it works: A mixed methods analysis of online survey reports. *PLoS ONE*, 13(11), e0206531. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0206531>
5. Bjorvatn, B., Waage, S., & Saxvig, I. W. (2023). Do people use methods or tricks to fall asleep? A comparison between people with and without chronic insomnia. *Journal of Sleep Research*, 32(2), e13763. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.13763>
6. Buus, R. M., Genovese, S., & Jespersen, K. V. (2024, October 22). The Art of Sleep: Examining sleep strategies in the general population with a focus on the use of music for sleep. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/2rc4a>

7. Scarratt, R. J., Heggli, O. A., Vuust, P., & Jespersen, K. V. (2023). The audio features of sleep music: Universal and subgroup characteristics. *PLoS ONE*, 18(1), e0278813. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0278813>
8. Kirk, R., & Timmers, R. (2024). Characterizing music for sleep: A comparison of Spotify playlists. *Musicae Scientiae*, 29(1), 62-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10298649241269011> (Original work published 2025)

Soundscapes for Stress Regulation: A Multi-Modal Investigation of Psychophysiological Responses to Environmental Audio Stimuli in Hong Kong Workplaces

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Background While a large body of empirical work has focused on the capacity of music to regulate stress (Chanda & Levitin, 2013), comparatively less is known about the impact of soundscapes on psychological wellbeing. Prior research has proven strong linkages between soundscape exposure and physiological reactions (Ratcliffe, 2021), and a recent systematic review of 23 studies (Aletta et al., 2018) suggests that restorative soundscapes may speed up stress recovery and improve self-reported health conditions, especially for workplace wellness interventions. However, more research is needed to understand how different types of soundscapes—and their acoustic characteristics—contribute to stress and emotion regulation. This PhD project combines perceptual ratings of soundscapes (e.g., pleasantness, eventfulness) with acoustic predictors of affect, such as timbre-related features (Eerola et al., 2012), to examine in detail how different soundscapes influence stress-related responses and emotion (Li et al., 2024).

Aims This PhD project aims to (1) achieve an extensive comprehension of individual soundscape preferences in workplace settings in Hong Kong (Indrani et al., 2023), (2) introduce a newly composed and validated set of stimuli for the empirical study of soundscapes in stress and emotion research, and (3) investigate the physiological and psychological effects of various soundscape types on stress and emotion regulation (Sander et al., 2021). Specifically, the project explicitly compares the effects of natural sounds, noisy surroundings, and musical soundscapes on stress management and emotion regulation.

Methods The project takes a three-stage mixed-methods approach. First, a representative sample of young adults working in Hong Kong will complete an online questionnaire about their acoustic working environment and sound preferences. These results will inform the second stage of the project, consisting in the preparation of different types of soundscapes (natural sounds, noisy surroundings, and musical soundscapes) of different lengths. Behavioural ratings (perceived stress and felt emotion) will be obtained from a sample of 100 listeners. In a final experiment, 50 participants will be exposed to three different soundscapes (natural, noise, and music) in a controlled environment. Physiological responses will be assessed utilizing the Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) and Heart Rate Variability (HRV)

(Sriramprakash et al., 2017). Psychological reactions (stress, mood, emotion) will be measured pre- and post-listening using standard tools including the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), and the dimensional model of emotion (Russell, 1980). The Brief Music in Mood Regulation Scale (B-MMR) will be also used to assess mood regulation profiles of the listeners. Post-intervention interviews will supply qualitative information on participant experiences.

Expected Results Data collection for the online survey is about to start. We expect to showcase audio samples and early insights into how soundscape influences emotion and stress regulation (a set of 24-30 acoustic stimuli for soundscape research, as well as accompanying behavioral and physiological data). Overall, we expect that natural soundscapes will have better stress-reduction capabilities than the other conditions as shown by both physiological measures (GSR and HRV) and psychological evaluations (PSS and PANAS scores).

Conclusions This ongoing research aims to assist us understand how soundscapes may be used successfully to alleviate workplace stress. The generated dataset and conclusions will provide strong evidence for the crucial role of soundscapes in stress regulation.

References

- Aletta, F., Oberman, T., & Kang, J. (2018). Associations between Positive Health-Related Effects and Soundscapes Perceptual Constructs: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(11), 2392. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15112392>
- Chanda, M. L., & Levitin, D. J. (2013). The neurochemistry of music. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 17(4), 179-193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2013.02.007>
- Eerola, T., Ferrer, R., & Alluri, V. (2012). Timbre and affect dimensions: Evidence from affect and similarity ratings and acoustic correlates of isolated instrument sounds. *Music Perception*, 30(1), 49–70. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2012.30.1.49>
- Indrani, H. C., Ekasiwi, S. N. N., & Arifianto, D. (2023). Indoor soundscape model: Assessing contextual factors in open-plan offices on university campuses in Surabaya, Indonesia. *Building and Environment*, 237, 110267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110267>
- Li, Z., Ba, M., & Kang, J. (2024). Measuring soundscape quality of urban environments using physiological indicators: Construction of physiological assessment dimensions and comparison with subjective dimensions. *Building and Environment*, 257, 111549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111549>
- Ratcliffe, E. (2021). *Sound and Soundscape in Restorative Natural Environments*:

A Narrative Literature Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 570563. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.570563>

Russell, J.A. (1980). A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 39(6), 1161-1178. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0077714>

Sander, E. (Libby) J., Marques, C., Birt, J., Stead, M., & Baumann, O. (2021). Open-plan office noise is stressful: Multimodal stress detection in a simulated work environment. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 27(6), 1021–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2021.1>

Sriramprakash, S., Prasanna, V. D., & Murthy, O. V. R. (2017). Stress Detection in Working People. *Procedia Computer Science*, 115, 359–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.09.090>

How music can jeopardise the abstinence of individuals with substance use disorder

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Background Music and the use of psychotropic substances are closely linked for many individuals with substance use disorder (SUD). For some, music serves as a means for emotional regulation, perception changes, and expressing their personal and social identities (Horesh, 2010; Cournoyer Lemaire et al., 2021). While a few studies suggest that music may jeopardize abstinence (Silverman et al., 2023; Bensimon, 2024), the extent to which it can be risky, either individually or collectively, is not well understood. Various factors contribute to this risk, including socialization, social environment, personality traits, music preferences, triggering of emotional responses, and conditioning. It's important to note that the same genre of music does not carry the same risk for all individuals with SUD (Horesh, 2006/2010; Vafaie & Kober, 2022). Additionally, not all individuals affected by SUD are aware of their personal risk factors (Ree, 2016).

Aims Only basic research has been conducted internationally on the potential dangers of music during abstinence. This study aims to fill this gap in an exploratory manner for Germany by examining risk factors as described above that could jeopardise abstinence, individually and collectively.

Methods The explorative study's results are derived from semi-structured interviews with therapists ($n=13$) and groups of individuals with SUD ($N=5$, $n=38$), along with a questionnaire ($n=442$) that builds upon the interview findings. The interviews were analysed using qualitative content analysis. The questionnaire was analysed descriptively.

Results Many individuals who begin therapy view music solely as a positive influence and struggle to imagine a time when they might not want to listen to 'their' music. However, those who have relapsed indicate that music has played a direct or indirect role in their relapse. For instance, music can reinforce thoughts that grant permission for substance use; 17% of respondents reported agreeing or mostly agreeing with this idea. When someone changes their preferred substance or becomes abstinent, it often comes with a shift in their musical preferences as well. The primary reason individuals consume music is for emotion regulation, with 69% stating they do this 'often'/'always'. However, this music can evoke emotions that some find only bearable with the aid of substances. Quantitative results show that

individuals with alcohol addiction view music as a low-risk trigger, with 61% stating it doesn't trigger cravings. Conversely, consumers of other substances report higher risks: 32% say music is a non-trigger, 25% a weak trigger, and 37% a strong trigger.

Conclusions Music can pose a significant risk to achieving and maintaining abstinence, particularly for individuals who use psychotropic substances other than alcohol. For those who are unstable in their abstinence, music may be a trigger for relapse. It is crucial for individuals to recognize their specific vulnerabilities related to music and for therapy to create space to address this issue. Many people in recovery often view music positively and may not realize it can be inherently dangerous. Therefore, it is the therapist's responsibility to raise awareness about these risks and to help clients develop coping mechanisms.

References

- Bensimon, M. (2024). Beneficial and harmful music for substance use disorder clients: Implementation of the musical presentation technique. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, 87, Artikel 102121, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2024.102121>
- Cournoyer Lemaire, E., Loignon, C. & Bertrand, K. (2021). The influence of music on the addictive trajectory: a conceptual framework. *Addiction Research & Theory*, 29(6). <https://doi.org/10.1080/16066359.2021.1896710>
- Horesh, T. (2006). "Music is My Whole Life": The many Meanings of music in addicts' lives. *Music Therapy Today*, VII(2 (July)), 297–317. <http://musictherapyworld.net>
- Horesh, T. (2010). Drug Addicts and Their Music: A Story of a Complex Relationship. In D. Aldridge & J. Fachner (Hrsg.), *Music Therapy and Addictions* (S. 57–74). Jessica Kingsley Publishers. Chapter 3.
- Silverman, M. J., Bourdaghs, S., Abbazio, J. & Riegelman, A. (2023). A systematic review of music-induced substance craving. *Musicae Scientiae*, 27(1), 137–175. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10298649211030314>
- Vafaie, N. & Kober, H. (2022). Association of Drug Cues and Craving With Drug Use and Relapse: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA psychiatry*, 79(7), 641–650. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2022.1240>
- Ree, M. van de (2016). Music as a Trigger for Craving: Exploring the Phenomenon and Possible Music Therapy Approaches from a Client and Music Therapist Perspective. Master Thesis. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/50571>

Talk Session 5

Cross-Cultural Perspectives in Music Cognition and Perception

Chair: Persefoni Tzanaki

Time: June 12th, 11:40 – 12:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68332075785>

Favourite Tunes, Cultural Clues: Self-Construal and Musical Rewards

Jonathan Tang

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Background I define musical reward as the pleasurable experience associated with music and is understood as a hierarchical concept in which different subtypes are subsumed under a higher-level unitary form of reward (Dubé & Le Bel, 2003). Research has shown that multiple factors influence musical reward and its subtypes, such as personality, age, gender, musical expertise, and music-cognitive traits (Cardona et al., 2022; Gupta, 2018; Kreutz & Cui, 2022; Mas-Herrero et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2023). Although participants from different countries were recruited in these studies, it would be premature to conclude that determinants of musical reward are pancultural for two reasons. First, no cross-cultural comparisons were made, so there is no evidence for or against the theory that musical rewards differ according to cultural context. Second, culture goes beyond country and nation-state (Taras et al., 2016).

Aims This study investigates the role of self-construal in musical reward across cultures. Markus and Kitayama (1991) proposed that national differences in collectivism-individualism give rise to interdependent-independent self-construals. In collectivistic cultures, individuals construe the self as interconnected with others, known as interdependent self-construal. In individualistic cultures, individuals construe the self as distinct from others, known as independent self-construal.

Methods Four hundred and thirty-five respondents (mean age = 35.76 years; $SD = 12.63$) participated in an online study. Using Hofstede et al.'s (2010) individualism index, participants were divided into two groups based on their nationality: collectivist (<50 on the index, $n = 73$) and individualist (>50 ; $n = 361$). Participants completed the Barcelona Music Reward Questionnaire (BMRQ; $\alpha = .86$; Mas-Herrero et al., 2013) with respect to their favourite piece of music. They then completed the Self-Construal Scale ($\alpha = .84$ for interdependent self-construal; $\alpha = .82$ for independent self-construal; Singelis, 1994) and other demographic questions.

Results The one-way ANOVA revealed no significant differences between collectivist and individualist cultures on total BMRQ nor its subtypes. Separate multiple regression analyses for the two groups showed that, for the collectivist group, interdependent self-construal predicted social reward while independent self-construal predicted musical-seeking. For the individualist group, both self-construals predicted social reward and sensory-motor, interdependent self-construal predicted

emotion evocation, and independent self-construal predicted musical seeking and mood regulation subtypes.

Conclusion This study found that reward experiences with favourite music are comparable between collectivistic and individualistic cultures. However, the findings also suggest that using nationality as a proxy for collectivism–individualism may be insufficient for detecting cultural variations. Regression analyses further revealed similarities and differences between cultures. Overall, this study demonstrates the importance of incorporating specific cultural factors in cross-cultural investigations of musical reward. In other words, our sense of self, whether construed as interdependent or independent, influences the types of reward experienced with favourite music. This research presents a novel approach to cross-cultural studies of affective experiences with music, paving the way for future research exploring the intricate interplay between culture, self-construal, and musical reward. Examining the self can be a step-change to advance theory and cross-cultural understanding of affective experiences within music psychology.

References

- Cardona, G., Ferreri, L., Lorenzo-Seva, U., Russo, F. A., & Rodriguez-Fornells, A. (2022). The forgotten role of absorption in music reward. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1514(1), 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14790>
- Dubé, L., & Le Bel, J. (2003). The content and structure of laypeople's concept of pleasure. *Cognition and Emotion*, 17(2), 263–295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0269930302295>
- Gupta, U. (2018). Personality, gender and motives for listening to music. *Journal of Psychosocial Research*, 13(2), 255–273. <https://doi.org/10.32381/JPR.2018.13.02.1>
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010). *Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind* (Revised and expanded 3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Kreutz, G., & Cui, A.-X. (2022). Music empathizing and music systemizing are associated with music listening reward. *Music Perception*, 40(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2022.40.1.3>
- Markus, H. R., & Kitayama, S. (1991). Culture and the self: Implications for cognition, emotion, and motivation. *Psychological Review*, 98(2), 224–253.
- Mas-Herrero, E., Marco-Pallares, J., Lorenzo-Seva, U., Zatorre, R. J., & Rodriguez-Fornells, A. (2013). Individual differences in music reward experiences. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 31(2), 118–138. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2013.31.2.118>
- Singelis, T. M. (1994). The measurement of independent and interdependent self-

construals. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 20(5), 580–591. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167294205014>

Taras, V., Steel, P., & Kirkman, B. L. (2016). Does country equate with culture? Beyond geography in the search for cultural boundaries. *Management International Review*, 56(4), 455–487. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11575-016-0283-x>

Wang, J., Xu, M., Jin, Z., Xia, L., Lian, Q., Huyang, S., & Wu, D. (2023). The Chinese version of the Barcelona Music Reward Questionnaire (BMRQ): Associations with personality traits and gender. *Musicae Scientiae*, 27(1), 218–232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10298649211034547>

Effect of Length of the Rhythmic Cycle on its Perception and Learning. A Cross-cultural Exploration through North-Indian Rhythmic Patterns.

Nashra Ahmad, Martin Clayton, Tuomas Eerola
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Background The impact of length has been explored for musical tones and words, where participants fail to recognise longer tonal sequences, which may be recognised when played faster (Akiva-Kabiri et al., 2009). The current study extends this effect to the perception of rhythmic cycles using long cycles existing in North Indian Classical Music (NICM). Previous studies focusing on cross-cultural rhythm perception have included shorter cycled isochronous (with regular beats in a cycle) and non-isochronous (with unequal subdivisions of beats) rhythms. The existence of long rhythmic cycles in NICM, which can be both Isochronous (ISO) and Non-Isochronous (NI), has been highlighted by recent studies (Clayton, 2020; Ahmad et al., 2024).

Aims The study's primary aim is to examine the effect of the length of the rhythmic cycle, learning and rehearsal among three participant groups varying in musicianship and cultural familiarity. The study will also highlight whether the length effect is as notable as the Isochronous and Non-Isochronous nature of the meters by utilising two ISO (beats: 8, 16) and two NI (beats: 7, 10) rhythmic cycles from NICM itself.

Methods Stimuli includes four rhythmic cycles from NICM (original). ISO: Ke-hervatal (8 beats divided into 4+4) and Teental (16 beats divided into 4+4+4+4); and NI: Rupaktal (7 beats divided into 3+2+2) and Jhaptal (10 beats divided into 2+3+2+3). Test rhythmic patterns include an altered original pattern with an extra beat. Participants include 81-Culturally Familiar Non-Musicians (non-musicians from Indian Demography), 65-Culturally Unfamiliar Musicians (non-listeners of NICM and trained in Western music) and 61-Culturally Unfamiliar Non-Musicians (non-listeners of NICM). The task consisted of three parts: 1. Baseline, followed by 2. Training/short-term explicit learning, and 3. Testing. Baseline and training involved participants rating each test rhythm compared to the original rhythm on a 7-point scale of Similarity, from 'Extremely Similar' to 'Not at all Similar.' Training included explicit instructional videos of the rhythmic pattern. Each participant performed the task for only one rhythmic cycle.

Results The results highlight that cultural exposure and musical training (not in the culture) can separately affect one's ability to learn and differentiate rhythmic

patterns. Shorter rhythmic cycles were learned and recalled by Culturally Familiar Non-Musicians and Culturally Unfamiliar Musicians, and longer rhythmic cycles posed challenges. Culturally Unfamiliar Non-musician participants showed no learning or recall for the four rhythmic cycles. Furthermore, the effects of length did not stand in isolation and were impacted by the NI nature of the rhythmic patterns. This was observed as Culturally Unfamiliar Musicians could differentiate the 10-beat NI-Jhaptal before the short-term explicit learning. The study considers the chunking process to be an important factor in perceiving these rhythmic cycles.

Conclusions The study demonstrates that both cultural familiarity and musical training influence the perception and learning of rhythmic cycles, with shorter and isochronous cycles being easier to learn and recall. The chunking process and the non-isochronous nature of some cycles further modulate these effects. These findings contribute to our understanding of cross-cultural rhythm perception and the cognitive mechanisms underlying the learning of complex rhythmic structures.

References

- Ahmad, N., Clayton, M., & Eerola, T. (2024, preprint). The Role of Cultural Familiarity, Musicianship and Explicit learning in the perception of Long Rhythmic Cycles. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/ay3tk>
- Akiva-Kabiri, L., Vecchi, T., Granot, R., Basso, D., & Schön, D. (2009). Memory for tonal pitches: A music-length effect hypothesis. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1169(1), 266-269.
- Clayton, M. (2020). Theory and practice of long-form non-isochronous meters: The case of the North Indian rūpak tāl. *Music Theory Online*, 26(1).

Comparing Absolute Pitch Recognition Between Western and Carnatic Musicians

Keerthana Vishwanath, Kelly Jakubowski, Martin Clayton

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Background Absolute Pitch (AP), the ability to immediately recognize a pitch without the use of a reference/standard pitch (Deutsch, 2013), can be divided into two categories: Overt and Latent. Overt AP is the traditional form of the ability and those who possess it can provide a label using a note name (Ross et al., 2004). Latent AP is the ability to produce or identify the pitch level of melodies which are familiar without referring to specific labels (Bartlette, Henry, & Moore, 2014). While AP has been researched heavily in relation to Western Music (Levitin, 1994), some aspects, such as its testing, have not been fully researched within the context of other musical cultures.

Aims The aim of the present study is to design an AP recognition test and compare test performance between musicians who have learned Western Classical and Carnatic (South Indian Classical Music) music as well as those who have learned both styles. Additionally, this study will test the musicians' latent AP recognition.

Methods The participant pool will consist of musicians who are trained in the Western and Carnatic music traditions, as well as a subset that have learned both. Participants will answer a background survey with a series of questions regarding musicianship and demographic information. Participants will be divided into three groups based on their selection of which music tradition(s) they learned. Those who select only "Western Classical Music" are given eight blocks of five pitches each and asked to recall and identify each pitch. Those who select only "Carnatic Music" are asked to identify which shruthi (key) they sing/play in and are given the same set of blocks (modified according to the chosen shruthi) and asked to recall and identify each pitch. Those who select "Both" are given both sets of the test. All participants will then be asked to complete a Latent AP task in which they are asked to sing or hum a few phrases of two self-selected songs and describe how well they felt they recalled the pitch. Additionally, participants who choose either "Carnatic Music" or "Both" are asked to sing or hum the shruthi (single pitch) they chose.

Expected Results Data collection for this study is ongoing with expected analysis of results to be completed by July 7th. Participant responses will be analyzed to gain an understanding of the cultural differences in AP recognition and will look specifically at how participant performance compares across the two cultural groups in

both overt and latent AP tasks. The analysis of the results will also look to see if there is a correlation between performance in the two tasks and will extend to see how well those with exposure to music from both cultures perform on the test. Finally, participant responses will be analyzed to see how latent AP recognition varies between the cultures and to see if there is evidence that some Carnatic musicians have AP.

Conclusions Through this study, I hope to gain an insight into how AP recognition varies between different cultures. The results will be used to further inform the creation of tests for AP in a cross-cultural context.

References

- Bartlette, C., Henry, M. L., & Moore, J. (2014). Interaction of Relative Pitch Memory and Latent Absolute Pitch for Songs in an Ordered List. *Psychomusicology*, 24(4), 279–290. Arts Premium Collection.
- Deutsch, D. (2013). 5—Absolute Pitch. In D. Deutsch (Ed.), *The Psychology of Music (Third Edition)* (Third Edition, pp. 141–182). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-381460-9.00005-5>
- Levitin, D. J. (1994). Absolute memory for musical pitch: Evidence from the production of learned melodies. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 56(4), 414–423. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03206733>
- Ross, D., Olson, I., Marks, L., & Gore, J. (2004). A nonmusical paradigm for identifying absolute pitch possessors. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 116, 1793–1799. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1758973>

Poster Session 2

Time: June 11th, 13:30 – 14:50 UTC+2

Location:

Online Presentation: <https://sysmus25.virtualpostersession.org/>

Chunking, Duration, and Cycle Length: Cognitive Factors Affecting Rhythmic Perception in North Indian Classical Music

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Background Recent research has highlighted the existence and perception of long rhythmic cycles existing in North Indian Classical Music (NICM), which are Isochronous (ISO, regular beats) and Non-isochronous (NI, irregular beats) (Ahmad et al., 2024). Unlike most studies on meter perception, which primarily focused on short aksak-type meters, NICM's long rhythmic cycles present unique challenges to cognitive processing. Working memory and retention limit of approximately 2 seconds has been observed for speech (Baddeley, 1975), tones (Fraisse, 1963) and music (London, 2012). However, even typical long rhythmic cycles from NICM far exceed these limits (Clayton, 2020). This suggests that these rhythmic cycles from NICM likely require participants to employ chunking strategies to facilitate their recognition. Furthermore, existing research (Ding et al., 2018) suggests that working memory may prioritise the number of elements in a sequence over its duration, raising questions about the interaction between cycle length (number of beats), cycle duration (slow-fast), and rhythmic structure (ISO vs. NI). This study will address these gaps by exploring how cycle length and duration variations affect rhythmic perception, focusing on whether chunking strategies differ between ISO and NI patterns.

Aims The aims of this study were to: Investigate how cycle duration (shorter vs. longer) and number of beats (fewer vs. more) influence the perception of rhythmic patterns from NICM, explore whether chunking strategies affect recognising long rhythmic cycles, and examine whether the ISO-NI nature of rhythmic cycles influences perceptual processes.

Methods The study will recruit Western musicians unfamiliar with NICM to ensure that cultural familiarity does not influence the results. Four rhythmic cycles from NICM will be used (coded Original or N): Isochronous (ISO): Kehervatal (8 beats, divided 4+4) and Teental (16 beats, divided 4+4+4+4); Non-isochronous (NI): Rupaktal (7 beats, divided 3+2+2) and Jhaptal (10 beats, divided 2+3+2+3). Each rhythmic cycle will be presented at four durations (3.5, 4, 5, and 8 seconds). Test variations will include cycles with an additional beat (N+1) and one less beat (N-1). The task includes: (a) Forward Discrimination Task: Participants will listen to pairs of rhythmic cycles and indicate whether the second pattern is the 'same' or 'different' from the first; (b) Chunking Task: Participants will choose one of five visual representations of the rhythmic pattern (based on Bamberger, 2013), each

showing a different grouping structure, to represent how they internally processed the rhythm.

Results Data collection is ongoing, with results expected by May 2025. The analysis will include: Discrimination Performance: d-prime scores will assess how beat number, duration, and structure influence perception, Chunking: Correlations will determine if participants using chunking strategies perform better in discrimination, and ISO vs. NI Comparison: Differences between ISO and NI patterns will highlight how rhythmic structure impacts cognitive processing.

References

- Ahmad, N., Clayton, M., & Eerola, T. (2024, preprint). The Role of Cultural Familiarity, Musicianship and Explicit learning in the perception of Long Rhythmic Cycles. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/ay3tk>
- Baddeley, A. D., Thomson, N., & Buchanan, M. (1975). Word length and the structure of short-term memory. *Journal of verbal learning and verbal behaviour*, 14(6), 575–589.
- Bamberger, J. (2013). *Discovering the musical mind: A view of creativity as learning*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Clayton, M. (2020). Theory and practice of long-form non-isochronous meters: The case of the North Indian rūpak tāl. *Music Theory Online*, 26(1).
- Ding, Y., Gray, K., Forrence, A., Wang, X., & Huang, J. (2018). A behavioral study on tonal working memory in musicians and non-musicians. *PloS one*, 13(8), e0201765. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0201765>
- Fraisse, P. (1963). *The psychology of time*. Harper & Row.
- London, J. (2012). *Hearing in time: Psychological aspects of musical meter*. Oxford University Press.

Violin gesture and expressiveness: a process

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Background The performer can embody musical meaning through diverse bodily movements and facial expressions (Davidson, 2012; Poggi, D'Errico & Ansani, 2020). The research literature categorizes the performing movements in different ways, mostly according to the reference to sound-producing or ancillary gestures (Wanderley, 2006; Godøy & Leman, 2010). These movements can be used to convey emotions, communicate social cues to co-performers and interact with the audience (D'Amario et al., 2023; Puusaari, 2023). Gestures can be produced consciously or in a pre-reflective way based on the expressive intentionality of the performer (King & Ginsborg, 2011; Moura & Serra, 2024). Additionally, a gestural lexicon can be formulated and categorized (Poggi & Ansani, 2018; Moura et al., 2024), investigating both body movements and facial expressions.

Aims This ongoing PhD project attempts to explore how a violinist uses expressive gestures in rehearsals and performances. The aim is to observe whether and in which way the expressive and ancillary gesture change along the practice sessions and in the performance. To address this question, a pilot study was performed with a professional violinist as participant, playing the first movement of Hindemith's Violin Solo Sonata op. 31 n. 2. Musical characteristics and the presence of explicit dynamics and suggestions written by the composer were elements esteemed important for this research.

Methods This pilot study involves a female violinist (26 years old) who is specialized in contemporary music. The participant is required to practice the piece three times in a private setting for about 30 minutes. Each session is video recorded by the participant, who is not allowed to watch the recording. After two weeks of practice, a performance with a public audience is organized and video recorded. Afterwards, the participant is invited to observe the videos and to provide a self-reflection about the expressive musical intentions and the gestures used. Data will be analysed through a qualitative video analysis. Movements, gestures and facial expressions will be tracked through Elan software and analysed using LMA (Laban Movement Analysis). Visual data will be analysed by two independent scholars to quote the agreement through an inter-rater reliability. Video data will be integrated with the participant's thoughts, feelings and consciousness of her body movements and facial expressions during practice sessions and performance.

Results As it is an ongoing project, the results are not yet available. However, it is expected to find differences in gestures between practice sessions and the performance. The pilot study will take into consideration both a first-person perspective based on the self-reflection of the performer and a third-person perspective based on the visual data.

Conclusions In conclusion, this project will add knowledge to the field of embodiment, examining the expressive and communicative gestures of a violinist in different contexts and understanding the relevance of the presence of an audience for a performer. Furthermore, the study will expand to investigate how the violinist's movements act in different roles in chamber music ensembles.

References

- D'Amario, S., Ternström, S., Goebel, W., & Bishop, L. (2023). Body motion of choral singers. *Frontiers in psychology*, Vol. 14.
- Davidson, J. W. (2012). Bodily movement and facial actions in expressive musical performance by solo and duo instrumentalists: Two distinctive case studies. *Psychology of Music*, Vol. 40, No. 5, (pp. 595-633).
- Godøy, R.I., & Leman, M. (Eds.). (2010). *Musical Gestures: Sound, Movement, and Meaning*. Routledge.
- King, E., Ginsborg, J. (2011). Gestures and Glances: Interactions in Ensemble Rehearsal. *New Perspectives on Music and Gestures* (pp. 177-201).
- Moura, N., & Serra, S. (2024). Saxophone players' self-perceptions about body movement in music performing and learning: an interview study. *Music Perception*, Vol. 41, No. 3 (pp.199-216).
- Moura, N., Fonseca, P., Graça, J., Trovão, P., Goethel, M., Vilas-Boas, J. P., Serra, S. (2024). Video-based categorization system and frequency analysis of gestures in saxophone playing. *Psychology of music*.
- Poggi, I., & Ansani, A. (2018). The lexicon of the Conductor's gaze. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Movement and Computing, MOCO'*, Vol. 18, No. 5 (pp. 1-18).
- Poggi, I., D'Errico, F. & Ansani, A. (2020). The conductor's intensity gestures. *Psychology of music*, Vol. 49, No. 6.
- Puusaari, M. (2023). 'Leading' as a strategy in the performance-practice of contemporary solo violin music. *Music Performance Research*, Vol. 11 (pp. 85-107).
- Wanderley, M. M., & Vines, B. W. (2006). Origins and functions of clarinetists' ancillary gestures. In A. Gritten & E. King (Eds.), *Music and gesture: New perspectives on theory and contemporary practice* (pp. 165-191).

Alpha-Delta Interplay in Rhythmic Auditory Perception: Investigating the Role of Pre-Gap Alpha Power in Target Detection

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Background Previous research has established the importance of neural delta oscillations in predicting optimal stimulus timing and behavioral outcomes in auditory tasks using rhythmic stimuli (Henry & Obleser, 2012), similar to those found in music. These oscillations synchronize with rhythmic patterns, enhancing our ability to anticipate sounds. Recent studies also suggest that alpha frequencies, known for their involvement in attentional processes, contribute to this entrainment mechanism (Cabral-Calderin and Henry, 2022), further enriching our perception of musical rhythms and temporal structures.

Aims While delta oscillations synchronize with rhythmic stimuli, alpha oscillations are thought to serve a more sustained, inhibitory function in auditory perception. During rhythmic auditory stimulation, increased alpha oscillatory activity might play a role in suppressing neural entrainment to irrelevant information, potentially reflecting a more sustained mode of processing as opposed to a rhythmic one (Henry et al., 2017). However, the precise role of alpha oscillations in shaping rhythmic auditory perception remains unclear. This study aims to investigate the interplay between alpha and delta oscillations during rhythmic auditory tasks, addressing this knowledge gap.

Methods We will record EEG while participants listen to rhythmic auditory stimuli (i.e., a 2 Hz frequency modulated sound) and detect embedded targets (i.e., short gaps). Crucially, we will manipulate the predictability of target onsets within the rhythmic structure, creating conditions where targets are either randomly distributed across the rhythm or aligned with optimal detection points in the rhythm. This manipulation aims to investigate how alpha oscillations interact with rhythmic processing under varying levels of temporal predictability. We will analyze whether alpha power exhibits systematic increases or decreases between task conditions (i.e., different levels of temporal predictability).

Expected Results We expect to observe lower alpha power during blocks where targets align with optimal detection points in the rhythm compared to blocks with equally distributed targets. This pattern would support the hypothesis that alpha oscillations serve a more sustained processing mode as opposed to a strictly rhythmic

mic one, potentially reflecting reduced need for sustained inhibitory control when temporal predictions can be formed based on the rhythmic structure.

Conclusions By investigating the interplay between alpha and delta oscillations, this study seeks to provide new insights into the neural mechanisms underlying auditory attention and continuous perceptual tracking. Our findings may have implications for understanding how the brain optimizes its response to rhythmic auditory stimuli and maintains sustained attention in dynamic auditory environments. Moreover, this research could shed light on how listeners process and engage with complex musical rhythms, potentially advancing our understanding of music perception and the neural basis of musical experiences.

References

Henry, M. J., & Obleser, J. (2012). Frequency modulation entrains slow neural oscillations and optimizes human listening behavior. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(49), 20095-20100. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1213390109>

Cabral-Calderin, Y., & Henry, M. J. (2022). Reliability of Neural Entrainment in the Human Auditory System. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(5), 894-908. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0514-21.2021>

Henry, M., Herrmann, B., Kunke, D. et al. (2017). Aging affects the balance of neural entrainment and top-down neural modulation in the listening brain. *Nat Commun* 8, 15801. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15801>

Unveiling the Musical Features of EDM Subgenres: A Music Information Retrieval Approach

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Background This paper presents the first study of a PhD project focused on music-induced altered states of consciousness (ASC). In the context of raves, Electronic Dance Music (EDM) goes beyond creative expression; it serves as a powerful tool for inducing transformative spiritual experiences that can lead to profound and lasting changes in self-perception and life outlook^{1,2}. The rhythmic pulses and bass vibrations of EDM, combined with multimedia technologies, deeply engage listeners, immersing them in the music and dance experience^{3,4}. Despite the general effects of EDM in these settings, little is known about how specific musical features contribute to the induction of ASC.

Methods I will present ongoing research utilizing Music Information Retrieval (MIR) techniques to identify musical features that differentiate four EDM subgenres^{5,6}: psytrance, minimal techno, progressive house, and dubstep. We analyzed 4,676 30-second sample tracks tagged with one of the four subgenres by Spotify, extracting 30 features related to melody, harmony, rhythm, tone color, and dynamics using the Essentia library. To identify the features that best distinguish these subgenres, we applied statistical and machine learning methods, including linear discriminant analysis, logistic regression, and decision trees. Additionally, we curated a subset of 200 songs from the dataset based on expert ratings to further validate our results and create a refined dataset for future research.

Results Our findings show that features like BPM, spectral flux, attack time in low frequencies, chord change rate, onset rate and dissonance best differentiate EDM subgenres. These results will contribute to the development of EDM-like stimuli for investigating the phenomenology and neural correlates of EDM-induced altered states of consciousness in future studies.

References

1. Hutson SR. Technoshamanism: spiritual healing in the rave subculture. *Popular Music & Society*. 1999 Sep 1;23(3):53-77.
2. Sylvan R. *Trance formation: The spiritual and religious dimensions of global rave culture*. Routledge; 2013 Oct 8.

3. Weinel J. Shamanic diffusions: a technoshamanic philosophy of electroacoustic music. *Sonic Ideas/Ideas Sonicas*. 2014;6(12).
4. Simão E, de Magalhães ST. Psychedelic trance and multimedia neo-rituals: The modern shamanic tools. *Exploring Psychedelic Trance and Electronic Dance Music in Modern Culture*. Hershey: IGI Global. 2015 Aug 4:87-108.
5. Panteli M, Rocha B, Bogaards N, Honingh A. A model for rhythm and timbre similarity in electronic dance music. *Musicae Scientiae*. 2017 Sep;21(3):338-61.
6. Caparrini A, Arroyo J, Pérez-Molina L, Sánchez-Hernández J. Automatic sub-genre classification in an electronic dance music taxonomy. *Journal of New Music Research*. 2020 May 26;49(3):269-84.

Music Performance Anxiety in Former Military Musicians

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Background Music performance anxiety (MPA) is a highly prevalent issue among musicians (Kenny, 2011; Nagel, 2010). Despite extensive research, military musicians remain an understudied group, although it has been often noted that worldwide military organisations are major employers of professional musicians (Elam et al., 2022). The current study focused on MPA in military musicians who previously served in the British Army, offering an original contribution to the literature.

Aims The study aimed to assess levels of MPA by measuring competitive state anxiety and examining relationships with age, gender and military experience. Additionally, the study explored the main triggers of MPA, management techniques and participants' attitude towards MPA.

Methods Mixed method design combined quantitative and qualitative approaches through an online survey ($N = 79$), complemented by two semi-structured interviews. The survey included questions on various aspects related to MPA and Revised Competitive State Anxiety Inventory–2 (CSAI–2R; Cox et al., 2003), which measures self-confidence, somatic anxiety and cognitive anxiety.

Results Participants displayed cognitive and somatic anxiety levels similar to or higher than those in other musicians, while self-confidence scores were generally higher (Yoshie et al., 2009; Miller & Chesky, 2004; Yao & Li, 2022). Women scored higher on both anxiety measures and lower on self-confidence than men, consistent with prior research (Ackermann et al., 2014). Military experience appeared to be less associated with state anxiety than age. Most participants rated MPA as moderately negative. Cognitive and somatic anxiety scores demonstrated an inverted U-shape relationship with attitude towards MPA, whilst self-confidence was unrelated, although lowest self-confidence was shown for least negative ratings of MPA. Most frequently used management strategies were breathing techniques, similar to other musicians (Kenny et al., 2014; Miller & Chesky, 2004), and alcohol. Solo performances and pressure from self were the most common causes of MPA, similar to previous findings. Qualitative interviews identified several key themes, including military-specific demands faced by the musicians, various ways of dealing with MPA and pressure from scrutiny, judgement from others, high expectations and fear of making mistakes.

Conclusions Levels of somatic and cognitive anxiety in former military musicians were similar to or higher than those of civilian musicians, highlighting that MPA is an important issue to address in military contexts. The prominence of cognitive anxiety suggests a particular need for cognitive-based interventions, such as cognitive behavioural therapy, mindfulness and mental skills training, which have shown to be effective in previous research (Kenny, 2011; Nagel, 2010). Since alcohol was commonly mentioned by the participants and it has been shown that alcohol consumption is higher in the armed forces than in the general population (Fear et al., 2007), it is crucial to offer alternative, healthier coping strategies. Additional triggers of MPA identified by the participants, such as bullying, criticism and uniform- and weather-related pressure, propose future research directions.

References

- Ackermann, B. J., Kenny, D. T., O'Brien, I., & Driscoll, T. R. (2014). Sound Practice-improving occupational health and safety for professional orchestral musicians in Australia. *Frontiers in psychology*, 5, 973. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00973>
- Cox, R. H., Martens, M. P., & Russell, W. D. (2003). Measuring Anxiety in Athletics: The Revised Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 25(4), 519-533. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jsep.25.4.519>
- Davison, D. (2022). Sources of occupational stress among the military musicians of the Royal Air Force. *BMJ Mil Health*, 168(3), 181-185. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjmilitary-2020-001432>
- Elam, T., Mowen, S., & Jonas, C. (2022). Occupational Injuries in Musicians: A Literature Review. *Military Medicine*, 187(5-6), e619-e623. <https://doi.org/10.1093/milmed/usab499>
- Fear, N.T., Iversen, A., Meltzer, H., Workman, L., Hull, L., Greenberg, N., Barker, C., Browne, T., Earnshaw, M., Horn, O., Jones, M., Murphy, D., Rona, R.J., Hotopf, M. and Wessely, S. (2007), Patterns of drinking in the UK Armed Forces. *Addiction*, 102, 1749-1759. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2007.01978.x>
- Kenny, D. (2011). *The psychology of music performance anxiety*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kenny, D., Driscoll, T., & Ackermann, B. (2014). Psychological well-being in professional orchestral musicians in Australia: A descriptive population study. *Psychology of Music*, 42(2), 210-232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735612463950>
- Miller S. R., Chesky K. (2004). The multidimensional anxiety theory: An assessment of and relationships between intensity and direction of cognitive anxiety, somatic anxiety, and self-confidence over multiple performance requirements among col-

lege music majors. *Medical Problems of Performing Artists*, 19(1), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.21091/mppa.2004.1003>

Nagel J. J. (2010). Treatment of music performance anxiety via psychological approaches: a review of selected CBT and psychodynamic literature. *Medical problems of performing artists*, 25(4), 141–148.

Yao, Z., & Li, Y. (2022). Preliminary assessment of Individual Zone of Optimal Functioning model applied to music performance anxiety in college piano majors. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 764147. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.764147>

Yoshie, M., Kudo, K., Murakoshi, T., & Ohtsuki, T. (2009). Music performance anxiety in skilled pianists: effects of social-evaluative performance situation on subjective, autonomic, and electromyographic reactions. *Experimental brain research*, 199(2), 117–126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-009-1979-y>

Polyrhythm Meets Virtual Reality: A Novel Framework for Cognitive and Neural Research

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Background Polyrhythms, characterized by the simultaneous execution of contrasting rhythmic patterns, are fundamental to many musical traditions, such as African drumming and Indian classical music (Arom, 1991; Clayton, 2000). They engage intricate sensory and motor synchronization processes, providing a rich framework for studying brain and body dynamics. However, the steep learning curve associated with mastering polyrhythms limits their accessibility for broader research and practical applications.

Aims This project aims to develop a gamified virtual reality (VR) platform to facilitate the learning of polyrhythms. The research seeks to examine how the brain adapts to complex rhythmic structures and to explore the potential applications of polyrhythmic training in cognitive enhancement and sensorimotor integration.

Methods The VR-based training system has been developed using Unreal Engine, integrating visual and auditory feedback mechanisms based on the approach of Kovacs et al. (2010), which demonstrated the effectiveness of visual feedback in rhythm learning. The system is designed to record neurophysiological data, including electroencephalography (EEG), to analyze neural adaptations during training. The first functional prototype has been completed, and a behavioral study is being prepared to evaluate the system's usability and effectiveness in facilitating polyrhythmic learning.

Expected Results Preliminary results from the behavioral study are expected to validate the platform's ability to enhance the acquisition of polyrhythms. The study will also provide insights into the dynamics of brain activity during training, potentially revealing broader applications for cognitive rehabilitation and performance optimization.

Conclusions This project integrates VR technology, cultural rhythm practices, and neuroscience to address challenges in polyrhythm learning. The innovative approach highlights the potential of rhythm-based training in cognitive and motor function enhancement. Feedback from this presentation will guide further development and refine the research framework.

References

Arom, S. (1991). *African Polyphony and Polyrythm: Musical Structure and Methodology*. Cambridge University Press.

Clayton, M. (2000). *Time in Indian Music: Rhythm, Metre, and Form in North Indian Rag Performance*. Oxford University Press.

Kovacs, A. J., Han, C. E., & Shea, C. H. (2010). Visual feedback facilitates learning of bimanual 1:2 coordination. *Journal of Motor Behavior*, 42(3), 165–178.

Improvisational Wisdom: Nurturing Human Flourishing Through Music-Making.

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Background My project aims to combine research in music cognition, phenomenology and ethics to advance a nuanced understanding of how music both shapes and reflects the human experience. Specifically, my goal is to explore new perspectives on musical improvisation and its potential role in education and human flourishing, through a project titled *Improvisational Wisdom: Nurturing Human Flourishing Through Music-Making*. Musical improvisation is the spontaneous creation of something musically new and valuable, crafted in the moment using the resources and ideas immediately at hand. Existing literature highlights how its practice involves the development of cognitive and interpersonal skills such as imagination, adaptability, strategic thinking and collaboration, enhancing cognitive flexibility and interpersonal connection (Torrance & Schumann, 2018). Moreover, extensive studies on music practices more generally suggest that learning to play an instrument fosters human flourishing, meant as the realisation of a person's full potential, which involves living a meaningful, purposeful life in accordance with personal virtues (Silverman & Elliott, 2014). However, no research to date has explicitly examined how training in musical improvisation nurtures specific virtues.

Aims The central aim of this project is to combine empirical and theoretical research to examine how musical improvisation not only cultivates essential cognitive capacities, but also fosters the development of skills that are closely aligned with Aristotelian ethical virtues; specifically, the ability to adapt and respond thoughtfully in improvisational contexts mirrors the virtue of *phronesis* or practical wisdom.

Main Contribution The project is grounded in two foundational frameworks, that most effectively explain the connection between musical improvisation and virtues: (i) *enactive music cognition* and (ii) *virtue ethics*. The former is a recently developed approach which explores the musical mind as a mode of engagement with the environment (van der Schyff et al., 2022); the enactive perspective examines the dynamic interplay between the improvisers' actions, the sonic feedback they receive and the emergent musical structures that arise, highlighting how the improvisers' moment-to-moment interactions with their instrument and the unfolding soundscape drive their creative choices and shape the resulting musical expression, regardless of musical genre or field. The latter is an Aristotelian-derived philosophical approach that seeks to understand how a person's motivations and emotions drive

the exercise of their own virtues, defining their character in relation to the environment in which they are situated and offering valuable insights for the development of pedagogical strategies aimed at fostering these virtues in educational settings (de Caro et al., 2018). Drawing on these two approaches, my research proposes that the connection between cognitive skills derived from improvising and virtue development could provide a framework for fostering creativity, critical thinking, and interpersonal engagement, ultimately contributing to both individual and collective flourishing. Empirically, my research makes use of a qualitative approach based on semi-structured and phenomenological interviews (Høffding & Kristian, 2015) to ground such conceptual insights into the lived experiences of music improvisers with different degrees of expertise (students, professors and professional performers). Through the interviews, Aristotelian virtues - such as courage, justice, prudence and, most importantly, practical wisdom (*phronesis*) - will be examined by exploring instances of musical risk-taking, descriptions of collaborative interactions, real-time decision-making, and accounts of how improvisers exercise sound judgment and navigate unforeseen musical situations as they unfold.

Implications This research aims to propose an artistic-ethical framework for integrating improvisational activities into educational practices. By highlighting the connections between music-making, virtue development and human flourishing, the study offers innovative strategies for fostering creativity, critical thinking and interpersonal engagement in both musical and non-musical contexts. Ultimately, it seeks to demonstrate how musical improvisation can contribute to shaping individuals' character, mindsets, and approaches to life.

References

- De Caro, M., Macarthur, D., & Sandis, C. (2018). *Virtue, Emotion, and Imagination*. Oxford University Press.
- Høffding, S., & Kristian, M. (2015). *Phenomenological Approaches to Music and the Arts*. Routledge.
- Silverman, M., & Elliott, D. (2014). *Music Matters: A Philosophy of Music Education*. Oxford University Press.
- Torrance, E., & Schumann, L. (2018). *Improvisation in Cognitive and Social Contexts*. Cambridge University Press.
- Van der Schyff, D., Schiavio, A., Walton, A., Velardo, V., & Chemero, A. (2022). Musical Creativity and the Enactive Mind. *Music Perception*, 39(3), 213-226.

Exploring Music Making in Everyday Lives through a Grounded Theory Study

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Background Music exists in all known societies (Mehr et al., 2019) and the capacity to make music appears to be universal (Cross & Morley, 2010). It serves many functions—in society (e.g., social bonding and promoting prosocial behaviour (for review: Savage et al., 2021)) and for individuals (e.g., mood regulation and self-expression (for review: Schäfer et al., 2013)). However, most studies examining the role of music in people’s lives focus on music listening, which is a relatively recent phenomenon when compared with music making. Further, the motivation to make music has mainly been explored in music education, which overlooks music making as a prominent leisure activity in adults’ everyday life.

Aim Based on the lack of research on motivations on music making as a leisure time activity in everyday life, the main research question of the present study was: *Why do people make music in their everyday lives?*

Methods An in-depth qualitative online survey asking participants open-ended questions about their motivations and functions of music making in their everyday lives was conducted. Participants were recruited through social media and mailing lists of amateur orchestras, choirs etc. A sample of 13 participants [Mean age = 56.23 (*SD*: 12.25)] completed the study. Data analysis consisted of 3 stages of coding: initial coding (codes were inductively generated from the data); intermediate coding (codes were merged, simplified and grouped into categories), and advanced coding (using storyline technique and theoretical coding, the core category was conceptualized and its relation to the other categories was examined to develop the final theory).

Results The grounded theory data analysis generated 13 categories which were grouped into 3 clusters of motivations: self oriented (joy, emotional fulfilment, coping, promoting health, self esteem), other-oriented (community, supporting others, validation) and results-oriented (progress and achievement, external structures, self-actualization, using and developing skills, music itself) with the category self actualization forming the centre of the grounded theory. The resulting theory proposes that people make music in their daily lives because it gives them an opportunity to interact with themselves, with others, and the outer world, and therefore to experience and express themselves.

Conclusions This study provides valuable insights on why people make music in their everyday lives and has several implications, especially for social prescribing and the development of music-based interventions. However, the study is limited by its small and homogeneous sample and future studies should aim to address these limitations. In summary, music making is motivated by self, other and results oriented motivations to satisfy people's basic psychological needs. It is an invaluable part of their everyday lives and facilitates their journey towards self-actualisation.

References

- Cross, I., & Morley, I. (2010). The evolution of music: Theories, definitions and the nature of the evidence. In *Communicative Musicality* (pp. 61–82).
- Mehr, S. A., Singh, M., Knox, D., Ketter, D. M., Pickens-Jones, D., Atwood, S., Lucas, C., Jacoby, N., Egner, A. A., Hopkins, E. J., Howard, R. M., Hartshorne, J. K., Jennings, M. V., Simson, J., Bainbridge, C. M., Pinker, S., O'Donnell, T. J., Krasnow, M. M., & Glowacki, L. (2019). Universality and diversity in human song. *Science*, 366(6468), eaax0868. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax0868>
- Schäfer, T., Sedlmeier, P., Städtler, C., & Huron, D. (2013). The psychological functions of music listening. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 511. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00511>
- Savage, P. E., Loui, P., Tarr, B., Schachner, A., Glowacki, L., Mithen, S., & Fitch, W. T. (2021). Music as a coevolved system for social bonding. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 44, e59. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X20000333>

Impact of Tempo Fluctuations on Brain Dynamics during Naturalistic Music Listening

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Background Several studies have examined the effects of tempo variations on the brain in both controlled and naturalistic experimental settings, using either short musical excerpts with different tempos or gradual tempo changes (Thaut et al., 2014; Tian et al., 2013; Nicolaou et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2021; Cong et al., 2013; Daly et al., 2014; Weineck et al., 2022). However, they have not focused explicitly on real-time tempo changes and how these can affect musicians and non-musicians differently. Instead, they used other static measures, such as the standard deviation of tempo (Daly et al., 2014). Overall, these studies demonstrated that different tempos engage auditory, motor, and emotion-related brain areas, with faster tempos increasing motor-auditory connectivity while modulating emotional arousal.

Aims This study investigates how tempo fluctuations impact brain dynamics during naturalistic music listening, aiming to bridge the gap between artificial music listening conditions and real-world experiences, using real musical pieces with diverse tempo variabilities (Vuust & Witek, 2014). Brain dynamics here refer to the changes in neural activation and patterns involved in processing, adapting to, and responding to music (Vuust & Witek, 2014). Comparisons between musicians and non-musicians will be made, as previous research suggests that auditory-motor system interaction is stronger in musicians at the cortical level (Burunat Pérez, 2017, p. 35).

Methods The present dataset comes from the broad project “Tunteet”, used in multiple publications, which yielded significant results in group differences (see Al-luri et al., 2015, 2017; Burunat et al., 2015, 2016, 2017; Kliuchko et al., 2015). During the initial experiment, thirty-six healthy participants (18 female) listened to three pre-existing musical pieces in counterbalanced order while undergoing fMRI. Half of the participants were professional musicians, while the rest were non-musicians. Each piece lasted 8 minutes and had different levels of tempo variability and instability. The pieces’ tempo was extracted using MIR Toolbox (Lartillot & Toivainen, 2007), and its rate of change was quantified by calculating the derivative of tempo over time. This was correlated with the fMRI data over time to determine changes in brain activation throughout the listening experience. Group differences among musicians and non-musicians will be tested using non-parametric t-tests.

Expected Results Based on previous studies, it can be expected that parts of the motor system will be activated during fluctuating tempos, including the premotor cortex, basal ganglia, cerebellum, and supplementary motor area (Burunat Pérez, 2017). In addition, an increased frontal activation in the left hemisphere (Trochidis & Bigand, 2013) and temporal cortex is expected for accelerations in tempo (Liu et al., 2018), while the opposite effect is expected for decelerations of tempo.

Conclusions The study's results will provide further insights into the neural mechanisms underlying tempo fluctuations while enhancing our understanding of how the brain processes complex auditory stimuli in real-world contexts. Furthermore, these insights could have applications in neurologic music therapy (Thaut, McIntosh & Hoemberg, 2015) and inform therapeutic strategies for motor recovery after brain related injuries (Molinari et al., 2003).

References

- Alluri, V., Toiviainen, P., Jääskeläinen, I. P., Glerean, E., Sams, M., & Brattico, E. (2015). Musical expertise modulates functional connectivity of limbic regions during continuous music listening. *Psychomusicology: Music, Mind, and Brain*, 25(4), 443–454.
- Alluri, V., Toiviainen, P., Lund, T. E., Wallentin, M., Vuust, P., Nandi, A. K., & Brattico, E. (2017). Connectivity patterns during music listening: Evidence for action-based processing in musicians. *Human Brain Mapping*, 38(6), 2955–2970.
- Burunat, I., Alluri, V., Toiviainen, P., Bogert, B., Numminen, J., & Brattico, E. (2015). Dynamics of brain activity underlying working memory for music in a naturalistic condition. *Cortex*, 57, 254–269.
- Burunat, I., Toiviainen, P., Alluri, V., Bogert, B., Numminen, J., & Brattico, E. (2016). Coupling of action-perception brain networks during musical pulse processing: Evidence from region-of-interest-based independent component analysis. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 10, 230.
- Burunat Pérez, I. (2017). *Brain integrative function driven by musical training during real-world music listening* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Jyväskylä).
- Cong, F., Alluri, V., Nandi, A. K., Toiviainen, P., Fa, R., Abu-Jamous, B., ... & Ristaniemi, T. (2013). Linking brain responses to naturalistic music through analysis of ongoing EEG and stimulus features. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 15(5), 1060–1069.
- Daly, I., Hallowell, J., Hwang, F., Kirke, A., Malik, A., Roesch, E., & Nasuto, S. J. (2014). Changes in music tempo entrain movement-related brain activity. In 2014 36th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society. IEEE.

- Kliuchko, M., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Monacis, L., Gold, B., Heikkilä, K., Spinosa, V., Tervaniemi, M., & Brattico, E. (2015). The association of noise sensitivity with music listening, training, and aptitude. *Noise & Health*, 17(78), 350–357.
- Lartillot, O., & Toiviainen, P. (2007). A Matlab Toolbox for Musical Feature Extraction From Audio. In *International Conference on Digital Audio Effects, Bordeaux*.
- Liu, Y., Liu, G., Wei, D., Li, Q., Yuan, G., Wu, S., Wang, G., & Zhao, X. (2018). Effects of Musical Tempo on Musicians' and Non-musicians' Emotional Experience When Listening to Music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2118.
- Liu, Y., Lian, W., Zhao, X., Tang, Q., & Liu, G. (2021). Spatial connectivity and temporal dynamic functional network connectivity of musical emotions evoked by dynamically changing tempo. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 15, 700154.
- Molinari, M., Leggio, M. G., De Martin, M., Cerasa, A., & Thaut, M. (2003). Neurobiology of rhythmic motor entrainment. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 999(1), 313-321.
- Nicolaou, N., Malik, A., Daly, I., Weaver, J., Hwang, F., Kirke, A., ... & Nasuto, S. J. (2017). Directed motor-auditory EEG connectivity is modulated by music tempo. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 11, 502.
- Thaut, M. H., Trimarchi, P. D., & Parsons, L. M. (2014). Human brain basis of musical rhythm perception: common and distinct neural substrates for meter, tempo, and pattern. *Brain sciences*, 4(2), 428-452.
- Thaut, M. H., McIntosh, G. C., & Hoemberg, V. (2015). Neurobiological foundations of neurologic music therapy: rhythmic entrainment and the motor system. *Frontiers in psychology*, 5, 1185.
- Tian, Y., Ma, W., Tian, C., Xu, P., & Yao, D. (2013). Brain oscillations and electroencephalography scalp networks during tempo perception. *Neuroscience Bulletin*, 29, 731-736.
- Trochidis, K., & Bigand, E. (2013). Investigation of the Effect of Mode and Tempo on Emotional Responses to Music Using EEG Power Asymmetry. *Journal of Psychophysiology*, 27(3), 142–148.
- Vuust, P., & Witek, M. A. G. (2014). Rhythmic complexity and predictive coding: A novel approach to modeling rhythm and meter perception in music. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5.
- Weineck, K., Wen, O. X., & Henry, M. J. (2022). Neural synchronization is strongest to the spectral flux of slow music and depends on familiarity and beat salience. *Elife*, 11, e75515.

How does music training influence the effect of synchrony on social bonding?

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Background Social bonding is foundational to society and the need for establishing bonds with others is key in interactions between individuals and groups (Savage et al., 2020). Listening and dancing to music, singing, and playing it with others can have a positive effect in social bonds formation (Bamford et al., 2023; Pearce et al., 2015; Tarr et al., 2016; Vuoskoski et al., 2017). Movement synchrony plays a crucial role in social bonding, known as the synchrony-bonding effect (Launay et al., 2016). Music training can enhance a person's ability to synchronize with others (Tranchant et al., 2022). However, the influence a person's previous music training (MT) has on social bonding through movement synchrony remains unclear. We hypothesize that prior music training will increase social bonding through the facilitation of more accurate movement synchrony.

Aim In this study we aim to determine if previous MT influences synchronization's effect on social bonding.

Method 64 participants (32 pairs) did several randomized coordination exercises, with different coordination (synchrony, anti-phase) and leadership (leading, following, and joint) conditions. They completed a series of questionnaires before and after the exercises: the MT subscale of the Gold-MSI, Inclusion of Other in the Self (IOS) Scale, short PANAS, a familiarity scale, and three novel items created by Taylor (2019) designed to measure reliance of and on others. For statistical analysis, differences in the pre and post IOS and TC scores were evaluated with T-tests, then those scores were simplified to obtain the change scores of each. Correlation tests were run with the scores of MT and the IOS and TC change scores. For exploratory analyses, participants were separated based on their MT scores into the High Music Training (HMT) group and the Low to No Music Training (LNMT) group and running correlations between the MT and IOS scores.

Results There was no correlation between overall MT and Change in IOS scale. However, the results of the exploratory analysis indicate that there is a positive correlation between Change in IOS scale and musical training for the HMT group ($P = .025$), but not for the LNMT group ($P = .057$).

Conclusion The implications of this study will be discussed, along with the need for further research into how personal context may influence the synchrony-bonding

effect.

Auditory neural synchronization and consciousness: EEG study with binaural beats

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Background Consciousness involves the flow of neuronal information strongly linked to oscillatory synchronization in the brain (Hunt et al., 2022). The alignment between environmental rhythms and brain oscillations is known as neural entrainment (Lakatos et al., 2019), and it might play a role in states of consciousness. When it occurs in response to auditory stimuli, it is termed auditory neural entrainment - brain waves syncing with sound waves (Obleser et al., 2020; Henao et al., 2020).

Aims Building on previous research about the effects of music on people with disorders of consciousness (Lancioni et al., 2021), our study aimed to characterize and modulate states of consciousness (focused attention and mind wandering) through matching and mismatching of auditory neural entrainment (Dias da Silva et al., 2022). Furthermore, we aimed to investigate the effect of musical training on entrainment.

Methods This study used electroencephalography (EEG) and auditory stimulation (binaural beats) to investigate auditory synchronization in 5 binaural beat (BB) conditions, matched in frequency with the brain waves delta, theta, alpha, beta and gamma.

Expected Results We hypothesise that neural synchronization caused by low frequency BB will increase the power of delta, theta and alpha brain waves, and high frequency BB will entrain beta and gamma brain waves, correlating with behavioral measures of focused attention and mind wandering.

Conclusions Understanding neural synchronization with auditory stimulation in diverse states of consciousness holds potential for future research focused on improving the rehabilitation of disorders of consciousness, as well as deepening our knowledge about the effects of sound on the brain.

References

- Dias da Silva, M. R., Gonçalves, Ó. F., Branco, D., & Postma, M. (2022). Revisiting consciousness: Distinguishing between states of conscious focused attention and mind wandering with EEG. *Consciousness and Cognition*.
- Henao, D., Navarrete, M., Valderrama, M., & Le Van Quyen, M. (2020). Entrainment and synchronization of brain oscillations to auditory stimulations. *Neuroscience Research*, 156, 271–278.
- Hunt, T., Ericson, M., & Schooler, J. (2022). Where's My Consciousness-Ometer? How to Test for the Presence and Complexity of Consciousness. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 17(4).
- Lakatos, P., Gross, J., & Thut, G. (2019). A New Unifying Account of the Roles of Neuronal Entrainment. *Current Biology*, 29(18), R890–R905.
- Lancioni, G. E., Singh, N. N., O'Reilly, M. F., Sigafos, J., & Desideri, L. (2021). Music Stimulation for People with Disorders of Consciousness: A Scoping Review. *Brain Sciences*, 11(7), 858.
- Obleser, J., & Kayser, C. (2019). Neural Entrainment and Attentional Selection in the Listening Brain. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 23(11), 913–926.

The Beat Goes On: Jazz, Dance and Community in the work of Wilfrid Mellers

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Background As founding Professor of Music at the University of York in the 1960s, Wilfrid Mellers transformed higher music education in the UK. Among a range of innovations, he was the first to introduce jazz as an academic subject,¹ the first to hire an ethnomusicologist, and the first to establish a community music programme within a university. Themes of jazz, dance, and community recur throughout Mellers' work as an educator, author, and composer. These are evident in his 1969 Proms commission *Yeibichai*, inspired by the dance traditions of the Navajo people, and in his writings such as *Music and Society*,² and *Bach and the Dance of God*,³ where he argues that loss of communal dance traditions contributed to parallel declines in social cohesion. Though some in emerging fields such as popular musicology treated him as an outsider, Mellers' innovations expanded the scope of accepted academic music study, and his work paved the way for a more integrated balance between practical and theoretical methods in music education.

Aims This research aims to demonstrate how Mellers' innovations anticipated key developments in music education, and how renewed attention to his work may help address current challenges facing the sector. In the UK, where music education has experienced a 34% drop in A-level music entrants (2014–2024) and the closure of university departments,⁴ Mellers' legacy raises pressing questions for educators and policymakers: How effective is our current approach to balancing theory and practice in music education? How global should our outlook be? To what extent do we recognise the role of community, in both the learning process and its outcomes?

Main Contribution This study is the first to examine Mellers' extensive archive at the Borthwick Institute, University of York, making an original contribution to music education research. Drawing on unpublished essays, course materials, press cuttings, correspondence, and audio recordings, the research uncovers Mellers' pioneering approach to jazz, dance and the broadening of music education. Using content and thematic analysis, grounded theory, and biographical methods, the study includes key themes of jazz, dance, and community, and illuminates the rationale behind Mellers' expansive and forward-thinking educational vision in the second half of the twentieth century.

Implications This research offers valuable historical and theoretical context for music educators and policymakers. By demonstrating the long-term impact of Mellers'

inclusive and integrative approach, it suggests new possibilities for curriculum development, particularly approaches which promote breadth and balance without sacrificing depth or rigour. As the archive reveals, Mellers' philosophy, intentionally avoidant of prejudice and open to strikingly diverse musical forms and traditions, can serve as a foundation for curricula which incorporate rhythm, movement, and collaboration in meaningful and transformational ways.

References

1. 'York digs jazz - academically!', *Downbeat*, date unknown, found in Mellers Collection, Uni. of York
2. Mellers, Wilfrid, *Music and Society* (London: Dennis Dobson, 1946)
3. Mellers, Wilfrid, *Bach and the Dance of God* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1981)
4. UK Music, "UK Music Congratulates A-Level Music Students and Issues Call for More Music Teachers," *UK Music*, 15 August 2024, <https://www.ukmusic.org/news/uk-music-congratulates-a-level-music-students-and-issues-call-for-more-music-teachers/>

MUSIFEAST-17: MUsic Stimuli for Imagination, Familiarity, Emotion, and Aesthetic STudies across 17 genres

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Background Musical stimuli are commonly used in psychological research for investigating a range of emotional, cognitive, and physiological processes. Despite this widespread use, many studies continue to rely on ad hoc music stimulus selection, compromising experimental control, reliability, and comparability of results across studies. Existing musical stimulus sets tend to be limited in variability in terms of style (e.g., comprising 1-3 genres) and familiarity (e.g., focusing on highly familiar or unfamiliar music) (Aljanaki et al., 2021; Belfi & Kacirek, 2021; Rainsford et al., 2018; Strauss et al., 2024)

Aims In this paper, we introduce MUSIFEAST-17; a music stimulus set featuring 356 instrumental 30-second clips from commercially released music across 17 genres, aiming to contribute ecological validity to studies tailored for UK and US listeners. Designed to reflect the diversity of everyday Western musical experiences, MUSIFEAST-17 includes art music, popular music, and music composed for media. MUSIFEAST-17 includes normative data from UK and US participants, sampled evenly across adulthood (ages 18–75), on familiarity, enjoyment, emotional expression, perceived contrast, genre recognition, thought types, and contextual associations evoked by each excerpt.

Methods A systematic approach was used to compile 356 instrumental music clips across 17 genres — Ambient, Classical, Country, Dance, Electronic, Film Music, Folk, Funk, Hip-hop, Jazz, Metal, Pop, R&B, Rock, Video Game Music, Sixties Pop, and Eighties Pop — selected based on 2024 UK and US listening statistics. Clips were 30-second instrumental sections from commercially released tracks containing no lyrics (allowing non-lexical vocables such as “oh” or “la”). Participants ($N=701$) were balanced across eight demographic groups partitioned by the two nationalities (UK/US) and four age groups (18-30, 31-45, 46-60, 61-75). Each participant heard and rated 17 clips (one from each genre) on clip familiarity, style familiarity, contrast, enjoyment, valence, and arousal, including responses on perceived genre, perceived decade and location of creation, thought types (Jakubowski et al., 2024), and contextual associations evoked by the music.

Results Analyses indicated that, while some responses vary by genre, nationality, and age group, MUSIFEAST-17 overall exhibits stylistic diversity, spans fa-

miliar to unfamiliar music, covers a broad emotional expression spectrum across valence and arousal, and is broadly perceived as Western music (originating from US/Canada/Europe). Common reported thought type occurrences included media memories, fictional imaginings, and autobiographical memories, with frequent contextual associations such as “movie”, “club”, and “concert”, reported across genres.

Conclusions The MUSIFEAST-17 stimulus set, with included normative data, offers a valuable tool for systematic stimulus selection for diverse applications within psychology, such as emotion studies, aesthetic studies, and music-evoked imaginings. With availability through an online repository, MUSIFEAST-17 promotes Open Science practices, facilitates cross-study comparisons, collaboration, and interdisciplinary research endeavours.

References

- Aljanaki, A., Kalonaris, S., Micchi, G., & Nichols, E. (2021). MCMA: A Symbolic Multitrack Contrapuntal Music Archive. *Empirical Musicology Review*, 16(1), 99–105.
- Belfi, A. M., & Kacirek, K. (2021). The famous melodies stimulus set. *Behavior research methods*, 53, 34-48.
- Jakubowski, K., Margulis, E. H., Taruffi, L. (2024). Music-Evoked Thoughts: Genre and Emotional Expression of Music Impact Concurrent Imaginings. *Music Perception*, 42(1), 3–18.
- Rainsford, M., Palmer, M.A., & Paine, G. (2018). The MUSOS (MUSIC SOFTWARE SYSTEM) Toolkit: A computer-based, open source application for testing memory for melodies. *Behavior Research Methods*, 50, 684–702.
- Strauss, H., Vigl, J., Jacobsen, P. O., Bayer, M., Talamini, F., Vigl, W., Zangerle, E., & Zentner, M. (2024). The Emotion-to-Music Mapping Atlas (EMMA): A systematically organized online database of emotionally evocative music excerpts. *Behavior Research Methods*, 56, 3560–3577.

The Top-down Control of Entrained Delta Oscillations during Rhythmic Auditory Perception: The Effect of Target Onset Predictability

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Background Neural entrainment, the alignment of neural oscillations to rhythmic sensory input, has been observed for a variety of stimuli (Lakatos et al., 2008, 2019). Neural entrainment is an adaptive mechanism aiding auditory processing through the extraction of and subsequent alignment to pacing signals in auditory information (Henry & Obleser, 2012; Lakatos et al., 2019). Behaviourally, neural entrainment can be reflected in enhanced sensory perception performance at time points that can be predicted from rhythmic stimuli (i.e., musical beat).

Aim The current study aims to examine if neural delta phase predicts detection of near-threshold sensory targets embedded in rhythmic stimuli. Since our understanding of top-down influences on neural entrainment remains incomplete (Lakatos et al., 2019), a second aim is to investigate potential top-down influences through manipulation of target predictability.

Methods The current study adapts Cabral-Calderin and Henry's (2022) research design, in which participants listen to a 2 Hz-frequency-modulated sound and detect near-threshold targets (i.e., short gaps) by button press. Meanwhile, an electroencephalogram will be recorded to measure neural entrainment. Crucially, a block design has been implemented to manipulate target predictability in the rhythmic stimuli. This block implementation allows for comparison of predictably distributed targets, the optimal block, with randomly distributed targets, the control block.

Expected Results It is hypothesised that the neural delta phase predicts target detection performance. More specifically, that the target detection rate will be higher for targets that coincide with a specific (optimal) neural delta phase compared to targets coinciding with the opposing phase (anti-phase). Furthermore, this effect may be more pronounced for the optimally predictable blocks, due to the potential top-down suppression of neural entrainment in the control block, as this condition puts higher demands on sustained monitoring (non-rhythmic) to optimize detection performance.

Conclusion These results would contribute to previous research on the relationship between entrained delta phase and sensory perception performance. Additionally, these findings would offer novel insights on the influence of target predictability, providing a window into the top-down influences on neural entrainment. These findings will extend the research literature on neural entrainment which, in turn, hold implications for research areas concerning individual differences in rhythm, music, and speech processing.

References

- Cabral-Calderin, Y., & Henry, M. J. (2022). Reliability of Neural Entrainment in the Human Auditory System. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(5), 894–908. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0514-21.2021>
- Henry, M. J., & Obleser, J. (2012). Frequency modulation entrains slow neural oscillations and optimizes human listening behavior. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(49), 20095–20100. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1213390109>
- Lakatos, P., Gross, J., & Thut, G. (2019). A New Unifying Account of the Roles of Neuronal Entrainment. *Current Biology*, 29(18), R890–R905. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2019.07.075>
- Lakatos, P., Karmos, G., Mehta, A. D., Ulbert, I., & Schroeder, C. E. (2008). Entrainment of Neuronal Oscillations as a Mechanism of Attentional Selection. *Science*, 320(5872), 110–113. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1154735>

Which role does harmonic clarity play in sound preference across species?

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Background Music is a unique communication system rooted in human biology. Its evolution can be studied by comparing abilities that are shared between species and were possibly shaped by similar selective pressures. Human vocalizations and music feature clear harmonics (integer multiples of the sound's fundamental frequency, unobscured by noise) that help voices merge while singing together, fostering adaptive social bonding and making clear harmonics attractive to humans. Following this reasoning, known as the *vocal similarity hypothesis* (e.g., Bowling, 2023; Bowling et al., 2018), we hypothesized that, conversely, species with noisy vocalizations would prefer noisy sounds. Budgerigars (*Melopsittacus undulatus*), a parrot species, mainly produce noise-obscured harmonics but possess traits analogous to those important for music (e.g., vocal learning and vocal coordination).

Aim and Methods To test the hypothesis that preference is based on attributes in a species' own vocalizations, three experiments were conducted using a place preference paradigm (see Hoeschele & Bowling, 2016; Wagner et al., 2020), where the time spent with different sounds served as an indicator of preference. If an individual moved onto one of the three options in a place preference arena (Budgerigars: perches; Humans: mats), playback of noisy or clear sounds was triggered, while one option remained silent.

Results Unexpectedly, budgerigars overall exhibited no preference for either clear or noisy sounds, while humans showed a preference for clear sounds.

Discussion This indicates that sound preferences might be influenced by additional factors shared across species, such as arousal cues. This opens up the exciting possibility of examining how different species utilize the harmonic frequency spectrum, with consideration of traits like vocal learning and the aforementioned additional factors. This can enhance our understanding of the biological foundations of sound preferences and further clarify potential evolutionary functions of music.

References

- Bowling, D. L. (2023). Vocal similarity theory and the biology of musical tonality. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 46, 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2023.05.006>
- Bowling, D. L., Purves, D., & Gill, K. Z. (2018). Vocal similarity predicts the relative

attraction of musical chords. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(1), 216–221. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1713206115>

Hoeschele, M., & Bowling, D. L. (2016). Sex Differences in Rhythmic Preferences in the Budgerigar (*Melopsittacus undulatus*): A Comparative Study with Humans. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 07. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01543>

Wagner, B., Bowling, D. L., & Hoeschele, M. (2020). Is consonance attractive to budgerigars? No evidence from a place preference study. *Animal Cognition*, 23(5), 973–987. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-020-01404-0>

Accessible instrument performance for everyone: gesture controlled Guzheng, an example of traditional instrument innovation based on audio-visual interaction

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Background Traditional instruments use fingers or airflow created by mouth muscles to change the sound. The performance technique requires a long period of training, discouraging people with disabilities or people with no training from engaging with sound-making expression (1). Accordingly, some instruments that require high performance techniques are fading in musicians' memory. Since 1960s, many musicians use effect pedals while aiming to create novel sounds with musical instruments and perform with no necessary conventional musical skills (2). However, effect pedal is a pre-set black box with limited effects, and does not allow full freedom of creativity. Also, the more effects there are on a pedal, the more expensive and more difficult to learn they are. This runs counter to the idea of making them less difficult to play, and also more interesting and appealing to more musicians.

Aims With the development of interaction design, it is possible to innovate the sound of traditional musical instruments through technology, and use a more instinctual approach, the gestural control to creative performance (3), so that more people can rediscover the instrument and the joy of music. Using Jitter image functions and MSP sound functions, I tried to use non-contact gestures to shape the sound of Guzheng, a traditional Chinese stringed instrument.

Methods Guzheng is amplified by a microphone in the resonance case. The microphone is connected with computer through sound card or USB. Sounds from guzheng are treated inside MAX 8 (Cycling 74 version 8.5.6). A camera is capturing a live video feed of the musician and the instrument. The data is loaded by `jit.grab` function, and the min/mean/max value (3m values) of each plane is extracted by `jit.3m` function. I connect those values with `pitch` and `overdrive` function in order to change the Guzheng sound. Finally, the influenced sound is projected into space via speaker(s).

Results Musicians can use the Guzheng in order to create sounds both in conventional and innovative ways. When musician performs and moves naturally with the music, the 3m values vary synchronously. Pitch and overdrive change the Guzheng sound according to 3m values, resulting the music is affected by musician's movement. The wider range the movement is, the greater change in music, making music

more responsive to instinctual emotion.

Conclusions I've performed this Guzheng-gestural interactive set-up in more than 40 concerts and workshops through Asia and Europe (4). The traditional instrument Guzheng gets more attention. Also, many musicians are willing to try this interactive set-up on their instrument. This will help to discover more creative possibilities especially in improvisation (5). In my future research, I am considering using electromagnetic induction, skin electricity or EEG for interaction and more sophisticated sound synthesis engineering to make the Guzheng sound richer.

References

- (1) Morreale, F., Bin, S. M. A., McPherson, A., Stapleton, P., & Wanderley, M. (2020). A NIME Of The Times: Developing an Outward-Looking Political Agenda For This Community. *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, 160–165. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4813294>
- (2) Pedal town, *A Brief history of Guitar Effects Pedals*, <https://pedaltown.nl/en/a-brief-history-of-guitar-effects-pedals> Consulted the 17 January 2025.
- (3) Mice, L., Mcpherson, A. (2020). From miming to NIMEing: the development of idiomatic gestural language on large scale DMIs. *International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4813200>
- (4) Yellow Wasabi, *Yellow Wasabi -- Timeline*, <https://yellowwasabi.net/timeline.html> Consulted the 17 January 2025.
- (5) Ciufo, T., Dvorak, A., Haaheim, K., Hurst, J., IONE, Leu, G. S., Miller, L., Mizumura-Pence, R., Oddy, N., Stewart, J., Sullivan, J., Tucker, S., Waterman, E., & Wilks, R. (Eds.). (2024). *Improvising Across Abilities: Pauline Oliveros and the Adaptive Use Musical Instrument*. University of Michigan Press. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.11969438>

Shared Musical Understanding in Live Performance: A Review and Conceptual Framework

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Background *Shared understanding* refers to the overlap of conceptual cores and the coordination of mental models (Pennington, 2016). More recent approaches highlight its dynamic, distributed, and interactional construction in real-time settings (Goodwin, 2017). Live music performance may serve as an ideal setting to explore this in detail, offering a rich environment for examining how shared understanding is constructed and negotiated in practice. In such a context, performers are seen to engage in the dynamic integration of internal intentions with external perceptual and interactional cues, continuously adjusting their actions in response to the unfolding musical environment (Reybrouck & Schiavio, 2024), while audiences (including co-performers as active listeners) engage through listening shaped by co-presence and affective resonance (Bishop & Goebel, 2018). Recent studies have examined how performers' structured and spontaneous intentions shape musical coordination in performance (Bishop, 2018); how variations expressive parameters preserve musical identity while enabling interpretive nuance (Gabrielsson & Juslin, 1996); and how musical expression evokes synchronised emotional and physiological responses between performers and audiences (Lauria, 2023). While previous studies have proposed influential models of musical interaction—such as GERMS model (Juslin & Västfjäll, 2008) of musical expression and Keller's (2014) framework linking behavioural cues with psychological coordination mechanisms—these approaches often focus separately on expressive structure or performer collaboration. To fully understand how performers and audiences co-experience live performance, however, a more integrated perspective is needed.

Aims The present contribution aims to systematically analyse the existing literature on music sense-making, focusing on three key dimensions: intention, expressivity, and emotion, and integrate these dimensions into a conceptual framework - *shared musical understanding* - that focuses on how musical meaning emerges through dynamic engagement between performers and audiences.

Main Contribution Live musical performance provides a paradigmatic context for studying real-time interpersonal interaction, making it especially suited for investigating how performers and audiences construct shared musical understanding. Much of the existing research on interaction has focused on the triadic relationship between intention, action, and emotion. Specifically, individuals engage with their

environment through internally driven intentional actions, while the external environment influences them through emotional feedback (Peng et al., 2022). However, live performance involves interactional dynamics that go beyond such linear models. The present contribution reviews literature on musical sense-making in live contexts and proposes three interrelated dimensions—intention, expressivity, and emotion—as central to this process. Structured and spontaneous intentions guide coordination; expressivity translates interpretative actions into perceivable form and evokes affective responses; emotion involves synchronised affective states that shape the musical experience for both performers and audiences. These dimensions have been applied in preliminary video analysis to explore their potential in identifying key interactional features of live performance.

Implications The proposed framework may offer a novel starting point for research on performer–audience interaction, providing an approach for investigating how intention, expressivity, and emotion recursively interact and in real time. It may be applied across different musical genres and ensemble settings to support future work on shared musical experience.

References

- Bishop, L. (2018). Collaborative Musical Creativity: How Ensembles Coordinate Spontaneity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1285. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01285>
- Bishop, L., & Goebel, W. (2018). Performers and an active audience: Movement in music production and perception. *Jahrbuch Musikpsychologie*, 28, e19. <https://doi.org/10.5964/jbdgm.2018v28.19>
- Gabrielsson, A., & Juslin, P. N. (1996). Emotional Expression in Music Performance: Between the Performer's Intention and the Listener's Experience. *Psychology of Music*, 24(1), 68–91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735696241007>
- Goodwin, C. (2017). *Co-Operative Action*. Cambridge University Press; Cambridge Core. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781139016735>
- Juslin, P. N., & Västfjäll, D. (2008). Emotional responses to music: The need to consider underlying mechanisms. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 31(5), 559–575. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X08005293>
- Keller, P. (2014). Ensemble Performance: Interpersonal Alignment of Musical Expression. In D. Fabian, R. Timmers, & E. Schubert (Eds.), *Expressiveness in music performance* (1st ed., pp. 260–282). Oxford University Press/Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199659647.003.0015>
- Lauria, F. (2023). Affective Responses to Music: An Affective Science Perspective. *Philosophies*, 8(2), 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies8020016>

Peng, W., Hu, Y., Xie, Y., Xing, L., & Sun, Y. (2022). *CogIntAc: Modeling the Relationships between Intention, Emotion and Action in Interactive Process from Cognitive Perspective* (No. arXiv:2205.03540). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.03540>

Pennington, D. (2016). A conceptual model for knowledge integration in interdisciplinary teams: Orchestrating individual learning and group processes. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 6(2), 300–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13412-015-0354-5>

Reybrouck, M., & Schiavio, A. (2024). Music performance as knowledge acquisition: A review and preliminary conceptual framework. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1331806. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1331806>

The Role of Cultural and Language Familiarity in Cross-Cultural Emotional Communication in Music Performance

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Background Cultural familiarity plays a crucial role in effective emotional communication in music performance. The theory of cultural distance and dialect (Laukka & Effenbein, 2020) suggests that cultural and linguistic backgrounds influence emotional expression and recognition. Previous research indicates that individuals from similar cultural contexts are better at understanding each other's emotional expressions in music (Argstatter, 2015; Balkwill et al., 2004; Laukka et al., 2013). However, the extent to which cultural and language familiarity influence the accuracy of music communication has not been fully explored.

Aims This study aims to examine how varying levels of cultural and language exchange affect music emotion communication among Chinese and British participants, focusing on the impact of cultural, educational, and linguistic contexts on both performers' emotional expression and listeners' perception.

Methods The study will involve violinists from China and the UK performing folk excerpts. These performances will vary in expressiveness (deadpan and expressive) and convey the emotions of tenderness, happiness, sadness, and anger. The recorded performances will serve as stimuli for listener participants from both countries, who represent a range of cultural exchange and language familiarity experiences, from minimal to extensive. Participants will be tasked with identifying the emotions expressed in the audio recordings, and their accuracy will be analyzed. In addition, performers and listeners will complete a demographic questionnaire (age, gender, education, musical training, and cultural background), along with a cultural familiarity survey assessing their exposure to Chinese and Western music, media, and languages. Performers will also complete the Big Five Personality Questionnaire (Gosling et al., 2003), while listeners will complete the 31-item Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy (QCAE) (Reniers et al., 2011).

Expected Results It is hypothesized that participants will recognize emotions more accurately when they share cultural or linguistic familiarity with the performers. If supported, the results could highlight the potential role of cultural and linguistic familiarity in enhancing emotion recognition in music.

Conclusions This study will deepen the understanding of how sociocultural factors influence emotional communication in music. By identifying key factors that

affect emotion recognition, the study will offer insights into how performers and listeners navigate emotional expression across cultural divides. The findings will have implications for psychology, music education, linguistics, and cross-cultural studies, emphasizing the importance of cultural and linguistic familiarity in emotional communication in music.

References

- Argstatter, H. (2015). Perception of basic emotions in music: Culture-specific or multicultural? *Psychology of Music*, 44(4), 674–690. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735615589214>
- Balkwill, L., Thompson, W. F., & Matsunaga, R. (2004). Recognition of emotion in Japanese, Western, and Hindustani music by Japanese listeners¹. *Japanese Psychological Research*, 46(4), 337–349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5584.2004.00265.x>
- Gosling, S. D., Rentfrow, P. J., & Swann Jr, W. B. (2003). A very brief measure of the Big-Five personality domains. *Journal of Research in personality*, 37(6), 504–528.
- Laukka, P., Eerola, T., Thingujam, N. S., Yamasaki, T., & Beller, G. (2013). Universal and culture specific factors in the recognition and performance of musical affect expressions. *Emotion*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031388>
- Laukka, P., & Elfenbein, H. A. (2020). Cross-Cultural Emotion Recognition and In-Group Advantage in Vocal Expression: A Meta-Analysis. *Emotion Review*, 13(1), 175407391989729. <https://doi.org/10.1177/175407391989729>
- Reniers, R. L., Corcoran, R., Drake, R., Shryane, N. M., & Völlm, B. A. (2011). The QCAE: A questionnaire of cognitive and affective empathy. *Journal of personality assessment*, 93(1), 84-95.

Exploring the role of music in enhancing the well-being of Chinese international students in the UK.

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Background International students face significant challenges abroad, including sociocultural issues like isolation and cultural adaptation, psychological struggles such as anxiety and homesickness, academic difficulties due to unfamiliar teaching styles, and economic pressures from high costs (Alharbi & Smith, 2018; Oduwaye et al., 2023). This is particularly relevant for Chinese international students, who represent 32% of non-EU international students in the UK, with a 50% enrollment increase over the past five years (HESA, 2023). While music is recognized for its therapeutic potential in supporting mental and physical health (Dingle et al., 2021), limited research explores its role in mitigating these challenges for international students. This study addresses this gap by examining how Chinese international students perceive and use music to navigate their well-being during their studies abroad.

Aims This study aims to: explore the ways Chinese international students in the UK engage with music in daily life and investigate their subjective perceptions of music's role in enhancing physical, emotional, social, and academic well-being.

Methods Design: A qualitative study using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to prioritize participants' lived experiences. Participants: Fifteen Chinese international students (aged 20–28) enrolled at UK universities were recruited through university forums, WeChat groups, and snowball sampling. Data Collection: Semi-structured interviews (20–30 minutes) were conducted in Mandarin to ensure linguistic and cultural comfort. Questions focused on music habits, perceived benefits, and contextual challenges. Interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated into English for analysis. Analysis: Thematic analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach, including iterative coding, theme development, and reflexive journaling to minimize researcher bias.

Results Five themes emerged from participants' accounts: 1) Physical Well-being: Participants described using upbeat playlists (e.g., pop, electronic) to motivate exercise and instrumental music (e.g., classical, ambient) to improve sleep quality. 2) Social Connection: Shared musical activities—karaoke nights, collaborative playlists, and concert attendance—fostered peer bonding and reduced feelings of isolation. 3) Emotional Regulation: Nostalgic music (e.g., Mandarin ballads, folk songs) alleviated homesickness, while calming genres (e.g., lo-fi, nature sounds) helped man-

age academic stress. 4) Academic Focus: Background music (e.g., classical, instrumental, white noise) was reported to enhance concentration during study sessions, though preferences varied by task complexity. 5) Meaning of Life: Music created personal “zones” for relaxation and focus, while learning music boosted self-fulfillment and achievement.

Conclusions Chinese international students perceive music as a versatile, culturally resonant tool for enhancing well-being. Their engagement with music reflects both universal therapeutic mechanisms (e.g., stress reduction) and culturally specific practices (e.g., nostalgic Mandarin lyrics). Universities could support students by creating music-friendly spaces, organizing culturally inclusive music events, and offering music therapy programs. Future research should explore cross-cultural differences in music engagement and longitudinal impacts of music-based interventions.

References

- Alharbi, E. S., & Smith, A. P. (2018). Review of the Literature on Stress and Well-being of International Students in English-Speaking Countries. *International Education Studies*, 11(6), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v11n6p22>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>
- Dingle, G. A., Sharman, L. S., & Bauer, Z. (2021). How do music activities affect health and well-being? A scoping review of studies examining psychosocial mechanisms. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.713818>
- HESA. (2023). Higher education student statistics: UK, 2022/23. Retrieved from <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/19-01-2023/sb265-higher-education-student-statistics/numbers>
- Oduwaye, O., Kiraz, A., & Sorakin, Y. (2023). A trend analysis of the challenges of international students over 21 years. *SAGE Open*, 13(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231210387>

Talk Session 6

Music Interventions for Aging and Neurological Conditions

Chair: Oliver Tab Bellmann

Time: June 12th, 15:00 – 15:50 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/68332075785>

Self-regulatory functions of musical imagery in Parkinson's

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Background Parkinson's disease is a neurodegenerative condition that, due to the loss of dopaminergic neurons in the brain, results in both motor (e.g., tremor, freezing) and non-motor symptoms (e.g., anxiety, apathy). While traditional treatments (e.g., medication and physiotherapy) primarily improve motor rehabilitation (e.g., Goodwin et al., 2008), additional therapies have been developed to address mood and adherence to physical programs, such as music and dance therapies (e.g., Hackney & Earhart, 2010; Pantelyat et al., 2016). A relatively new trend in music-based Parkinson's research is the use of musical imagery (e.g., Poliakoff et al., 2023), which is the mental representation of music without any acoustic stimulation (Jakubowski, 2020). While research has primarily focused on the potential of musical imagery for motor rehabilitation in Parkinson's (e.g., Schaefer, 2023), Poliakoff et al. (2023) also report its emotional-motivational aspects among people with Parkinson's (PwP), suggesting it could serve as a potential rehabilitation strategy. However, further research into the specific self-regulatory functions of musical imagery in PwP is needed to advance therapeutic approaches.

Aims This exploratory study aimed to identify self-regulatory functions of musical imagery in PwP within an intervention-like setting. Additionally, it sought to create a catalogue of music that could serve as musical imagery for each function.

Methods A qualitative design following the approach of a diary study was chosen. Over a 24-week period (12 weeks per group), 26 PwP (16 female) participated in weekly phone interviews while taking part in a music- and movement-based group intervention that introduced and taught the concept of musical imagery. The interviews were designed to capture the occurrence of musical imagery, the music serving as such, reasons for the occurrences (voluntary or involuntary), and emotional states during the occurrences. The phone interviews, which lasted between six and 20 minutes, were recorded and transcribed. Thematic analysis (Kuckartz, 2019) was used to identify overarching themes and their interactions.

Results Five overarching themes were identified: motivation, movement control, relaxation, reminiscence and positive mood regulation. Subthemes included pas-time/background under motivation; personal relation, Parkinson's relation, and familiarity under reminiscence; and walking, freezing, shaking, motor imagery, exercising, and voice exercise under movement control. For relaxation, subthemes

included pain reduction and distraction, while positive mood regulation also encompassed the feeling of company. Furthermore, a strong interaction between the themes were indicated by the repeated occurrence of the same musical images for different emotional-motivational functions.

Conclusions This study represents an important step towards understanding the potential of musical imagery as a therapeutic approach for improving both motor and non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's. Further steps include administering the Involuntary Musical Imagery Scale (Floridou et al., 2015) on a Parkinson's cohort to validate the qualitative findings using a standardized questionnaire. Furthermore, a computational analysis of the music is planned to explore any overarching musical characteristics associated with each emotional-motivational function.

References

- Floridou, G. A., Williamson, V. J., Stewart, L., & Müllensiefen, D. (2015). The Involuntary Musical Imagery Scale (IMIS). *Psychomusicology: Music, Mind, and Brain*, 25(1), 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pmu0000067>
- Goodwin, V. A., Richards, S. H., Taylor, R. S., Taylor, A. H., & Campbell, J. L. (2008). The effectiveness of exercise interventions for people with Parkinson's disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Movement Disorders*, 23(5), 631–640.
- Hackney, M. E., & Earhart, G. M. (2010). Effects of dance on movement control in Parkinson's disease: a comparison of Argentine tango and American ballroom. *Journal of rehabilitation medicine*, 42(10), 973–981.
- Jakubowski, K. (2020). Musical imagery. In *The Cambridge handbook of the imagination* (p. 187). Cambridge University Press.
- Kuckartz, U. (2019). Qualitative Text Analysis: A Systematic Approach. In G. Kaiser & N. Presmeg (Eds.), *Compendium for Early Career Researchers in Mathematics Education* (pp. 181–197). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15636-7_8
- Pantelyat, A., Syres, C., Reichwein, S., & Willis, A. (2016). DRUM–PD: The use of a drum circle to improve the symptoms and signs of Parkinson's disease (PD). *Movement disorders clinical practice*, 3(3), 243–249.
- Poliakoff, E., Bek, J., Phillips, M., Young, W. R., & Rose, D. C. (2023). Vividness and Use of Imagery Related to Music and Movement in People with Parkinson's: A Mixed-methods Survey Study. *Music & Science*, 6, 20592043231197919. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20592043231197919>
- Schaefer, R. S. (2023). Imagery and movement in music-based rehabilitation and music pedagogy. In M. B. Küssner, L. Taruffi & G. A. Floridou (Eds.), *Music and mental imagery* (p. 211–220). Routledge.

Becoming me with music - a qualitative investigation of older adults' autobiographical narratives on music, identity and wellbeing

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Background Music has the ability to provide older adults with tools to understand and develop their identity, and therefore contribute to their wellbeing and positive ageing (Hays & Minichiello, 2005). It is recognized that music can be used as e.g. a technology of self (DeNora, 2000), and as a cultural immunogen (Ruud, 2013) throughout the lifespan, but there have been few studies to investigate the role that music has particularly in older adults' lives and how their preferences might change over ageing (Greenberg & Rentfrow, 2017), or how receptive musical activities of non-musicians might shape one's musical identity (Rickard & Chin, 2017). Also, so called healthy older adults are in minority regarding research on the connection of music and wellbeing (Siltainsuu & Peltola, 2024).

Aim This study aims to explore how older individuals' (mostly non-musicians in relatively good health) lifelong relationship with music has contributed to their identity formation and subjective wellbeing, according to their own experiences. We also aim at mapping the possible age-specific features of the musical identity of an older individual.

Method An interpretive phenomenological analysis was conducted of written musical life narratives ($n=18$, western participants aged 61-91, 14 females) and semi-structured interviews carried out with the the writers ($n=14$, aged 62-88). Participants were gathered in Finland through an open writing invitation with no further musical or health-related requirements. This sample of participants was not musically educated, a minority had played an instrument or sung in a choir. All of them had listened to music throughout their lifespan. Majority of the participants were so called healthy older adults, all of them lived in their own homes.

Results Analysis of this data shows that music has contributed to these individuals' identity and wellbeing through 1) offering dynamic anchors towards their musical affective self and into their own life narrative in the past, present and future, 2) adding positive ingredients into their personality and life as it is, and 3) contributing to their wellbeing and identity through music-related emotional work and growth resources, resulting in maintenance or reformation oriented musical identities in older age.

Conclusion Lifelong engagement with music, also in its receptive ways, may have a significant contribution to individuals' identity formation and wellbeing from childhood to older age through the themes of anchors, growth and resources, regardless of their musical backgrounds. These results will contribute to understanding the formation of life-long wellbeing benefits of music among ageing individuals in their everyday lives, and shed light to the age-specific features of the musical identity of older individuals.

References

- DeNora T. Music as a technology of self. In: *Music in Everyday Life*. Cambridge University Press; 2000:46-74.
- Greenberg, D. M., and Rentfrow, P. J. 'The Social Psychological Underpinnings of Musical Identities: A Study on how Personality Stereotypes are formed from Musical Cues', and
- Rickard, N., and Chin, T., 'Defining the musical identity of "non-musicians"' in Raymond MacDonald, David J. Hargreaves, and Dorothy Miell (eds), *Handbook of Musical Identities* (Oxford, 2017; online edn, Oxford Academic, 20 Apr. 2017).
- Ruud E. 2013. Can music serve as a "cultural immunogen"? An explorative study. *Int J Qual Stud Health Well-being*. 2013 Aug 7;8:20597. doi: 10.3402/qhw.v8i0.20597. PMID: 23930988; PMCID: PMC3740498.
- Hays, T., & Minichiello, V. (2005). The meaning of music in the lives of older people: A qualitative study. *Psychology of Music*, 33(4), 437–451.
- Siltainsuu, H., & Peltola, H.-R. (2024). Music as Support for Older Adults' Wellbeing: A Scoping Review. *Music & Science*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20592043241268721>

Understanding Neurological Music Therapy, an intervention for Parkinson's through diffusion tensor imaging

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Background Parkinson's Disease, one of the most commonly known movement disorders, does not have a clinical cure. However, beat-based and rhythmic music stimulation (Cochen De Cock et al., 2021) have significant effect on developing neuroplasticity in the cerebellar-thalamocortical network (Law & Zentner, 2012) of these patients, which not only helps them in managing, planning, and sequencing their movement better but also in slowing down the overall cognitive decline that comes at a later stage of the disease. However, the cognitive construction of music perception through different auditory features and their shared neurological resources with movement that help Parkinson's patients develop neuroplasticity in response to music therapy is not scientifically well understood.

Aims We want to investigate the neural correlates that are shared between processing certain auditory features and governing movements, which helps Parkinson's patients to develop compensatory neuroplasticity. We want to use this information to provide patients with neuroinformed and targeted music therapy.

Methods We used both cognitive and neurological components with PROMS (Profile for Music Perception Skills) (Lesiuk, Bugos & Murakami, 2018) and DTI (diffusion tensor imaging in functional MRI) to investigate these questions. Using PROMS-S, we collected data from 80 participants, of whom 36 were musicians and 44 were non-musicians, based on their objective performance scores in comparing a reference and a target stimulus for various acoustic features. DTI helped understand the integrity of the different white matter tracts associated with processing these acoustic features. We aim to identify training-independent auditory features and their corresponding neural correlates to design targeted and evidence-based Neurologic Music Therapy.

Results The behavioral findings from PROMS-S suggested that for all auditory features, a training effect was observed. Principal Component Analysis revealed the cognitive construction of music perception through auditory features, where non-musicians had the highest loading for tempo, making it a clinically relevant feature for targeted auditory intervention. Melody and rhythm turned out to be unique features for musicians through factor analysis, while tempo and rhythm were unique for non-musicians, making these two features independent of spe-

cific training and explaining the relevance of beat-based and rhythmic intervention, playing a significant role in defining plasticity in literature. Findings from diffusion tensor imaging suggest that musicians have higher white matter integrity in the internal capsule, which plays an important role in movements. This is a clear neurological indication of music therapy being a good tool for movement management in Parkinson's patients. We see higher white matter integrity in the genu of the corpus callosum (Rajan et al., 2021) for musicians for auditory features like rhythm, while non-musicians show higher white matter integrity for temporal and rhythmic features in the splenium, thereby suggesting a double dissociation in beat perception between genu and splenium among musicians and non-musicians.

Conclusions These behavioral and neurological findings help understand the cognitive construction of music perception and the neurological mechanisms of processing these features, which help in movement coordination. It also provides insight regarding how beat-based music therapy can significantly contribute to better management of movements and delay the overall cognitive decline that comes at a later stage of the disease.

References

- Cohen De Cock, V., Dotov, D., Damm, L., Lacombe, S., Ihalainen, P., Picot, M. C., Galtier, F., Lebrun, C., Giordano, A., Driss, V., Geny, C., Garzo, A., Hernandez, E., Van Dyck, E., Leman, M., Villing, R., Bardy, B. G., & Dalla Bella, S. (2021). BeatWalk: Personalized Music-Based Gait Rehabilitation in Parkinson's Disease. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 655121.
- Law, L. N., & Zentner, M. (2012). Assessing musical abilities objectively: construction and validation of the profile of music perception skills. *PLoS one*, 7(12), e52508.
- Lesiuk, T., Bugos, J. A., & Murakami, B. (2018). A Rationale for Music Training to Enhance Executive Functions in Parkinson's Disease: An Overview of the Problem. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*, 6(2), 35.
- Rajan, A., Shah, A., Ingahalikar, M., & Singh, N. C. (2021). Structural connectivity predicts sequential processing differences in music perception ability. *The European journal of neuroscience*, 54(6), 6093–6103.

Talk Session 7

Children and Adolescent Musical Experiences

Chair: Chiara Apa

Time: June 13th, 10:40 – 11:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/j/67606774782>

Children's free descriptions of subjective responses to selected musical extracts reveal new taxonomy of music-evoked experience

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Background Within the abundance of research exploring human responses to music, there is surprisingly little empirical investigation of children's subjective experiences and minimal interest in children's own interpretations of these. One important exception is Herbert and Dibben's (2018) study with adolescents (ages 10–18). Previous work reporting children's feelings and thoughts evoked by music generally presents these in terms of a developing perceptual ability. Measuring their responses against cultural or educational expectations, rather than viewing children's own perspectives as inherently interesting or consequential (a notable exception being the work of John Blacking, e.g., Blacking, 1995), reflects a historical tendency to adopt a deficiency-based approach in much research with children (Minks, 2002). However, young children's own views of their music-induced experiences might be of relevance within music therapy and education, offering important insight into how music begins to evoke meaning for many people. Gabrielsson (2002), among others, suggested music-evoked experience is a complex spectrum from perception to feeling. There remains scope to explore the detail and extent of such a spectrum and consider potential influencing factors. Young children's responses might provide clues to its genesis.

Aims By giving children aged 5 to 11 years a platform to articulate their lived experiences with music from a first-person perspective over a period of three years, this study aims to reveal insight into their processes of musical meaning-making, extending the work of Herbert and Dibben to some of the youngest individuals who are able to express themselves verbally.

Methods In the first of six online experiments within a longitudinal study, children ($n = 44$) listened to seven musical extracts (Eerola & Vuoskoski, 2011; Owen et al., 2024) presented in random order via Qualtrics, and gave free responses to two questions: (i) *How does this music make you feel?* and (ii) *Does the music make you think of or imagine anything?* Thematic analysis of their written responses provided a starting point to explore the detail and scope of their experiences and examine between-participant differences, demographic and stimulus effects.

Results Content analysis of children's written responses revealed 537 concepts and emerging themes aligning with semantic categories identified in previous research with adults (Taruffi & Küssner, 2023), and adolescents (Herbert & Dibben,

2018). Children's responses to both questions included feelings, imagery, narrative, inferences of meaning, critical evaluations and descriptions of musical and expressive elements, illustrating a range of perspectives of the questions asked and indicating considerable variability in the distinction between music-evoked feeling, imagination, and perception. Differences in the egocentricity of children's perspectives reflected age-related expectations in the development of theory of mind.

Conclusions These findings support the theory of a spectrum of music-evoked experience from embodied, intrinsically experienced feelings to detached observations, that might be viewed in terms of distance from the self, intrinsically or extrinsically construed. We offer a taxonomy of music-evoked response, based on these findings, that can be explored further with different populations and musical stimuli.

References

- Blacking, J. (1995). *Venda children's songs: A study in ethnomusicological analysis*. University of Chicago Press, retrieved 1/12/24 from https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=QQv95iAX6H4C&oi=fnd&pg=PA3&ots=YPLV4k0-cD&sig=tH-abwA2J0-1AUzLWypHDTk1htxg&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Eerola, T., & Vuoskoski, J. K. (2011). A comparison of the discrete and dimensional models of emotion in music. *Psychology of Music*, 39(1), 18–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735610362821>
- Gabrielsson, A. (2002). Emotion perceived and emotion felt: Same or different? *Musicae Scientiae, Spec Issue, 2001-2002*, 123–147.
- Herbert, R., & Dibben, N. (2018). Making sense of music: Meanings 10- to 18-year-olds attach to experimenter-selected musical materials. *Psychology of Music*, 46(3), 375–391.
- Minks, A. (2002). From children's song to expressive practices: old and new directions in the ethnomusicological study of children. *Ethnomusicology*, 46(3), 379–408.
- Owen, C., Egermann, H., & Schiavio, A. (2024). Putting musical feelings into words: Children's verbal descriptions of music-evoked experiences. *Music & Science*, 7, 20592043241265318.
- Taruffi, L., & Küssner, M. B. (2023). Visual mental imagery, music, and emotion. In M. B. Küssner, L. Taruffi, & G. A. Floridou (Eds.), *Music and mental imagery* (pp. 32–41). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429330070-4>.

Finnish Adolescents' Experiences of Scary Music: A Qualitative Study

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Background Music-evoked emotions have been researched a great deal in the last years. However, the research on young people's subjective experiences of music-related fear is scarce. Previous studies have found that the will to scare oneself may peak in adolescence (Lawrence and Palmgreen, 1997; Hoffner & Levine, 2005) and that horror can be enjoyable and even have psychological benefits, for instance, in stress or anxiety regulation (Scrivner et al., 2023; Scrivner, 2021). Music is an important tool for young people in emotional work, such as mood regulation (Saarikallio & Erkkilä, 2007).

Aims The aim of this study is to find out how young people experience music-related fear and their subjective experiences and expressions in relation to scary music. Furthermore, this study aims to explore the contexts young people listen to scary music and whether it is used for affect regulation.

Methods The is collected during the spring 2025 in a group discussion using open-ended questions and free discussion; a setting replicated from Peltola's (2017) study. Small groups (3–6 people) of Finnish adolescents, aged 13–18, will be asked to choose a piece of music they find scary. The songs will be listened to in the discussion setting and the participants will be asked to reflect on their experiences. The discussion will be recorded on video and audio. Data is analysed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), and video analysis to examine embodied expressions.

Expected Results Preliminary results will be presented at the conference. It is expected that young peoples' use of scary music varies depending on their personal preferences, and that it is linked to audiovisual and social contexts, such as horror films or horror games either alone or with friends, and that adolescents may also use scary music in affect regulation.

References

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>

Hoffner, C. A., & Levine, K. J. (2005). Enjoyment of Mediated Fright and Violence: A Meta Analysis. *Media Psychology*, 7(2), 207–237. <https://doi.org/10.1207/S153>

2785XMEP0702_5

Lawrence, P. A., & Palmgreen, P. C. (1996). A uses and gratifications analysis of horror film preference. In J. B. Weaver & R. Tamborini (Eds.), *Horror films: Current research on audience preferences and reactions* (pp. 161–178). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.

Peltola, H.-R. (2017). Sharing experienced sadness: Negotiating meanings of self-defined sad music within a group interview session. *Psychology of Music*, 45(1), 82–98. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735616647789>

Saarikallio, S., & Erkkilä, J. (2007). The role of music in adolescents' mood regulation. *Psychology of Music*, 35(1), 88–109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735607068889>

Scrivner, C. (2021, February 4). Scaring away anxiety: Therapeutic avenues for horror fiction to enhance treatment for anxiety symptoms. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/7uh6f>

Scrivner, C., Andersen, M.M., Schjødt, U., Clasen, M., 2023. The Psychological Benefits of Scary Play in Three Types of Horror Fans. *Journal of Media Psychology* 35, 87–98. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-1105/a000354>

The role of non-formal musical and sports engagement in children's development

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Background *MUSPRO* – music, sports, and prosocial behavior project aims at investigating how regular music or physical education (PE) activities might support children's social-emotional (SE) development and executive functions in the early childhood years.

Aims This presentation shows the first results of the project collected before starting the music and PE interventions, aiming at exploring whether previous attendance of similar activities and the amount of music and physical exercise done at home is associated with children's development.

Methods Participants (children and their caregivers) from the early childhood centers were recruited in a Finnish medium-size city. After collecting the informed consents, the caregivers filled in background information regarding children's prior attendance, extracurricular activities, their own music and sports' background, as well as the amount of music and exercise activities at home. Children's (N = 115) verbal fluency, verbal working memory, perceptual IQ, music perception and fundamental motor skills were measured in the daycare premises.

Results According to parental reports, 32 Finnish-speaking children had attended music playschool for 2 - 37 months by the time this data was collected. Preliminary analysis shows that previous attendance in music playschool was associated with better verbal working memory, but not with verbal fluency or perceptual IQ. In terms of physical activity, the preliminarily observed trend was that those children from families engaging in high-intensity physical activities home, had higher locomotor, manipulative and balancing skills. This connection was not found regarding low-intensity physical activities at-home, previous hobbies attendance, or caregivers' background.

Conclusions The role of non-formal and at-home engagement regarding musical and physical activities is discussed along the trends observed in these results. Further longitudinal data from the project is needed to confirm the causal relationship and understand these possible connections deeper.

Talk Session 8

Music's Influence on Cognitive and Emotional Processing

Chair: Sandra Solli

Time: June 13th, 11:40 – 12:30 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/s/67606774782>

Thoughtscapes in music: An examination of thought types occurring during music listening across 17 genres

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Background Music listeners often experience a variety of extramusical thoughts. Some may be evoked directly by the music, such as autobiographical memories, fictional stories or scenes, visual imagery, or observations about features of the music itself (Dahl et al., 2023; Jakubowski et al., 2024). In other cases, listeners may move into a state of mind-wandering, thinking about everyday matters or future plans (Taruffi et al., 2017). Previous studies have typically examined these thought types in isolation, such as just autobiographical memories or fictional stories (Jakubowski & Ghosh, 2021; Margulis, 2017), precluding investigation of why certain music evokes certain thought types over others.

Aims This study investigates how musical genre, familiarity, enjoyment, contrast, and emotional expression (valence and arousal) of music influence the type and frequency of thoughts occurring during music listening across 17 genres. The stimuli represent the array of styles UK and US listeners typically encounter, from art and popular music to media-accompanying music, spanning familiar to unfamiliar music. We aim to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how music- and listener-specific variables affect thought types during music listening.

Methods We systematically curated a stimulus set of 357 music clips spanning 17 frequently listened-to Western music genres: Ambient, Classical, Country, Dance, Electronic, Film music, Folk, Funk, Hip-hop, Jazz, Metal, Pop, Rhythm & Blues (R&B), Rock, Video game, Sixties pop, and Eighties pop music. We collected 30-second sections of commercially released tracks containing no lyrics (allowing non-lexical vocables, such as “oh”, “la”), with each genre containing clips expected to range from high to low familiarity. Participants (N=701) from the UK and US, sampled equally across adulthood (ages 18-75), each listened to and rated 17 excerpts (one from each genre). We analysed the frequency of thoughts occurring during these excerpts, and how these varied in relation to ratings of familiarity, contrast, enjoyment, valence, and arousal of the music. The thought types we analysed, informed by Jakubowski et al., (2024), were: music-related thoughts, autobiographical memories, media memories, fictional imaginings, abstract imaginings, thoughts about “everyday stuff”, and no thoughts.

Results All our predictors showed some significant effects on thought types. Genre impacted all thought types; for example, Film music evoked more media memories and fictional imaginings than most other genres. More familiar and more enjoyed music evoked more autobiographical memories, and more positively valenced and more enjoyed music evoked more fictional imaginings. Music perceived as lower in contrast evoked more thoughts about everyday stuff.

Conclusions Our findings elucidate how compositional and contextual elements and listener engagement may shape thoughts occurring during music listening. The emergence of genre as a key influencer emphasises the importance of incorporating wider ranges of music styles in future research to better capture the diversity of thoughts during music listening. This study extends previous research by exploring a broader range of genres and musical features, offering insights into the mental landscape of thoughts arising, factors that modulate these experiences, informing research and practical applications in areas such as music medicine, marketing, creativity, and aesthetics.

References

Dahl, S., Stella, A., & Bjørner, T. (2023). Tell me what you see: An exploratory investigation of visual mental imagery evoked by music. *Musicae Scientiae*, 27(3), 717-740. Jakubowski, K., Ghosh, A. (2021). Music-evoked autobiographical memories in everyday life. *Psychology of Music*, 49(3), 649-666. Jakubowski, K., Margulis, E. H., Taruffi, L. (2024). Music-Evoked Thoughts: Genre and Emotional Expression of Music Impact Concurrent Imaginings. *Music Perception*, 42(1), 3-18. Margulis, E. H. (2017). An exploratory study of narrative experiences of music. *Music Perception*, 35(2), 235-248. Taruffi, L., Pehrs, C., Skouras, S., & Koelsch, S. (2017). Effects of sad and happy music on mind-wandering and the default mode network. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 14396.

Kinetic affect and the construction of musical emotions.

Mítia Ganade D’Acol

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Background Research in musical emotions has long sought to describe the mechanisms by which musical parameters induce emotion in humans. Many theories of emotional contagion, such as basic emotions (Juslin, 2013a, 2013b, 2019), appraisal theory (Scherer, 2004; Scherer and Coutinho, 2013; Spitzer, 2020), social and psychological construction theories (Warrenburg, 2020; Cespedes-Guevara & Eerola, 2018; Céspedes-Guevara, 2023) rely on quantitative cues such as skin conductivity, physiological changes in the body’s internal milieu, muscular tension, and nervous system activity to describe emotional experience. Yet these measurements often fail to fully account for ways in which musical elements and performance idiosyncrasies lead to experiences of musical emotion, such as in the case of exploring embodied nonverbal communication activities like dance. The theory of kinetic affect addresses this issue by centering on dancers’ bodies as they communicate embodied emotions, while still engaging with questions that drive musical emotion research such as (1) where and when the emotional cues occur (pre- v. post-conscious, predictive v. stimulus-response models), and (2) enculturation of emotional expression and experience (innate v. culturally learned).

Aims I aim to address a gap in the musical emotion literature, which does not wholly account for the unique ways in which ballet and other dance music genres construct and communicate embodied emotion, since studies have been more focused on exploring dance, movement, and music parameters separately. First, I propose a theory of kinetic affect, listing possible parameters with which dancers and audiences engage when experiencing dance spectacles (posture, energy, speed, movement type). Second, I argue how kinetic affect pairs better with embodied and constructive paradigms in emotion theory, reflecting on the efficiency of predictive theories of emotion in music (Meyer, 1956; Huron, 2006). I argue against the inherent fixity of basic emotion and appraisal theories in both music theory and dance studies (Batiste, 2014; Raposo et. al., 2019; Warrenburg et. al., 2020; Cespedes-Guevara & Dibben, 2022). Finally, I demonstrate how kinetic affect can efficiently describe emotions in three stylistic diverse choreographies created for distinct audiences, respectively: Pecour’s setting for the fifth-act passacaglia in Lully’s *Persée*, Francine Lancelot and Béatrice Massin’s setting for the first-act *divertissement* in Lully’s *Atys*, and Bintou Dembélé’s setting for *Danse du Grand Calumet de la Paix* in Rameau’s *Les Indes Galantes*.

Main Contribution By interweaving music and dance analyses, I suggest novel paths to understanding how kinetic affect supports musical emotion expression and experience dancers’ expressive gestures, paired with music’s power for sparking predictive engagement in audiences, provide fertile ground for discussions of how instances of emotion are constructed, expressed, and experienced in context. My analyses demonstrate how kinetic affect efficiently describes affective expression in communities where extremely controlled bodies steer how emotions are felt and experienced, such as in the court of Louis XIV, by analyzing how the slight changes in parameters create strong affective experiences. It also describes how modern stagings can either emulate this type of emotionally controlled experience, such as in Lancelot and Massin’s choreography, or obliterate tradition by choosing an emotionally charged dance style such as Krump—which many times explores the limits of the parameters in kinetic affect—to depict the salvages in Rameau’s *Les Indes Galantes*.

Implications This paper argues that bodies not only feel but, perhaps more importantly, construct and express emotions in socially experienced events. I also support the idea that bodies are in the center of a body-brain-culture construct that is constantly remembering, perceiving, and predicting events that evoke instances of emotion. The argument I provide here primes exploration of how musical and, ultimately, human emotions are constructed and experienced within the context of the community. Future work could adapt kinetic affect as a tool for exploring how we perceive and communicate emotions—providing parameters to be explored in psychological studies, a toolset for musicological investigations of historic emotions, or collaborating to current discussions of aesthetic movement and affect in performance studies.

References

- Batiste, Stephanie L. 2014. “Affect-Ive Moves: Space, Violence, and the Body in Rize’s Krump Dancing.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Dance and the Popular Screen*, edited by Melissa Blanco Borelli, 199–224. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Céspedes-Guevara, Julian. 2023. “A Constructionist Approach to Emotional Experiences with Music.” *Advances in Cognitive Psychology* 19 (4): 46–62. <https://doi.org/10.5709/acp-0402-4>.
- Céspedes-Guevara, Julian, and Tuomas Eerola. 2018. “Music Communicates Affects, Not Basic Emotions – A Constructionist Account of Attribution of Emotional Meanings to Music.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 9 (February):215. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00215>.
- Céspedes-Guevara, Julian, and Nicola Dibben. 2022. “The Role of Embodied Simulation and Visual Imagery in Emotional Contagion with Music.” *Music & Science* 5

(January):20592043221093836. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20592043221093836>.

Huron, David Brian. 2006. *Sweet Anticipation: Music and the Psychology of Expectation*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.

Juslin, Patrik N. 2013a. “From Everyday Emotions to Aesthetic Emotions: Towards a Unified Theory of Musical Emotions.” *Physics of Life Reviews* 10 (3): 235–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plprev.2013.05.008>.

———. 2013b. “What Does Music Express? Basic Emotions and Beyond.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00596>.

———. 2019. *Musical Emotions Explained: Unlocking the Secrets of Musical Affect*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Meyer, Leonard B. 1956. *Emotion and Meaning in Music*. Paperback ed. Chicago, Ill.: Univ. of Chicago Press.

Raposo, Francisco Afonso, David Martins de Matos, and Ricardo Ribeiro. 2019. “Learning Embodied Semantics via Music and Dance Semiotic Correlations.” arXiv:1903.10103 [Cs, Eess], March. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1903.10534>.

Scherer, Klaus R. 2004. “Which Emotions Can Be Induced by Music? What Are the Underlying Mechanisms? And How Can We Measure Them?” *Journal of New Music Research* 33 (3): 239–51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0929821042000317822>.

Scherer, Klaus R, and Eduardo Coutinho. 2013. “How Music Creates Emotion.” In *The Emotional Power of Music: Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Musical Expression, Arousal and Social Control*, edited by Tom Cochrane, Bernardino Fantini, and Klaus R Scherer, 121–46. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.

Spitzer, Michael. 2020. *A History of Emotion in Western Music: A Thousand Years from Chant to Pop*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

Warrenburg, Lindsay A. 2020. “People Experience Different Emotions from Melancholic and Grieving Music.” *Music & Science* 3 (January):205920432097738. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2059204320977384>.

Warrenburg, Lindsay A., Lindsey Reymore, and Daniel Shanahan. 2020. “The Communication of Melancholy, Grief, and Fear in Dance with and without Music.” *Human Technology* 16 (3): 283–309. <https://doi.org/10.17011/ht/urn.202011256766>.

Talk Session 9

Methodological Approaches and Theoretical Frameworks in Music Psychology

Chair: Cesc Bayle

Time: June 13th, 13:30 – 14:20 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/s/67606774782>

Embodiment Indicators in Music Skill Acquisition: A Systematic Review of Psychophysiological and Biomechanical Studies

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Background Music performance has been described as an embodied process (Reybrouck et al., 2024). It is a complex sensorimotor activity that involves acquiring cognitive, motor, and affective skills, which enable performers to coordinate and execute fast, precise movements with expressivity, flexibility, and fluidity (Zatorre et al., 2007). Previous theoretical work argues that this acquisition process is a gradual process of embodiment, during which the instrument becomes integrated into the musician's body and becomes experienced as a natural extension of the self (Nijs et al., 2017). From this perspective, learning to play an instrument impacts the body at three levels: the morphological, functional, and phenomenological level (Nijs et al., 2017; Metzinger, 2024). Building on this framework, we argue that the embodiment process becomes observable in a set of what we call *embodiment indicators*. These are biomechanical and psychophysiological patterns that reflect how the instrument impacts the body through the learning process. Although not explicitly termed as embodiment indicators, these have been studied using psychophysiological and biomechanical methods, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), electrocardiography (ECG), electromyography (EMG), and motion capture (MoCap). Such studies provide insight into the effects of music training on brain plasticity (Altenmüller et al., 2019) and on non-musical perceptual, cognitive, and motor functions (Herholz et al., 2009). They have also been used to investigate psychophysiological activity while performing, giving insight into the neural correlates of actual and imagined music performance, improvisation, sight-reading, and error-processing processes (Altenmüller et al., 2006). Furthermore, these methods have been used to quantify the physical demands of music performance, to help prevent fatigue-related injuries and playing-related musculoskeletal disorders (Schemmann et al., 2021). Additionally, biomechanical methods have been employed to describe and characterize skilled movements (Dalmazzo et al., 2021).

Aims Despite extensive research on the neural and physiological basis of music performance, little attention has been given to how psychophysiological and biomechanical indicators evolve with skill acquisition. To our knowledge, no studies have focused in identifying such indicators across the three levels. To begin addressing this gap, the present review examines studies that use psychophysiological and biomechanical methods to investigate music skill acquisition, with the aim of iden-

tifying embodiment markers that manifest at different levels of expertise. Specifically, we focus on first- and second-order embodiment, referring to morphological and functional changes in the body that occur through learning. By focusing on measurable indicators, this review aims to identify concrete markers that capture the development of embodied expertise in music skill acquisition and performance.

Methods The systematic review was conducted in November 2024, following the PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The inclusion and exclusion criteria were established based on the PICOS framework (Amir-Behghadami et al., 2020). The literature was searched on three databases, including PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus, using relevant search terms. The search strategy was limited by article type, as only peer-reviewed publications were considered. Gray literature was not considered, and we also excluded conferences papers, books and book chapters, reviews, meta-analyses and systematic reviews. The first literature search provided 4462 records. After removing duplicates, 3925 records remained for screening. Of these, 3829 records were excluded based on title and abstract reading. From the screened records, 96 reports were sought for full-text retrieval. Of these, 59 were excluded after full-text reading. In total, 37 studies were identified and included in the systematic review.

Main Contribution The review reports on sample characteristics (e.g., age range, skill level, instrument), skill-level group comparisons, methods used, and the nature of the musical tasks performed. In line with the review's aims, findings are categorized into psychophysiological or biomechanical indicators reflecting processes such as sensorimotor integration functions, neural and muscular efficiency, and motor control. These indicators are interpreted through the lenses of first- and second-order embodiment, capturing morphological and functional changes that occurs during skill acquisition. Limitations of the included studies are also discussed.

Implications By identifying embodiment indicators associated with skill acquisition, this review aims to offer a foundation for understanding the embodied processes underpinning musical learning and performance. It offers a conceptual and methodological bridge between embodied cognition theories and empirical studies of music expertise.

References

- Altenmüller, E., Wiesendanger, M., & Kesselring, J. (Eds.). (2006). *Music, motor control and the brain*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199298723.001.0001>
- Altenmüller, E., Furuya, S., Scholz, D. S., & Ioannou, C. I. (2019). Brain Research in Music Performance. In M. H. Thaut & D. A. Hodges (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook*

of Music and the Brain (pp. 458–486). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198804123.013.19>

Dalmazzo, D., Waddell, G., & Ramírez, R. (2021). Applying Deep Learning Techniques to Estimate Patterns of Musical Gesture. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.575971>

Herholz, S. C., Lappe, C., & Pantev, C. (2009). Looking for a pattern: An MEG study on the abstract mismatch negativity in musicians and nonmusicians. *BMC Neuroscience*, 10, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2202-10-42>

Metzinger, T. (2024). First-Order Embodiment, Second-Order Embodiment, Third-Order Embodiment. In L. Shapiro & S. Spaulding, *The Routledge Handbook of Embodied Cognition* (2nd ed., pp. 37–53). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003322511-6>

Nijs, L. (2017). The Merging of Musician and Musical Instrument. In M. Lesaffre, P.-J. Maes, & M. Leman (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Embodied Music Interaction* (1st ed., pp. 49–57). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315621364-6>

Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>

Reybrouck, M., & Schiavio, A. (2024). Music performance as knowledge acquisition: A review and preliminary conceptual framework. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1331806. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1331806>

Schemmann, H., Rensing, N., & Zalpour, C. (2018). Musculoskeletal Assessments Used in Quantitatively Based Studies About Posture and Movement in High String Players: A Systematic Review. *Medical Problems of Performing Artists*, 33(1), 56–71. <https://doi.org/10.21091/mppa.2018.1009>

Zatorre, R. J., Chen, J. L., & Penhune, V. B. (2007). When the brain plays music: Auditory–motor interactions in music perception and production. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 8(7), 547–558. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2152>

DEEM Instrument: Content Validity Assessments Using Subject Experts

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Background The development and validation of psychological scales follows several stringent stages to construct a measure of practical use and sufficient quality to measure constructs properly. For a new theory, like that of Eerola and colleagues (2024) emotional episodes to music, the process of developing a valid and reliable instrument to measure aspects of the theory is necessary to conduct further empirical investigations. The first stage in this process assesses Content Validity (CV) or how the measure has been constructed; operational definitions, item construction, and judgement about the content of the item pool.

Aims Our primary aim was to create a validated pool of items to represent the theoretical constructs proposed by Eerola and colleagues (2024). Using expert judges (EJ), we investigated whether the universe of items was sufficient to represent and relevant for proposed constructs. As a secondary aim we sought to develop a method for conducting evaluations of CV with EJ which would allow the researcher to make theory driven decisions with both qualitative and quantitative data.

Methods Our method of evaluating the item pool used a recursive process of feedback from EJ ($N = 14$) to evaluate the relevance, representativeness, and face validity of each item. In the first trial, experts rated the relevance of each item along a 4 point scale and provided feedback, for each item, the set of items in a survey, and opinions concerning the possible lack of construct elements. Afterwards, consensus agreement, through use of validity indexes, and expert feedback was combined to improve the item pool and reported back to EJ to review. In the second trial, EJ evaluated the representativeness, alongside rating relevance, of the item pool.

Results The original item pool ($N_{OG} = 495$) was reduced through semantic analysis ($N_S = 345$) and then a first round of expert evaluation of the content ($N_{1T} = 294$) through the use of an adjusted Item-level CV Index (I-CVI; Polit & Beck, 2006) and decisions made by the PI following expert feedback about the items. As the second trial is in progress, we expect to reduce the item pool further, $N_{2T} \approx 200$, by evaluating the content with Scale-Level CVI alongside expert feedback.

Conclusions Results indicate that experts agree on the relevance and representativeness of the item pool. However, further research is needed to support whether

these items are accurate and reliable for measuring the constructs we wish to measure. Our method of evaluating CV allows researchers to approach each step of the process skeptically, decisions are made with multiple pieces of information rather than any single metric, and involves support of a community of researchers rather than a narrow few. The pool of items is sufficient to represent our operational definitions of the constructs adapted from Eerola and colleagues theoretical position (2024).

References

- Eerola, T., Kirts, C., & Saarikallio, S. (2024). Episode model: The functional approach to emotional experiences of music. *Psychology of Music*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/03057356241279763>
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2006). The content validity index: are you sure you know what's being reported? Critique and recommendations. *Research in nursing & health*, 29(5), 489–497. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.20147>

The Origins of Musicality and Music Through an Extended Evolutionary Lens

Oliver Tab Bellmann, Marisa Hoeschele

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Background The origins of musicality and music remain enigmatic, with both genetic-biological and cultural factors likely contributing to their emergence. While various hypotheses have been proposed, a unified understanding of these factors and their interplay in shaping human musical behavior is still lacking.

Aim This talk aims to propose a comprehensive, co-evolutionary framework to integrate existing knowledge and shed light on the evolution of musicality and music. By applying the Extended Evolutionary Synthesis (EES, Feldman & Laland, 1996; Laland et al., 2014, 2015; Whiten et al., 2017), we unify previous proposals on the origins of musical behavior (e.g., niche construction, gene-culture coevolution, inclusive inheritance) and explore how biology and culture interact to drive evolutionary change in this domain.

Main Contribution The EES, a framework from evolutionary biology, emphasizes the interplay between biology and culture, recognizing the latter as a significant driver of evolution. We will argue that by incorporating concepts such as cultural transmission, gene-culture coevolution, and niche construction, we can better understand the complex dynamics underlying the evolution of musicality and music. Our framework centers on the following key mechanisms:

- **Cultural Transmission and Music:** Music, as a socially learned behavior, is transmitted across generations, shaping individual development and influencing the evolution of musicality.
- **Gene-Culture Coevolution:** The interaction between genetic and cultural factors drives the evolution of both biological and cultural traits related to music.
- **Niche Construction:** Humans actively modify their environment through music and other cultural practices, which, in turn, shapes their biological and cognitive development.
- **Ontogeny:** The development of musicality and music involves a complex interplay between biological and cultural factors, with social learning playing a crucial role.

Our contribution represents the first attempt to formally integrate cultural transmission, gene-culture coevolution, niche construction, and ontogeny as independent, integrated, and causal drivers of the evolution of musical behavior. It, thereby, not only unifies previous proposals in a comprehensive framework, but notably, uniquely positions ontogeny as a central hub for understanding the complex interplay of biological and cultural forces shaping the evolution of musicality and music.

Implications By adopting an EES perspective, we can gain a more nuanced understanding of the evolutionary processes that have shaped human musicality and music. Our framework has implications for various related fields, including music psychology, cognitive neuroscience, and evolutionary anthropology, because the proposed mechanisms and their interrelations are not limited to music and musicality, but also other cultural, socially transmitted phenomena. By recognizing the intricate relationship between biology and culture, we can better understand and appreciate the richness and complexity of the sources that fed into the emergence of human musical behavior.

References

- Laland, K., Uller, T., Feldman, M., Sterelny, K., Müller, G. B., Moczek, A., ... & Strassmann, J. E. (2014). Does evolutionary theory need a rethink?. *Nature*, 514(7521), 161-164. <https://doi.org/10.1038/514161a>
- Laland, K. N., Uller, T., Feldman, M. W., Sterelny, K., Müller, G. B., Moczek, A., ... & Odling-Smee, J. (2015). The extended evolutionary synthesis: its structure, assumptions and predictions. *Proceedings of the royal society B: biological sciences*, 282(1813), 20151019. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2015.1019>
- Feldman, M. W., & Laland, K. N. (1996). Gene-culture coevolutionary theory. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 11(11), 453-457. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347\(96\)10052-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347(96)10052-5)
- Whiten, A., Ayala, F. J., Feldman, M. W., & Laland, K. N. (2017). The extension of biology through culture. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(30), 7775-7781. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1707630114>

Talk Session 10

Computational Modeling and Analysis Methods in Music Research

Chair: Hugh Alexander von Arnim

Time: June 13th, 14:30 – 15:20 UTC+2

Location: Forsamlingsalen, Harald Schjelderups Hus

Zoom: <https://uio.zoom.us/s/67606774782>

A New Way of Thinking: A Proposed Methodology for EDM (Electronic Dance Music) Analysis

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Background EDM has always been a diverse area in terms of non-standardised types of analysis where reconstruction, spectrum analysis, score-based translation is some of the methods that we use today (Mazierska, 2021). However, some of these methods are still quite uncomfortable to use or do not adapt enough for sometimes a really unorthodox track that can be created under the umbrella of EDM. Some, in my opinion, really tend to even lose their musical language especially when being extremely scientific for example using classification models (Brink, 2020). As a result for my thesis, with inspiration from various places like Rainer Wehinger's listening score in 1970 (Ivorson, 2017), I came up with a custom, descriptive, chart-based method that is flexible, adaptable and perhaps more importantly, accessible. With tracks to show as test examples, this method could be useful to not standardise EDM analysis at all but to add a way that can consistently analyse with adaptability.

Aims The main aims of this is to propose a new methodology that can be used to analyse EDM tracks in a more descriptive way, compare the chart-based methodology to other methods that already exist and discuss their strengths and weaknesses such as Fogle's phenomenological approach (Fogle, 2011) and parametrical listening (Selle, 2018), and to explore a way to use it to flag moments of authenticity (or inauthenticity) in a track.

Main Contribution Its main contribution hopefully will be a new method that many analysts will have not thought of before for their arsenal as a more descriptive method but also something that can be a powerful tool in realising places of authenticity in a track.

Implications The implications of this suggest a new way of analysing EDM that is more adaptable and perhaps sparks discussion on standardisation but hopefully one of musical language.

References

Brink, Koen van den, 'Finding "The Drop": Recognizing the climax in electronic music using classification models.' (unpublished bachelor's thesis, University of Twente, 2020), pp. 1-6

Fogle, Megan, *Understanding Electronic Music: A Phenomenological Approach*,

(Ann Arbor: Proquest/Umi Dissertation Publishing, 2011)

Ivorson, Jennifer, 'Learning the Studio: Sketches for Mid-Century Electronic Music' *Contemporary Music Review*, 36(5) (2017), pp. 362-387

Mazierska, Ewa, *The Evolution of Electronic Dance Music*, (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2021)

Selle, Andrew, 'Experiencing Sound: A Hybrid Approach to Electronic Music Analysis', (Ann Arbor: Proquest/Florida State University, 2018)

Modelling individual differences in chord pleasantness judgments

Joshua Frank, Peter Harrison

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Background The pleasantness of isolated chords has been modelled extensively in terms of average ratings per stimulus (Smit et al., 2019; Harrison & Pearce, 2020; Eerola & Lahdelma, 2021; Friedman et al., 2021), but individual differences in pleasantness ratings are relatively understudied. Individual differences are present in other domains (e.g., visual aesthetics; McManus, 1980; McManus et al., 2010; Spehar et al., 2016; Bignardi et al., 2024), and may be expected to operate likewise in evaluations of musical chords.

Aims This study aims to build a data-driven understanding of individual differences in chord pleasantness judgments, and relate these individual differences to acoustic features of the stimuli as well as background features of the participants.

Methods 106 participants rated the pleasantness of 68 chords in an online experiment. A questionnaire gathered background information on participants. Principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted on rating data to extract axes of individual difference, which were then related to stimulus and participant features through regression and correlation analyses. Structural equation modelling (SEM) was used to decompose stimulus-level variance into between-participant preference variation and within-participant response noise, which were each correlated with stimulus features.

Results Two primary axes of individual differences were identified using PCA, which were most strongly related to the roughness and cardinality (pitch-class density) of the stimuli. Musical expertise showed a significant correlation with differential responses to roughness, with musically trained participants giving stronger negative responses to rough chords. SEM showed that chords varied widely in the levels of individual difference and measurement noise they support. Individual differences were greatest for smooth chords, and measurement noise was minimised in familiar chords.

Conclusions Common axes of individual differences account for a moderate proportion of variance in chord pleasantness ratings, and can be understood in terms of psychoacoustic features. The features we identify are at odds with the only prior study in this area (McDermott et al., 2010). We also find a possible novel link between musical training and aesthetic evaluation of roughness. Idiosyncratic individual differences manifest to differing degrees in different chords. Rough chords may

show less individual differences due to automatic negative responses, and familiar chords may show less measurement noise due to easier stimulus identification. PCA provides a powerful hypothesis-free method for quantifying individual differences, and SEM variance decomposition may be a useful tool for selecting stimuli in future studies.

References

- Bignardi, G., Smit, D. J. A., Vessel, E. A., Trupp, M. D., Ticini, L. F., Fisher, S. E., & Polderman, T. J. C. 2024. Genetic effects on variability in visual aesthetic evaluations are partially shared across visual domains. *Communications Biology*, 7:55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-05710-4>
- Eerola, T., & Lahdelma, I. 2021. The Anatomy of Consonance/ Dissonance: Evaluating Acoustic and Cultural Predictors Across Multiple Datasets with Chords. *Music & Science*, 4: 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20592043211030471>
- Friedman, R. S., Kowalewski, D. A., Vuvan, D. T., & Neill, W. T. 2021. Consonance Preferences Within an Unconventional Tuning System. *Music Perception*, 38(3): 313-330. <https://doi.org/10.1525/MP.2021.38.3.313>
- Harrison, P. M. C. H., & Pearce, M. T. 2020. Simultaneous Consonance in Music Perception and Composition. *Psychological Review*, 127(2): 216-244. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/>
- McDermott, J. H., Lehr, A. J., & Oxenham, A. J. 2010. Individual Differences Reveal the Basis of Consonance. *Current Biology*, 20(11): 1035-1041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2010.04.019>
- McManus, I. C. 1980. The aesthetics of simple figures. *British Journal of Psychology*, 71: 505-524. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.1980.tb01763.x>
- McManus, I. C., Cook, R., & Hunt, A. 2010. Beyond the Golden Section and Normative Aesthetics: Why Do Individuals Differ so Much in Their Aesthetic Preferences for Rectangles? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 4(2): 113-126. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017316>
- Smit, E. A., Milne, A. J., Dean, R. T., & Weidemann, G. 2019. Perception of affect in unfamiliar musical chords. *PLoS ONE*, 14(6): e0218570. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0218570>
- Spehar, B., Walker, N., & Taylor, R. P. 2016. Taxonomy of Individual Variations in Aesthetic Responses to Fractal Patterns. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 10:350. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2016.00350>

Characterising Sleep Music Preference Through Social Tags

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Background Social tagging - labelling items with short, descriptive pieces of text (e.g., 'happy', 'soft', 'electronic') - is a compact, flexible form of musical representation, previously used towards recommender systems and MIR tasks [1], [2], [3]. This approach constructs a feature space in which each separate 'dimension' (binary label) links explicitly to a high-level semantic property, meaning many different musical factors (mood, timbre, genre, ...) may be considered in parallel. ML models trained on large datasets of user-defined tags (e.g., those found in the Essentia library [4]) are able to produce tagging representations automatically for a given piece of music, while generative models (e.g., MusicGen [5]) can produce new pieces of music based on text prompts. This makes tagging representations controllable, replicable and suitable for large-scale analysis within a musical domain. Individual preference can also be expressed directly in terms of tags, independently of any specific musical stimulus. This flexibility means that a tagging representation of musical preference offers great potential in acting as an intermediary between real-world music, generated stimuli and individual listeners. Compared to general musical preference, preference towards sleep music may be simpler to model, involving a smaller set of practical motivations which would make it more easily characterised in terms of a subset of tags, thus making a compressed representation feasible [6].

Aims This work aims to identify a tag-based representation of sleep music preference which is capable of accurately predicting highly-preferred musical stimuli, given a minimal level of feedback from the individual.

Methods Analysis will first be conducted based on existing large datasets of sleep music (e.g., [7]), using various ML models to extract and identify a subset of tags which consistently characterise individual preferences towards music for sleep, thereby defining a reduced 'tagging space'. These tags will then be used as an input for generative models, producing a set of brief musical stimuli which evenly cover the reduced space - i.e., every possible combination of tags. These stimuli will eventually be used within an online study, in which the predictive capability of a participant's expressed sleep music preference (via the tagging representation) is validated through pairwise comparison.

Expected Results Two sets of tags will be identified through the analysis: a “static set”, which characterises sleep music as a whole, and a ‘variable set”, which characterises an individual’s preference towards sleep music, within the range of music typically used for sleep. A systematic analysis of the different available generative models will also be conducted, validating that their output produces a stimulus which is consistent with the original tag input. Finally, the online study expects individual participants to show an above-chance selection of the stimuli which correspond to their own expressed tagging preferences.

Conclusions This work focuses on a systematic, data-driven approach to identifying a tag-based representation for sleep music preference. This yields many applications, including personalised music recommendation, adaptive music generation, and tailored sleep intervention. The representation will eventually be validated through an online study, which also investigates the relation of such preferences to individual factors (e.g., age, personality, music listening habits).

References

- [1] Lamere, P. (2008). Social tagging and music information retrieval. *Journal of new music research*, 37(2), 101-114.
- [2] Lin, Y. C., Yang, Y. H., & Chen, H. H. (2011). Exploiting online music tags for music emotion classification. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)*, 7(1), 1-16.
- [3] Nanopoulos, A., Rafailidis, D., Symeonidis, P., & Manolopoulos, Y. (2009). Musicbox: Personalized music recommendation based on cubic analysis of social tags. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 18(2), 407-412.
- [4] Alonso-Jiménez, P., Bogdanov, D., Pons, J., & Serra, X. (2020, May). Tensorflow audio models in essentia. In *ICASSP 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (pp. 266-270). IEEE.
- [5] Copet, J., Kreuk, F., Gat, I., Remez, T., Kant, D., Synnaeve, G., ... & Défossez, A. (2023). Simple and controllable music generation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 47704-47720.
- [6] Trahan, T., Durrant, S. J., Müllensiefen, D., & Williamson, V. J. (2018). The music that helps people sleep and the reasons they believe it works: A mixed methods analysis of online survey reports. *PloS one*, 13(11), e0206531.
- [7] Scarratt, R. J., Heggli, O. A., Vuust, P., & Jespersen, K. V. (2023). The audio features of sleep music: Universal and subgroup characteristics. *PLoS One*, 18(1), e0278813.